

NERSC TECHNICAL REPORT No. 207

ESA ESTEC Contract No. 13971/00/NL/DC

**THE QUANTIFICATION OF THE IMPORTANCE OF THE SEA ICE
BUDGET IN THE CLIMATE SYSTEM**

Final report

Task 1 : Status of sea ice models and data assimilation

Task 2: Basic model scenarios including validation

Task 3: Mission capabilities for sea ice thickness retrieval

***Task 4: Simulated ice thickness data from radar altimeter, and
Assimilation of simulated ice thickness data into
a coupled ice-ocean model***

Task 5: Summary and recommendations

Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center, Bergen, Norway
and
Centre for Polar Observations and Modelling
Department of Space and Climate Physics, University College London, UK

November 2001

**UNIVERSITY COLLEGE LONDON
DEPARTMENT OF SPACE AND CLIMATE
PHYSICS, CENTRE FOR POLAR
OBSERVATIONS AND MODELLING (UCL)**

Gower Street
London, WC1 6BT
Phone: 44 20 7679 3932
Fax: 44 20 7419 7883
e-mail: swl@cpom.ucl.ac.uk

**NANSEN ENVIRONMENTAL AND REMOTE
SENSING CENTER (NERSC)**

Edv. Griegsvei 3a
N-5059 Bergen, Norway
Phone: +47 55 29 72 88
Fax: +47 55 20 00 50
e-mail: stein.sandven@nrsc.no
<http://www.nrsc.no>

<p>TITLE Study on the Quantification of the Importance of the Sea Ice Budget in the Climate System Final report</p>	<p>REPORT IDENTIFICATION NERSC Technical Report no. 207</p>
<p>CLIENT ESA ESTEC</p>	<p>CONTRACT 13971/00/NL/DC</p>
<p>CLIENT REFERENCE Helge Rebhan</p>	<p>AVAILABILITY Open</p>
<p>INVESTIGATORS S. Sandven, S. Laxon, H. Drange, K. A. Lisæther, H. Sagen, G. Evensen</p>	<p>AUTHORISATION Bergen: November 2001 DIRECTOR Ola M. Johannessen</p>

Chapters

Executive summary

Chapter 1: The status of sea ice models and data assimilation **section 1**

Chapter 2: Basic model scenarios including validation **section 2**

Chapter 3: Mission capabilities for sea ice thickness retrieval **Section 3**

Chapter 4: Simulated ice thickness data from radar altimeter **Section 4**

Chapter 5: Assimilation of simulated ice thickness data into a coupled ice-ocean model **Section 5**

Chapter 6: Summary and Recommendations **Section 6**

References

Appendix

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The overall objective is to *quantify the importance of a better knowledge of sea ice budget on relevant climate processes such as freshwater budget, thermohaline circulation and deep water formation.*

The retrieval of the key parameter sea ice thickness from remote sensing techniques poses a major challenge compared with the observation of sea ice extent and ice concentration. The specific objectives of this study are:

- To examine the sensitivity of state of the art dynamic-thermodynamic sea ice models to changes in sea ice thickness.
- To derive observation requirements (e.g. requirements for accuracy, repeatability and temporal-spatial coverage) scenarios for the estimation of sea ice thickness in the Arctic.
- Perform a sensitivity study of the importance of sea ice volume fluxes for freshwater budgets, thermohaline circulation and deep water formation in high latitude regions. Based on the results the observation requirements for ice thickness the analysis shall be updated and refined.

In order to meet these objectives five tasks have been conducted.

Task 1- The status of sea ice models and data assimilation.

Task 2- Basic model scenario including validation

Task 3- Mission capabilities for sea ice retrieval

Task 4- Simulation scenarios

Task 5- Summary and recommendation

In Task 1 the fundamental physics and model formulations for dynamic-thermodynamic sea ice models are reviewed. The model equations are described including the most common rheologies. The coupled ice-ocean model at the Nansen Center, consisting of the MICOM ocean model and Hibler's viscous-plastic ice model, is described and used for the basic model scenario in Task 2. Satellite observation techniques and their use in sea ice models are discussed, emphasizing the passive microwave data which is the only data set covering all sea ice areas globally and is obtained regularly for more than 20 years. The most important data sets are ice area and concentration from satellite passive microwave data and ice velocity data from drifting buoys and satellite data. Retrieval of ice thickness data from satellite altimeter is discussed based on recent analysis of ERS data carried out at UCL. The results of the Sea Ice Model Intercomparison Project (SIMIP) are reviewed where the performance of different ice rheologies are assessed. Finally, satellite data assimilation in ice models is mentioned, reflecting that only limited work has been done in this field. New results of data assimilation carried out in this project is discussed in chapter 5.

Task 2 describes the 40 years of simulations which have been done with the NERSC coupled ice-ocean model, addressing the model assumptions, the NCEP forcing data and the model output data. The other major effort in Task 2 has been the compilation and analysis of data sets for comparison and validation of the basic model scenario. Ice thickness data sets from Upward-Looking Sonars on submarines and fixed moorings in the Fram Strait were compiled and used to compare with ice thickness from the model. Ice velocity data from the Arctic Ocean Buoy Programme and satellite data from NOAA were also used to compare with the model simulations. The most extensive model validation has been done for ice extent and concentration, where merged SMMR and SSMI data have been used to assess the basic model scenario. UCL has also made a comparison of ERS altimeter thickness with the model simulations at University of Kiel and the Hadley Centre,

showing promising results of the altimeter-derived thickness estimates. The conclusion of the NERSC ice – ocean model simulations is that the coupled model gives a good description of the sea ice variations and trends in the Arctic, although some tuning of the performance might be necessary.

Parallel model experiments were conducted with perturbed freshwater discharge in to the Arctic Ocean. These experiments showed that increased freshwater discharge leads to reduced sea surface salinity and increased sea surface temperature in the central Arctic. This will furthermore lead to increased melting of ice and intensified Beaufort Gyre, which in turn increases the volume transport through the Arctic Archipelago. To compensate for this southward transport of mass, more warm and saline Atlantic Water is carried northward, leading to an increased heat transport to the Nordic Seas. The increased transport of salt to the North Atlantic and the Nordic Seas thus counteract the impact of the increased freshwater runoff in the Arctic, and tends to stabilize the thermohaline circulation.

Task 3 is focused on developing a sea ice simulation model for a beam-limited altimeter planned to be used on CryoSat. Synthetic observations of sea ice have been generated using a number of mission scenarios combined with models describing the statistical and surface properties of sea ice that may affect the quality of the observations. The ultimate aim is to provide a look up table which, for a given instrument, describes the error in ice thickness retrieval for a given ice/snow thickness, ice concentration and surface melt state. There are three key elements to the generation of an instrument surface model. The first is the generation of a realistic model, FGM (Floe Geometry Model), for the two dimensional geometry of an ice field which describes the horizontal distribution of ice and water within the instrument field of view. The second is to superimpose realistic vertical topography based on a given mean snow and ice thickness. The third is to attribute backscatter characteristics to the ice and water surfaces within the footprint depending on snow cover and the state of surface melt. The simulations provided the first comprehensive and quantitative view of likely CryoSat performance under a variety of different ice conditions. The data sets generated could provide the basis for the development and optimisation of more sophisticated processing systems required for CryoSat level 1.5 and 2 processing.

The work of Task4 has been divided into two subtasks:

4.1 Scenarios of simulated ice thickness measurements from radar altimeter

4.2 Assimilation of simulated ice thickness data into a coupled ice-ocean model

In Sub-Task 4.1 a set of synthetic data on freeboard and thickness measurements was generated by the CryoSat altimeter system. The raw thickness data were derived from ice-ocean model outputs supplied by NERSC in Task 2, which also provided ice concentration, snow thickness and ice temperature. These data were then modulated to account for the instrumental and geophysical errors that are likely to be introduced for the real system. The errors are derived from the instrument simulations carried out in Task 3 and broadly depend on surface state parameters including ice concentration, thickness, temperature and backscatter co-efficient. The surface state parameters also govern circumstances where no retrieval is possible according to experience gained from the ERS radar altimeters. The spatial and temporal sampling characteristics are achieved using a synthesised CryoSat orbit for a period of 12 months. The dependencies of retrieval error on model surface state parameters including ice concentration, ocean/ice backscatter contrast and ice thickness have been determined.

We have also generated a dataset with realistic spatial and temporal sampling characteristics though using a CryoSat simulated orbit coupled with criteria for the generation of ‘null’ data where temperature or concentration criteria are not satisfied. Within areas of valid data the percentage of ice retrievals is used to control the percentage of additional null data and the percentage of ocean retrievals is used to modulate the error in average ocean level determination. Simulated monthly mean ice thickness data sets have been generated for two years, based on simulation results in task 2: 1987 which had relatively much ice and 1990 with relatively little ice. Each data set was produced with three different variances to simulate various degrees of accuracy in satellite-derived ice thickness data.

In Sub-Task 4.2 simulated sea ice thickness data were assimilated into a coupled sea ice/ocean model to investigate the sensitivity of using CryoSat-like data in sea ice modelling. Several experiments were performed to assess the impact of this assimilation on the model state by varying the observation error variance. The model experiments were performed for two years, 1987 (a year with relatively much ice – low NAO year) and 1990 (a year with relatively little ice – high NAO year). The observational data used was the synthetic CryoSat dataset from sub-task 4.1. Specifically we varied the observation error variance by multiplying it with factors in the range from 0.25 to 100 to examine the effect it had on the assimilation step. The assimilation scheme chosen for the experiment was the Optimal Interpolation (OI) scheme. The time step in the assimilation scheme was 15 days, except in the melt season when no data were available.

The experiments performed in this study have shown that the synthetic observations of ice thickness have an error variance which is low enough to have a strong impact on the analyzed ice thickness fields in the analysis scheme. The experiments showed that only a few assimilation steps were required to obtain e-folding of the RMS distance between the modeled and the observed ice thickness field, using the original error variance of the observations, which represent a typical measurement sample error of 0.5 m. In this case the experiments showed that the data had a strong “pull” on the model state. Similar results were obtained for the experiments where the error variance was multiplied by a factor of 0.25 and 4. However, when this factor was increased to 100 (corresponding to a typical measurement sample error of ≈ 5 m), the experiments showed that it would take at least 20 analysis updates to obtain an e-folding of the RMS distance. This translates into 1500 days of model run to obtain the e-folding, not taking into account the melt period when no observations are available, indicating that the data had much weaker “pull” on the model state.

The conclusion of the assimilation experiments for ice thickness, with the given assimilation method and data updated every 15 days, is that a data field with measurement error of ≈ 1 m will have significant effect on the analyzed fields.

Task 5 gives an overall summary of the project results including limitations of the current study and recommendations for the future. These include:

Improvements to the CryoSat simulations and synthetic data sets.

- 1 Simulations should be carried out using the more advanced CryoSat (CRYMPS) simulator in development at MSSL.
- 2 More sophisticated ice/water discrimination and re-tracking procedures should be used in line with prototyping of the IPF software.
- 3 More comprehensive retrieval error statistics should be obtained through ensemble (rather than single) runs over the different ice surface scenarios. In particular the location and orientation of the synthetic ground track should be varied.

- 4 Observations of ice concentration and surface melting (from SSM/I and re-analyses data) should be used to prescribe changes in surface conditions likely to affect the retrievals on a daily basis.

Assimilation schemes:

The present experiments only represent an initial study, and more assimilation experiments are needed with other and more advance assimilation schemes such as Ensemble Kalman Filter.

Chapter 1. The status of sea ice models and data assimilation (Task 1)

Contents

1.1 REVIEW OF DYNAMIC-THERMODYNAMIC SEA ICE MODELS.....	2
1.1.1 <i>Fundamental physics</i>	2
1.1.2 <i>Model development</i>	2
1.2 MODEL EQUATIONS.....	4
1.2.1 <i>The momentum equation</i>	4
1.2.2 <i>Sea ice rheologies</i>	5
1.2.3 <i>Sea ice strength</i>	7
1.2.4 <i>Compactness and Thickness</i>	8
1.3 SEA ICE AREA AND CONCENTRATION FROM SATELLITE DATA AND THEIR USE IN SEA ICE MODELS.....	9
1.3.1 <i>Introduction to SSM/I, AVHRR and SAR data</i>	9
1.3.2 <i>Ice area from merged SMMR and SSM/I series</i>	9
1.4 ICE MOTION DATA.....	12
1.4.1 <i>Satellite data</i>	12
1.4.2 <i>Ice drift data from Arctic Ocean Buoy Program</i>	13
1.5 SEA ICE FREEBOARD ESTIMATES FROM SPACEBORNE ALTIMETRY.....	13
1.5.1 <i>Introduction</i>	13
1.5.2 <i>Altimeter data</i>	14
1.5.3 <i>Return echoes over sea ice</i>	14
1.5.4 <i>Ice elevation estimates</i>	17
1.5.5 <i>Calibration/Validation of altimeter estimates</i>	17
1.6 ASSESSMENT OF THE MODEL PERFORMANCES, AS FAR AS THEY ARE KNOWN.....	18
1.6.1 <i>Ice thickness estimates</i>	19
1.6.2 <i>Ice extent estimates</i>	20
1.6.3 <i>Ice drift</i>	21
1.7 ICE THICKNESS DATA FOR MODEL VALIDATION.....	24
1.7.1 <i>Ice thickness distribution</i>	25
1.7.2 <i>Submarine Upward Looking Sonar Ice Draft Profile data and Statistics</i>	25
1.7.3 <i>Bottom moored upward looking sonar's in the Fram Strait</i>	27
1.8 COMPARISON OF ICE THICKNESS DATA FROM ERS WITH MODEL SIMULATIONS.....	27
1.8.1 <i>Comparison with the University of Kiel sea ice model</i>	28
1.8.2 <i>Comparison with HADCOM</i>	29
1.8.3 <i>Trends in Arctic ice thickness</i>	31
1.9 DATA ASSIMILATION ASPECTS.....	33

Objective

The objective is to provide an overview of the currently used dynamic-thermodynamic sea ice models, describing ice rheologies and to what extent satellite data are used in the models. The performance of the models shall be assessed as far as it is possible.

This task will be based on literature survey, ongoing modelling work at NERSC and results provided by The Sea Ice Model Intercomparison Project (SIMIP) headed by Peter Lemke (Lemke, 1997). The objectives of this project is to develop better representation of sea ice in climate models. Efforts are focused on 1) producing a standard forcing and verification data set, 2) developing a model hierarchy from which the optimal model is derived.

1.1 REVIEW OF DYNAMIC-THERMODYNAMIC SEA ICE MODELS

1.1.1 Fundamental physics

The following fundamental assumptions are used:

- Thermal and dynamic forcing on upper and lower ice surface
- Energy balance: sum of the radiation and heat exchange acting on the ice-air, ice-snow and ice-water interfaces. The annual growth and decay of ice is largely determined by the energy balance.
- Momentum balance: sum of wind, current, Coriolis and internal forces acting on the ice pack. The short-term ice motion, fracturing, ridging and lead formation are determined by the momentum balance.
- Seasonal advance and retreat of the ice cover on regional and hemispheric scale is strongly determined by ice transport as well as ocean heat flux.

1.1.2 Model development

In dynamic sea ice models it is common to treat sea ice as a two-dimensional continuum where snow and ice thickness, compactness and horizontal velocity are the main variables. Newer models include additional prognostic variables such as ice roughness and age (Harder, 1997; Steiner et al., 1998) or a more complete treatment of the ice thickness distribution (Flato and Hibler, 1995). The prognostic equations are derived from conservation equations for snow and ice mass and area, and from a momentum balance including internal ice stress.

Dynamic-thermodynamic sea ice models consists of four major components:

- 1 A surface energy balance to compute the surface temperature from the atmospheric forcing and the heat conduction through the ice:
- 2 A model for the heat conduction through the ice for given surface temperature and oceanic heat flux into the ice;
- 3 A momentum balance including acceleration, Coriolis force, atmospheric and oceanic stress, sea surface tilt and internal ice stress from which the ice velocity is calculated

- 4 Budget equations for snow and ice mass and ice-covered area. These budget equations use the sea ice velocity and the freezing/melting rate determined from the heat conduction model together with the surface energy balance for ice and open water to calculate the temporal evolution of snow and ice thickness and area coverage in each grid cell.

The pattern of the net freezing rate depends mainly on sea ice dynamics (i.e. atmospheric and ocean forcing) and on the physical model describing sea ice dynamics. The most important difference between existing dynamic ice models lies in the treatment of the internal ice stress, which is formulated in the ice rheology.

There are essentially three different sea ice rheology schemes that are used for sea ice modelling today. The schemes are known as the viscous-plastic (VP), the cavitating fluid (CF), and the elastic-viscous-plastic (EVP) rheologies. The VP rheology dates back to the classical work of Hibler (1979), the most used cavitating fluid scheme is described by Flato and Hibler (1992), whereas the EVP rheology is discussed in a recent paper by Hunke and Dukowicz (1999). These rheologies are defined in section 1.2.2

The sea ice states produced by the different schemes are, generally speaking, quite similar at coarse spatial resolution (for instance 100 km or more), and when weekly or longer time averaged surface wind fields are used. For synoptic (6 hourly to daily) wind fields, the EVP scheme is expected to be superior to the other schemes. The assessment of different rheologies in climate studies are reviewed by Kreyscher et al., (2000) and is summarised in section 1.2.2.

The first ice models were pure thermodynamic models simulating the seasonal growth and decay of sea ice: i.e. Maykut and Untersteiner (1971), Semtner (1976), Lemke et al., (1990). One of the first dynamic-thermodynamic models were developed by Parkinson and Washington (1979). It was a 3-D model with four vertical layers: ocean mixed layer, ice layer, snow layer and atmospheric boundary layer. Free-drift ice dynamics was used.

Hibler included the effect of internal ice stress, treating ice as viscous, elastic, viscous-plastic (Hibler, 1979) or elastic-plastic medium (Hibler, 1986). An intermediate approach is the "cavitating fluid" approximation, which differs from free drift by allowing nonzero ice pressure under converging conditions, but, like free drift, offers no resistance to divergence or shear (Flato and Hibler, 1992).

The first coupled ice-ocean model was presented by Hibler and Bryan (1987), which coupled the Hibler ice model to the Bryan-Cox multilevel ocean model (Bryan, 1969). This model, which is initialized by climatological temperature and salinity, shows that parts of the Barents and Greenland seas are kept ice-free through the winter, but is less realistic with the ice thickness estimates.

Hakkinen and Mellor (1992) studied the large-scale variability of the Arctic ice using an 18-layer ocean model coupled to a 3-level snow-ice model. The viscous-plastic rheology scheme by Hibler (1979) have been used with other ocean models, i.e the ECHAM/OPYC coupled model (Oberhuber, 1992).

At the Nansen Center, the MICOM (Miami Isopycnic Coordinate Ocean Model) (Bleck et al., 1992) has been coupled to a dynamic-thermodynamic sea ice model using Hibler's viscous-plastic rheology modified by Harder (1996). A favourable aspect of MICOM is the ability to provide high vertical resolution in regions of strong vertical density gradients and to suppress artificial numerical

diffusion across isopycnals, both are important properties of the modelling of the Arctic Ocean. The validation of the MICOM-Hibler model has been done by comparing ice extent and concentration with passive microwave satellite data since 1978 (Lisæther et al., 2000). Another isopycnic model (Oberhuber, 1993) already used in the Arctic (Holland et al., 1996) has shown that this type of ocean model has the capability of doing well there.

Most of the General Circulation Models from climate research (GCMs) use pure thermodynamic sea ice models or models with simplified advection schemes (IPCC, 1996). Only few GCMs use more sophisticated dynamic-thermodynamic sea ice models where internal forces are described by a sea ice rheology.

In order to study the impact of different rheologies on the large-scale properties of the sea ice cover, the Sea Ice Model Intercomparison Project (SIMIP) is testing a number of models which are using the same grid, thermodynamic formulations and forcing fields. Results of this project are in publication (Kreyscher et al., 2000). Comparison of model results with sea ice data is done in a number of ongoing studies.

1.2 MODEL EQUATIONS

Sea ice dynamics describes how momentum is transferred through the sea ice system by equations representing the following elements

- 1) Momentum equation which describes the forces that determine drift and deformation of sea ice
- 2) Sea ice rheology
- 3) Ice strength
- 4) Ice compactness and thickness

1.2.1 The momentum equation.

The two-dimensional momentum equations used are (Hibler, 1979) given by

Equation 1

$$m \frac{D\mathbf{u}}{Dt} = -mf\mathbf{k} \times \mathbf{u} + \boldsymbol{\tau}_a + \boldsymbol{\tau}_w + \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma} - mg\nabla H$$

where $\frac{D\mathbf{u}}{Dt} = \frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla$ is the material derivative. \mathbf{u} is the horizontal ice velocity, m is the ice mass per unit area, \mathbf{k} is a unit vector normal to the ice surface, f is the Coriolis parameter, H is the elevation of the sea surface relative to the geoid, and the forces due to internal ice stresses are given by $\nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}$ where $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ is the stress tensor. The notation $\mathbf{k} \times \mathbf{u}$ refers to the two first components of this cross product. $\boldsymbol{\tau}_a$ and $\boldsymbol{\tau}_w$ are the atmosphere and water stresses acting upon the ice, respectively. The stresses are determined from non-linear integral boundary layer theories

Equation 2

$$\boldsymbol{\tau}_a = \rho_a C_a |\mathbf{u}_a^*| [\mathbf{u}_a \cos \Phi_a + \mathbf{k} \times \mathbf{u}_a \sin \Phi_a]$$

Equation 3

$$\boldsymbol{\tau}_w = \rho_w C_w |\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{u}_w| [(\mathbf{u}_w - \mathbf{u}) \cos \Phi_w + \mathbf{k} \times (\mathbf{u}_w - \mathbf{u}) \sin \Phi_w]$$

where ρ_a is the density of the air and C_a is the air drag coefficient, ρ_w and C_w are the corresponding quantities for water. The vector \mathbf{u}_w is the ocean current, and \mathbf{u}_a is the geostrophic wind velocity, typically much higher than ice velocity. Φ_w , Φ_a are water and wind turning angles. Analysis of the

forces show that the air and water drag and the internal stresses are the most important terms in Equation 1. The air drag is highly fluctuating, and is often the most important on short timescales, whereas the more constant water drag plays an important role over longer timescales.

1.2.2 Sea ice rheologies

Of the forces present in Equation 1 the most elusive is perhaps the internal ice stresses $\nabla \cdot \sigma$ where $\sigma = \sigma_{ij} \mathbf{i}_i \mathbf{i}_j$ is the symmetric stress tensor.

$$\nabla \cdot \sigma = \frac{\partial \sigma_{ik}}{\partial x_i} \mathbf{i}_k$$

The stress tensor σ_{ij} is based upon the properties of sea ice, and represents contact forces between individual ice floes. The determination of a realistic constitutive law relating the ice stress to deformation is critical to understand ice drift and deformation.

In large scale dynamic sea-ice models studying long term variations the usual approach is to describe sea ice as a two-dimensional continuum (Gray and Morland, 1994). Ice floe collision models have been considered for use in the MIZ and in situations where the model resolution is so high that the individual interaction between ice floes becomes important. As the work in this project is related to climatic changes in ice thickness main focus will be on models using a continuum description of the sea ice.

In the ice pack the continuum approach is not strictly correct as floes have dimensions of 10^3 - 10^4 , the variables represent mean area values rather than point values. With this background the development of a sea-ice rheology is a difficult task. Ice floe collision rheology is used when the resolution in the model becomes comparable with the individual floe size.

Several approaches to sea-ice rheologies exist that are based on demands upon physical properties and computational efficiency. Suggested rheologies are the elastic-plastic approach (Coon et al. 1974), the viscous-plastic (Hibler, 1979), the cavitating fluid (Flato and Hibler, 1992), the granular material (Tremblay and Mysak, 1997) and the collision-induced rheology (Shen et al. 1997).

The sea ice rheology is given by the constitutive equations which connects the forces acting at a material particle with the history of both the local geometry of the local deformation and temperature. Formally, this can be written as

$$\sigma_{ij} = f_{ij}(u_{i,j}, h, A, T_i)$$

where $u_{i,j} = \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_j}$ is the velocity gradient which can be written as

$$u_{i,j} = \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_j} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x_i} \right) + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_j} - \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x_i} \right) = \underbrace{\dot{\epsilon}_{ij}}_{\text{stretching strain rate tensor}} + \underbrace{\dot{\Omega}_{ij}}_{\text{spin tensor}}$$

h , A and T_i is the ice thickness, ice concentration and ice temperature, respectively.

The viscous-plastic, which is the most frequently used rheology within sea ice dynamics, include both viscous and rigid plastic rheologies. In general, a viscous rheology is defined as one in which stress can only be sustained through non-recoverable dissipation of energy by deformation. A plastic rheology is one in which stress can be sustained through the lack of deformation or

deformation where the energy is recoverable. Commonly used sea ice rheologies are summarised in Table 1.1

Table 1.1 Sea ice rheologies, governing equations and characteristics

Sea ice rheologies	Contimuum	Covering constitutive law	Comments/Characteristics
Caviating fluid	fluid	$\nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\tau} = -\nabla p^*$	The pack ice has a plastic behaviour in the case of compression deformation and allows divergence without any internal stresses.
Linear Elastic	solid	$\sigma_{ij} = \lambda \dot{\epsilon}_{kk} \delta_{ij} + 2\mu \dot{\epsilon}_{ij}$ λ and μ are Lamé constants	Can be used to study small scale oscillatory processes which do not allow an-elastic processes to act in any significant ways (eq. Ice coupled surface waves propagating in dense ice)
Viscoelastic	solid	$\sigma \propto \dot{\epsilon}(t)$	Time dependency in strain relation is introduced in the equations.
Elastic-plastic	solid	$\sigma_{ij} = \zeta \dot{\epsilon}_{kk} \delta_{ij} + 2\eta \left(\dot{\epsilon}_{ij} - \frac{1}{2} \dot{\epsilon}_{kk} \delta_{ij} \right)$ ζ and η are the bulk and shear moduli.	A time dependent kinematic condition between elastic and plastic deformation is given in Pritchard, 1988. Changes in the elastic strain arises from rotation and stretching of the material. Elastic waves may occur (Hibler,)
Viscous-plastic	fluid	$\sigma_{ij} = 2\eta \dot{\epsilon}_{ij} + [\zeta - \eta] \dot{\epsilon}_{kk} \delta_{ij} - \frac{P}{2} \delta_{ij}$ ζ and η are the non-linear bulk and shear viscosities and P is a pressure term	Yield surfaces has to be given, the most frequently used is an elliptical surface.
Elastic- Viscous - Plastic	fluid	$\sigma_{ij} = 2\eta(\dot{\epsilon}_{ij}, P) \dot{\epsilon}_{ij} + [\zeta(\dot{\epsilon}_{ij}, P) - \eta(\dot{\epsilon}_{ij}, P)] \dot{\epsilon}_{kk} \delta_{ij} - \frac{P}{2} \delta_{ij}$	The inclusion of viscoelastic properties is not for making the model more realistic but to make the numerics more trackable (Hunke et al)
Granular sea ice model.	Granular	$\sigma_{ij} = 2\eta \dot{\epsilon}_{ij} + \eta \dot{\epsilon}_{kk} \delta_{ij} - \frac{P}{2} \delta_{ij}$, where $\eta = \min \left(\frac{p \sin \phi}{\sqrt{(\dot{\epsilon}_{11} - \dot{\epsilon}_{22})^2 + 4\dot{\epsilon}_{12}^2}}, \eta_{\max} \right)$	Elastic properties are neglected. For small deformation the friction coefficient $\eta = \eta_{\max}$ is constant and sea ice behaves as a very viscous fluid.

* P is the ice pressure which is parameterised later on.

1.2.3 Sea ice strength

The NERSC model uses an implementation of Hibler's viscous-plastic rheology (Harder, 1996), and the nonlinear viscous-plastic fluid obeys the following constitutive law

Equation 4

$$\sigma_{ij} = 2\eta(\dot{\epsilon}_{ij}, P) \dot{\epsilon}_{ij} + [\zeta(\dot{\epsilon}_{ij}, P) - \eta(\dot{\epsilon}_{ij}, P)] \dot{\epsilon}_{kk} \delta_{ij} - \frac{P}{2} \delta_{ij}$$

Here $\dot{\epsilon}_{ij} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x_i} \right)$ is the strain rate tensor, and repeated indices denote summation. The law describes a **nonlinear viscous fluid** with a pressure term P , bulk viscosity $\zeta(\dot{\epsilon}_{ij}, P)$ and shear viscosity $\eta(\dot{\epsilon}_{ij}, P)$.

To close the equations appropriate values must be determined for all these terms. The pressure P is parametrized from thickness and ice concentration later. To determine bulk and shear viscosities a plastic yield curve in principal stress space is prescribed along with a normal flow rule (vector representation of strain rate invariants are normal to the yield curve). The most commonly used curve for sea ice is the elliptic yield curve as prescribed in (Hibler, 1997), and with the calculations covered there the bulk viscosity $\zeta(\dot{\epsilon}_{ij}, P)$ and shear viscosity $\eta(\dot{\epsilon}_{ij}, P)$ are given by

Equation 5

$$\zeta = \frac{P}{2} \Delta$$

Equation 6

$$\eta = \frac{\zeta}{e^2} \Delta$$

Equation 7

$$\Delta = \left[(\dot{\epsilon}_{11}^2 + \dot{\epsilon}_{22}^2) \left(1 + \frac{1}{e^2} \right) + 4e^{-2} \dot{\epsilon}_{12}^2 + 2\dot{\epsilon}_{11}\dot{\epsilon}_{22} \left(1 - \frac{1}{e^2} \right) \right]^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

The parameter e is related to the shape of the elliptic yield curve in principal stress space and is the ratio of the major and minor axis. For very small strain rates a maximal value is prescribed for the bulk and shear viscosity to avoid infinite values as $\Delta \rightarrow 0$. For small strain rates this rheology causes sea ice to move as a slowly creeping fluid with large viscosities, while for high strain rates the stresses are independent of strain rate (situated upon the yield curve in principle stress space) giving plastic flow.

1.2.4 Compactness and Thickness

The mean ice thickness (h) satisfies the following equation

Equation 8

$$\frac{\partial h}{\partial t} = -\nabla \cdot (h\mathbf{u}) + S_h$$

Equation 8 describes conservation of mass, where S_h is a thermodynamic term. The ice model uses a two-level distribution of the ice thickness, ice is characterised as thin or thick. Although this is a coarse distribution, it adequately reproduces large scale sea-ice dynamics because many of the dynamic and thermodynamic properties of sea ice are dominated by thin ice (e.g. high growth rate and low strength). The demarcation thickness between thick and thin ice types is $h/2$.

The compactness or concentration of thick ice per area, A , is given by

Equation 9

$$\frac{\partial A}{\partial t} = -\nabla \cdot (A\mathbf{u}) + S_A$$

where S_A is a thermodynamic term. Equation 9 has the restraint $A \leq 0.99$, and this introduces a mechanical sink term when $A=0.99$ as a parameterisation of ridging and rafting processes in the ice pack. There is no parameterisation of ridging and rafting for $A < 0.99$ in the model. The choice of $A \leq 0.99$ and not $A \leq 1$ is to ensure that there is at least a 1% fraction of thin ice. The coverage area of thin ice is given as $(1-A)$, our choice to estimate the amount of open water is to use the fraction $(1-A)$, hence the sea-ice concentration is taken to be the compactness A .

From the compactness A and mean thickness h the relationship to ice pressure P in equations Equation 4, Equation 5, Equation 6, is parameterised as follows (Hibler, 1979)

$$P = P_0 h e^{-C(1-A)}$$

where C and P_0 are empirical constants.

1.3 SEA ICE AREA AND CONCENTRATION FROM SATELLITE DATA AND THEIR USE IN SEA ICE MODELS

1.3.1 Introduction to SSM/I, AVHRR and SAR data

The most common satellite data for use with sea ice models are the passive microwave data (SMMR and SSM/I data) which have regular and spatial temporal coverage of all ice areas. The spatial resolution, which is of order 30 km, is ideal for use with ice-ocean models which have similar or coarser resolution. The passive microwave data provide over 20 years of ice area and ice concentration in both hemispheres. The data are primarily used to validate the performance of large-scale and regional models to simulate the seasonal and interannual variability in ice area and extent. AVHRR and other optical/IR data have been used for many years together with SSM/I data to produce ice charts by the operational ice services. These ice charts are also used to validate ice models. Ice models can roughly be divided in two categories: first research and process-oriented models which are developed to increase our understanding of dynamic and thermodynamic behaviour of sea ice; and secondly operational models which are used to produce ice forecasts. Preller et al. (1992) have given a more extensive review of the use of satellite data in ice models.

SAR data, which has been regularly available since the launch of ERS-1 in 1991, has provided much more detailed information about many sea ice parameter compared to other remote sensing techniques. With SAR it is possible to classify at least 4 – 5 ice types, ridges, cracks, leads and polynyas can be identified, the ice edge configuration can be mapped, and detailed ice motion can be calculated from a series of images (i.e. Kwok et al., 1990; Holt et al., 1992). The ice models are not yet capable of utilising all this information. However, ice drift vectors from SAR are important to study ice dynamic processes and how they can be simulated in models.

1.3.2 Ice area from merged SMMR and SSM/I series

The most direct, quantitative means to observe the global sea ice cover are satellite passive microwave remote sensors. Sea ice time series derived from multi-channel passive microwave data are among the longest continuous satellite-derived geophysical records, extending over two decades. The Nimbus-7 Scanning Multichannel Microwave Radiometer (SMMR) provided data

from 1978-87, and the follow-up Special Sensor Microwave Imager (SSM/I) onboard Defense Meteorological Satellite Program (DMSP) satellites has provided data since 1987. These data are used to estimate total ice area (the area of ice-covered ocean) and total ice extent (the area within the ice-ocean margin) and the fraction of multiyear ice (Fig. 1.1).

Figure 1.1. Sea ice extent and concentration in December 1980 in the Northern Hemisphere. White: 100 %, blue: < 15 % (open water)

Figure 1.2. map of sea ice area in the Arctic as observed from satellites from 1978 to present (a). Anomaly and trend in Arctic sea ice area after removal of the seasonal variability (b).

Analysis of the 20 year time series of global ice data shows that the Arctic ice area has been reduced by $0.3 \times 10^6 \text{ km}^2$ per decade (Figure 1.2 b), corresponding to $\sim 3\%$ of the ice area (Bjørge *et al.* (1997). The hemispheric ice covers fluctuate quasi-periodically, with predominant periods between 3-5 years, though their variability is apparently not correlated. Regionally, the trends vary significantly: The most pronounced reduction is found in the Kara and Barents Sea, with more than 10 % decrease in ice extent per decade while ice areas off eastern Canada shows increasing trend (Parkinson *et al.*, 1999).

The ice reductions were found to be most pronounced in the Siberian sector in the summer, with record low Arctic ice minima in 1990, 1993 and 1995, apparently linked to atmospheric circulation anomalies (Maslanik *et al.*, 1996). The summer reductions suggest consequential changes also in the perennial ice thickness. The perennial, multi-year ice, which having survived the summer melt, ice is about 3 times thicker than first-year or seasonal ice. Trends in multi-year ice area have also been investigated by the 20 years of SMMR and SSM/I data, showing a more pronounced reduction of the multiyear ice area ($\sim 7\%$ per decade) compared to the total ice area (Johannessen *et al.*, 1999). Analysis of the SMMR-SSM/I data reveals an 8% increase (5.3 days) in the length of the sea ice melt season in the Arctic over two decades (Smith, 1998). Ice thickness data obtained in the central Arctic by submarines since 1958 suggest that the thickness of the multiyear ice has decreased on average by 1.3 m over a period of 2 – 4 decades, from more than 3 m to less than 2 m (Rothrock *et al.*, 1999). However, the submarine data are only obtained along a few transects of the Arctic Ocean, and it is questionable to what extent the results of Rothrock *et al.* (1999) are representative for the whole Arctic sea ice. On the other hand, oceanographic data suggest a warming of the Arctic

water masses since the 1970s (McPhee et al., 1998), which is in agreement with the observed reduction in ice area.

1.4 ICE MOTION DATA

The circulation of sea ice determines the advective part of the ice balance and provides a velocity boundary condition on the ocean surface. The spatial gradient of this circulation, also expressed as ice deformation, controls the abundance of thin ice and therefore the many surface processes dependent on this thin ice, such as turbulent heat flux to the atmosphere and salt flux into the ocean. Convergent ice motion increases the local ice cover mass by rafting and ridging. Sea ice motion is readily observed in satellite imagery, the scale of the observed motion being dependent on the spatial resolution of the imagery. In recent years a number of procedures have been developed to recognize common features in various types of sequential images to obtain displacement measurements (i.e. Kwok et al., 1990, Holt et al., 1992). The quality of these measurements depends more on geometric fidelity and image resolution than on physical understanding of the ice signatures themselves. Imagery acquired by SAR and AVHRR are of particular importance, SAR because of its high resolution and all-weather capability and AVHRR because of its large coverage and frequent repeat over sea ice areas.

1.4.1 Satellite data

It has recently been demonstrated that sequential imagery from the 85 GHz Special Sensor Microwave Imager (SSM/I) can provide ice motion observation in spite of the 10 km or more footprint (Liu et al., 1998). Also the 37 GHz channel can provide ice motion information (Kwok et al., 1998) when combined with SAR-derived motion and buoy measurements. SSM/I data are particularly useful for estimating the large-scale ice drift in the winter periods (Martin and Augstein, 2000) and complement the drifting buoys which only measures ice drift in parts of the Arctic Ocean. Martin and Augstein (2000) used a box size for data averaging of 87.5 by 87.5 km (7 by 7 pixels) in order to obtain a time resolution of 3 days in the velocity estimates.

Example of a 3-day ice drift map for the Arctic ocean is shown in Fig. 1.3. By combining ice drift from SSM/I data and ice thickness from ULS data it is possible to calculate ice volume fluxes, as shown by Drinkwater et al (2000) in the Weddell Sea and Kwok and Rothrock (1998) in the Fram Strait.

Figure 1.3 Optically interpolated ice velocity field for the three-day period 8-11 April 1993, using SSM/I data in combination with drifting buoys (circles with arrows). The velocity data are produced by The Polar Remote Sensing Group at JPL, California Institute of Tehnology

1.4.2 Ice drift data from Arctic Ocean Buoy Program

A set of automatic data buoys which measure basic meteorological data such as atmospheric pressure, air temperature and buoy location are deployed in the Central Arctic Basin and its marginal seas. The data are transmitted via ARGOS. The programme was established in early 1979 by the Polar Science Center (PSC), University of Washington, USA. There are on average of 15 buoys in service at the time. The basic data sets consist of 12-hourly pressure and temperature fields (data set A and B) which represents 20 –30 Mbyte over a year. In addition there are 12-hourly buoy positions and interpolated ice velocity fields (data set C and D). Digital data sets are available from <http://iabp.apl.washington.edu/> via anonymous ftp as well as on tape from NSIDC.

1.5 SEA ICE FREEBOARD ESTIMATES FROM SPACEBORNE ALTIMETRY

1.5.1 Introduction

In this section we describe the newly developed technique to estimate sea ice elevation and hence thickness using a space-borne radar altimeter.

1.5.2 Altimeter data

The ERS-1 dataset used in our analysis spanned the period from 25 June 1993 to 2 June 1996, which includes five different mission phases encompassing the entire range of orbit repeat periods: 3, 35 and 168 days. Data prior to 1993 was unusable due to problems with the tracking performance of ERS-1 over sea ice (Scott, 1994). Data from ERS-2 acquired between 3 May 1995 and 28 June 1999 was also used, corresponding to cycles 0 to 43 of the satellite's 35-day repeat mission. The full 20 Hz WAP data records were used, which include the averaged waveforms necessary for the pre-processing of altimeter data in sea ice-covered regions.

1.5.3 Return echoes over sea ice

The presence of sea ice with the radar altimeter footprint generally changes both the shape and power of the return echo received. These changes are attributable both to reflections from sea ice itself and to changes in the water surface caused by the presence of ice. Radar altimeter echoes over sea ice fall into one of three categories (i) Specular, (ii) Diffuse and (iii) Complex (Fig. 1.4). Specular echoes make up between 50-80% of return echoes observed in current pulse limited space-borne altimeters.

Figure 1.4. Radar altimeter echo types observed over sea ice. Specular returns (i) originate from leads and thin new ice, complex echoes (ii) originate from the surface of ice floes. Complex echoes

occur when a heterogeneous mixture of ice and water occurs within the altimeter footprint and are discarded since an unambiguous elevation cannot be retrieved.

Specular echoes are characterised by a rapid fall off in return power after the initial rise indicating a highly specular reflecting surface and in addition the peak power can exceed that typically observed over the open ocean by up to three orders of magnitude (30dB). The origin of these specular echoes is not fully understood but consideration of normal incidence backscatter theory offers some clues as to their likely origin. Firstly to generate echoes which fall off within the narrow range of incidence angles sampled by the altimeter implies that the reflecting surface must be flat or smooth to within a fraction of the wavelength (say $\lambda/8 = 3\text{mm}$) over distances of several metres. Secondly reflections from such surfaces can, theoretically, dominate the altimeter echo even if they represent less than 1% of the reflecting area within the altimeter footprint. Although mm scale measurements of sea ice roughness are scarce those which do exist indicate that specular echoes are unlikely to originate from first and multi-year ice floes and can only originate from areas of open water or new ice within the pack. This hypothesis is supported by measurements of normal incidence backscatter from ice and water surfaces. Experiments on artificial sea ice show that backscatter from a calm water surface can exceed that from rough ice by 20dB [Gogineni *et al.*, 1990]. Measurements of the radar backscatter at 13GHz from aircraft in the early 1970's show the strongest returns at nadir ($\sigma_0=15\text{ dB}$) originating from open water within the pack ice with backscatter decreasing from 6 to 0dB as the ice thickness increased from 5 to 360 cm [Parashar *et al.*, 1974]. By isolating specular echoes therefore it is possible to accurately retrieve estimates of the instantaneous sea surface elevation even in areas of high ice concentration. This has for example enabled the derivation of

high resolution marine gravity fields in ice infested waters [Laxon and McAdoo, 1994][McAdoo and Laxon, 1997].

Figure 1.5. Percentage of diffuse, specular and complex return occurring during a seasonal cycle. The percentage of specular returns ranges from 50% during winter to 80% during the summer. The more broken character of the ice field and surface melting leads to a more homogeneous distribution of open water within the altimeter footprint during summer. The percentage of diffuse returns within the pack ice ranges from 5% during winter falling to near zero during the summer. The number of complex returns is higher during winter due to more frequent heterogeneity of ice/water mixtures during the winter.

Diffuse echoes, such as those typically observed over the open ocean, in areas of high ice are less common making up only 5% of returns during the winter and virtually none during high summer.

Comparisons with infra-red imagery (e.g. Fetterer *et al.*, 1992; Laxon, 1994) show that these occur where large ice floes or consolidated ice fill the altimeter footprint. In order to discriminate these “diffuse ice” returns from those usually observed over the open ocean a threshold on the ice concentration, as determined from passive microwave observations, is employed.

Figure 1.6. Location of specular (Blue circles) and diffuse (red circles) in co-incident sea ice imagery. Diffuse echoes are only observed where consolidated ice cover fills the altimeter footprint. Specular echoes occur over visible and sub-pixel lead. Data gaps indicate the location of complex echoes. The imagery (11 μm ATSR) and altimeter data are exactly co-incident if space and time.

Complex echoes form the remainder of return echoes and are caused when the reflecting surface are highly heterogeneous within the altimeter footprint. This type of echo is likely to occur in heterogeneous ice regimes or where the reflection from ice and water are of similar magnitude. These data are not generally usable for geophysical retrieval and they must be eliminated using data quality assurance algorithms.

The separation of echoes from ice and water offers a clear potential to directly measure sea ice freeboard and hence estimate ice thickness. Initial investigations using the ERS-1 and ERS-2 radar altimeter show promising results. Key to the success of ice freeboard retrieval is the estimation of the (unobserved) sea surface height beneath the ice floe. The largest variation in sea surface height, due to the marine geoid, is eliminated using repeat track analysis. Mean profiles are generated for each of the 501 orbits which make up a 35 day repeat cycle. More than 3 years of data are now available allowing for the generation a precise mean sea surface model. Superimposed on the time-invariant component of sea surface height are small temporal variations caused by dynamic topography. These are estimated by constructing a smoothed sea surface height anomaly field estimated from specular returns gathered during a particular repeat cycle. This field is then used as a reference against which estimates of the ice surface elevation are compared to retrieve sea ice freeboard (Figure 1.4).

Figure 1.7 Ice freeboard estimation through co-linear analysis. Specular returns (blue) are used to generate a mean sea surface which is then removed from individual passes. The elevation difference between diffuse (red) echoes and residual sea surface height is then used to estimate ice freeboard. Currently up to 60 profiles are averaged to obtain a mean sea surface.

The first step in generating estimates of ice freeboard is the estimation of the (unobserved) sea surface elevation using collinear elevation estimates. ERS passes over the same ground track every 35 days permitting the analysis of up to 60 co-linear elevation which are used to estimate mean sea level.

1.5.4 Ice elevation estimates

Figure 1.7 shows schematically how ice elevation estimates are derived. Co-located elevation estimates identified as open water/thin ice are time-averaged at each point of the ground track to obtain a mean and variance for sea surface elevation. The mean profile is then subtracted from individual profiles to obtain a residual. The elevation of the water surface beneath the ice floe is then determined using linear interpolation of the sea surface residual either side of the ice returns.

1.5.5 Calibration/Validation of altimeter estimates

The main source of validation data for our altimeter estimates is data from co-incident upward looking sonar systems, either mounted on submarines, or from moorings in the Fram Strait. We have concentrated on data gathered during SCICEX cruises, gathered during the 1990's in the

Beaufort Sea. The slow moving nature of the ice pack in this region reduces uncertainties caused by movement during the finite period used for inter-comparison (typically one month). The results of the validation is shown in Fig. 1.8.

Fig. 1.8 a: Comparison of radar altimeter elevations and submarine ULS drafts. Diagonal lines indicate the predicted ice/snow interface elevation for different months in the Beaufort Sea based on the snow depth climatology of (Warren, 1999). Submarine data are from April 1994, September 1994/7 and October 1996. Altimeter averages are based on data lying within 15 days and 100 km of the submarine averages. b: Comparison of ice thickness derived from radar altimeter ice elevation estimates and SCICEX submarine draft estimates

Figure 1.8 a shows a comparison between altimeter derived ice elevation (above mean sea level) and co-incident ice drafts collected during SCICEX submarine cruises in the Beaufort Sea. Also shown are the predicted ratios for different months assuming reflection from the snow/ice interface and climatological snow depths in the Beaufort Sea. The radar altimeter estimate assumes reflection from the snow/ice interface whilst the SCICEX estimates originate from draft estimates. Standard values are used for ice (910kgm^{-3}), snow (330kg m^{-3}) and water (1023 kg m^{-3}) densities and snow depth is derived from (Warren, 1999). This comparison indicates that reflection over snow covered ice likely comes from the snow/ice interface.

A comparison of ice thickness derived from SCICEX submarine drafts and radar altimeter elevation measurements (both corrected for snow climatology is shown in Fig 1.8 b. The comparison indicates shows agreement between the altimeter and submarine estimates of thickness to within $\sim 0.5\text{ m}$.

1.6 ASSESSMENT OF THE MODEL PERFORMANCES, AS FAR AS THEY ARE KNOWN

In the Sea Ice Model Intercomparison Project (SIMIP) several ice rheologies have been investigated by Kreyscher et al (2000). The objective of the study was to investigate to which extent the right choice of rheology improves the simulation for a given set of forcing observational data. Four different models have been compared:

VPM: Viscous-plastic model (Hibler, 1979; Kreyscher et al., 2000)

CFM: Cavitating fluid model (Flato and Hibler, 1992)

CNF: Compressible Newtonian fluid (Kreyscher et al., 2000)

FDC: Free drift model with velocity correction (Bryan, 1969)

All models have been run with the same grid, land boundaries and forcing fields. Atmospheric forcing data from 1979 to 1995 (wind and temperature) are derived from the NCEP/NCAR reanalysis (Kalney et al., 1996). The 10 m wind and 2 m temperature were averaged to daily means. Relative humidity were obtained from ECMWF monthly means. Monthly means of cloudiness and precipitation are taken from Ebert and Curry (1993) and Vowinckel and Orvig (1970). The ocean forcing includes heat flux from the deep water into the mixed layer, provided by the coupled ice-ocean simulation by Hibler and Zhang (1993), and annual mean geostrophic current and associated surface tilt. The ocean forcing includes heat flux from the deep water into the mixed layer, provided by subsequent study.

For verification the following data have been used: ice thickness data from Upward-Looking Sonars; ice concentration from SMMR and SSM/I data; buoy drift data from IABP; and ice drift from the 85 GHz SSM/I channel. In the comparison with observations, it is clear that differences between model results and observations can have many reasons, not all of them need to be related to the rheology. For example inaccuracy in the forcing fields, errors in the observations, limited resolution in time and space, and simplification of the physics in various parts of the model can all contribute to the differences which arise from such comparison.

1.1.1 Ice thickness estimates

The ice thickness estimates from the four models are compared and discussed by Kreyscher et al (2000). Here we will only present the comparison of the model results in four regions where ice thickness data are available from ULS data. The total mean thickness is shown in Fig. 1.9 for the Fram Strait, a site in the East Siberian Sea, the North Pole and a site in the Beaufort Sea. All models gives reasonable results except the free-drift model which tend to give higher thickness than the other models. The Beaufort site is noticeable due to the very wide spread in the estimates. This can be explained by the fact that the location is close to the coast and that the model resolution is too coarse to reproduce this site very well. The comparison between the models shows that the viscous-plastic model has the lowest RMS, while the free-drift model has relatively large RMS errors due to systematically overestimation of the thickness.

Figure 1.9 Mean ice thickness at the ULS positions for all models and observations (Kreyscher et al., 2000)

1.6.2 Ice extent estimates

Monthly anomalies of sea ice extent have been calculated from both SMMR/SSMI data and the model simulations for 1979 to 1995. The ice areas of the whole Arctic Ocean and the adjacent seas are included, except the Labrador and the Bering Sea. Time series of the anomalies are presented for a summer month (September) and a winter month (March) in Fig. 1.10. The observed anomalies are significantly larger in summer than in winter, with standard deviation of $0.4 \times 10^6 \text{ km}^2$ and $0.23 \times 10^6 \text{ km}^2$, respectively. In the summer there are large interannual variations which the models only partly can simulate. For example 1990 and 1995 show minimum ice extent which two of the models can reproduce: the viscous-plastic and the compressible Newtonian model. From 1979 to 1981 there is large discrepancy between model results and the data, but all models are in good agreement. This suggests that either the data or the forcing fields are inaccurate in these years. The free-drift model shows very poor correlation with the data in September, while it is better correlated with data in March, similar to the other models. In winter, there are very small differences between the rheologies. In summer ice extent is best reproduced by the viscous-plastic and compressible Newtonian models, while the cavitating fluid and free-drift models do not capture the large ice minimum in 1990.

Figure 1.10. Anomalies of ice extent in (a) September and (b) March. The correlation coefficient (r) between observation and models is shown. The shaded area gives the estimated error of the observation. (Kreyscher et al., 2000)

1.6.3 Ice drift

The mean ice drift fields are calculated for the periods when observation data are available for the whole Arctic Ocean from SSM/I data, analyzed by Martin and Augstein (2000) for the winters of 1987-88 and 1994-95. An example of a mean 3-day ice velocity field from SSM/I data is shown in Fig. 1.3. The mean simulated ice drift by the viscous-plastic model for the two winter periods studied by Martin and Augstein (2000) is shown in Fig. 1.11. This figure indicates the main features of the Arctic ice drift such as the Beaufort gyre, the Transpolar Drift, and the outflow through the Fram Strait. In order to obtain a quantitative comparison between models and data, correlations have been calculated between both horizontal components of the simulated and observed velocities, using all available buoy and SSM/I data. The correlation has been done for different averaging periods, from 3 to 50 days, showing that the correlation increases with longer averaging time.

Figure 1.11 Mean simulated ice drift by the viscous-plastic model for the winters of 1987/88 and 1994/95. The axes indicate the model grid. (Kreyscher et al., 2000).

The highest correlation is found for the viscous-elastic model, reaching 0.80 for correlation with drifting buoys, and up to 0.90 for correlation with SSM/I data. The more uniform spatial and temporal distribution of the SSM/I data compared the IABP buoy data gives higher correlation for the former data. The lowest correlation is found for the free-drift model, with a correlation of about 0.70 and 0.80 for buoy and SSM/I data, respectively.

Kreyscher et al (2000) have studied the ice export through the Fram Strait specifically, The north-south component of the ice drift through the Fram Strait, derived from SSM/I data and the viscous-elastic model, are shown in Fig. 1.12 a and b for the two winter periods 1987-88 and 1994-95.

Figure 1.12 Comparison of the northward drift velocities in the Fram Strait: a) and b) are time series of averaged 3-day velocities for the viscous-plastic model and the SSM/I observations; c) and d) are time series of monthly averaged velocities for all models and the observations (Kreyscher et al., 2000).

A significant temporal variability is found for these periods, using 3-day averaged data. The model is capable of reproducing the temporal variability quite well, at an RMS error of about 4 cm s^{-1} . Comparison between the models using monthly averaged data and corresponding data from SSM/I is shown in Fig. 1.12 c and d. The observed drift is best reproduced by the viscous-elastic model and poorest by the free-drift model, which systematically underestimated the drift.

By combining ice drift and ice thickness data, the ice volume flux through the Fram Strait can be calculated. All ice models except the free-drift model show a mean volume flux of about 0.09 Sv for the period 1979 - 1995, which is in good agreement with the results published by Vinje et al (1998).

The overall result of the model intercomparison shows that the viscous-plastic model yields the most realistic simulation, and that the free-drift model gives the largest errors. The compressible

Newtonian fluid cannot prevent excessive ice thickness build-up in the central Arctic and overestimates the internal forces in the Fram Strait. Because of the lack of shear strength, the cavitating-fluid model shows marked differences to the statistics of the observed ice drift and ice thickness pattern.

1.7 ICE THICKNESS DATA FOR MODEL VALIDATION

The ice thickness distribution displays the relative abundance of ice of different ice thicknesses. The distribution evolves in response to ice transport, deformation and thermodynamic growth and melt. Five techniques are considered to be reliable for direct measurements of ice thickness distribution: 1) submarine sonar profiling, 2) moored upward sonars, 3) airborne laser profilometry, 4) airborne electromagnetic techniques, and 5) drilling (Wadhams, 1994). Most synoptic data published so far have been obtained by upward looking sonar (ULS) profiling from submarines whose exact positions are classified (Wadhams, 1994). A map of available submarine ULS data is shown in Fig. 1.13. Upward looking sonar's mounted on moorings obtain valuable time series of the ice thickness at selected locations, such as in the Fram Strait (Vinje et al., 1998).

Figure 1.13. Cruise tracks of submarine measuring ice thickness in the Arctic Ocean

In a recent paper by Rothrock, et al, (1999) summer sea ice draft data from the SCICEX submarines cruises from 1993, 1996 and 1997 are analyzed and compared to summer and fall data obtained during cruises between 1958 and 1976. The study show that the mean draft data from a large portion of the Arctic have decreased on average by about 1.3 meters, roughly 4.5 cm a year. If we consider a 3m thick homogeneous ice plate it will take 67 years to melt the plate. A 20 year long time serie of effective ice thickness data reported by Nagurny et al, (1999) show an on the average decrease of 0.5 cm a year in mean effective ice thickness from 1972 to 1992. A similar calculation as above

would give a melting time of 600 years. This demonstrates the consequences of relatively small errors in effective ice thickness estimates.

An explanation to the around 9 times stronger ice thickness reduction rate found by Rothrock et al. (1999) is that the SCICEX experiments were carried out with in years with minimum in sea ice extent in the summer time, this may cause the reduction a year to be overestimated (Johannessen, et al, 1999). Furthermore, a more detailed inspection of the effective ice thickness time series show three periods of significant reduction of sea ice thickness the first 1972-1974 (8 cm-2.0 cm pr year), the second 1980-1982 (5 cm-2.5cm pr year) and the third between 1987 and 1990 (22.5 cm-7.5 cm pr year). In between these periods there are two period with significant increase in ice thickness (1.7-2.4 cm pr year). This shows the need of continuos and homogenous ice thickness data sets and that longer times series are needed before one can verify climatic trends from ice thickness data.

Despite the difference in ice thickness reduction rates found in the above studies, this represents a new confirmation that the sea ice cover thickness in the Arctic are in transformation.

1.7.1 Ice thickness distribution

Sea ice thickness on local scale is highly variable due to a number of ridges and corresponding ice keels. To characterize the ice cover it is necessary to estimate a thickness probability distribution function (PDF) which require a number of observations of each thickness category (Wadhams, 1994).

The ice thickness distribution $g(h)$ is defined as (Thorndike et.al. 1975)

$$\int_{h_1}^{h_2} g(h)dh = \frac{1}{R} [A(h_1, h_2)]$$

where h is the ice thickness, R is the area total area of some fixed region R about the point of interest, and $A(h_1, h_2)$ is the area within R covered by ice with thickness h between h_1 and h_2 . The function g can be considered as a probability density function (PDF, m^{-1}). The corresponding distribution for ice draft, D , is defined as

$$\int_{h_1}^{h_2} f(D)dD = \frac{1}{R} [A(h_1, h_2)]$$

$$\text{where } f(D) = \frac{1}{1.136} g(h)$$

It is the draft PDF function $g(h)$ which is available from submarines using upward looking sonars.

1.7.2 Submarine Upward Looking Sonar Ice Draft Profile data and Statistics

This section is based on the information obtained from database description available from http://www-nsidc.colorado.edu/NOAA/ULS_Drafts. The data base includes files with draft data and files with sea ice statistics. In this study where only the draft thickness is to be used for climate model validation it is most easy to use the draft files directly.

Data processing

Raw top-sounder profiles, from which data presented here are derived, were created by sampling ice draft with top-sounder profilers at intervals spaced equally in time as the submarine moved beneath the ice cover. Adjacent drafts in the raw profile, though recorded at intervals that are constant in time, represent spot measurements separated by non-constant distances, the length of which vary with changes in vessel speed. In this raw format, profiles from different tracks (or even from different segments of the same track) are not directly comparable because the same feature (keel, lead, etc.) sampled twice will have a different shape depending on whether the sensor platform was moving rapidly or slowly. Keels and other roughness elements in raw- top sounder profiles thus appear compressed at high speeds, and stretched out at low speeds. Such apparent differences in the sampling rate bias summary statistics (mean draft, variance etc.) and spectral characteristics (Fourier Transform and correlation etc.) because the bottom side ice profile represented in one section of data is over and under sampled with respect to that in another section.

To eliminate this problem, interpolated profiles composed of drafts spaced equally in distance (as opposed to time) are created. Navigation data combined with speed and bearing information give good estimates of the geographic location of each draft. Great circle distances between points, calculated from geographic location of each draft. Great circle distances between points, calculated from geographic coordinates using standard mapping equations provide a basis for interpolating a derivative set of equidistant drafts using a cubic spline algorithm. The interpolated profiles that result, consisting of drafts spaced equally with respect to distance (nominally 1.0 m apart), forms the basis of this database.

Draft data from submarines are available at the www using the address http://www-nsidc.colorado.edu/NOAA/ULS_Drafts. The raw digital data contain only information only about ice drafts and time. Uniform ice draft data on a uniform spatial interval has been obtained by integrating the speed and positions of the submarine with a interpolation routine. Segments of the data during which the submarine changed course and/depth has been removed, along with straight line segments smaller than 10 km. The draft data are stored in ASCII format. An overview of the data is given in Table 1.2

Table 1.2 Summary of available ice draft data from submarine upward looking sonars.

Cruise Reference	Date start	End date	Number of segments	Comments
UK-76	07-04-76	10-04-76	27	Accurate date and approximate positions.
UK-87	08-05-87	26-05-87	130	Accurate date and approximate positions..
UK-91	20-04-91	22-04-91	16	Accurate date and approximate positions..
L2-92	XX-04-91	XX-04-91	64	Positions are rounded to the nearest 5 min both in longitude and latitude.
SCICEX-93	01-09-93	12-09-93	139	Positions and date are precisely reported. The Position is accurate with 6 decimals.
1994	XX-04-94	XX-04-94	85	Accurate date and approximate positions.
SCICEX-96	20-09-96	22-10-96	217	Positions and date are precisely reported. The Position is accurate with 6 decimals.

SCICEX-97	03-09-97	02-10-97	192	Positions and date are precisely reported. The Position is accurate with 6 decimals.
-----------	----------	----------	-----	---

During the first phase of the work focus has been on the SCICEX draft data sets. All SCICEX data are presented in the same data format and are the most accurate data both regarding positioning and time. Next focus will be on the UK data which have a slightly different header format. The data has been condensed into a “listing” format to be used in a into a format which can be used in this project.

1.7.3 Bottom moored upward looking sonar’s in the Fram Strait.

During the 1990s ice thickness has been monitored by moored upward looking sonars in the Fram Strait at 79° N by the Norwegian Polar Institute (Vinje et al., 1998) and in the east Greenland Current at 75°N by Alfred Wegener Institute and others. The mean and variability of the ice thickness are recorded in fixed locations because the ice drifts continuously southwards in this region. The data are important for estimation of ice flux out of the Arctic Ocean (Kwok and Rothrock, 1999) and will be used in this study to validate the ice flux estimated by an ice-ocean model. Results of six year of monitoring of ice volume flux and ice area flux, starting in August 1990, published by Vinje et al. (1998) are shown in Fig. 1.14.

Figure 1.14. The flux through the Fram Strait at 79° N of (a) ice volume (in km³ per month) and (b) cumulative ice area in 5° longitude intervals (in km² per month) from August 1990 to July 1996 (Vinje et al., 1998).

1.8 COMPARISON OF ICE THICKNESS DATA FROM ERS WITH MODEL SIMULATIONS

The generation of monthly mean ice thicknesses from ERS radar altimetry permits a comparison of basin-wide monthly ice thickness estimates with model simulations of the first time.

1.8.1 Comparison with the University of Kiel sea ice model

The difference between ERS altimeter estimates of ice thickness and contemporary predictions from the University of Kiel Sea ice model are shown in Fig. 1.15. The comparisons are generated by simply averaging the altimeter ice thickness estimates within each model grid cell. The differences are then computed by subtracting the observed from modelled ice thickness value in each grid cell.

These comparisons indicate that the Kiel model appears to consistently over-predict ice thickness in the Western Arctic, whilst agreement in the Eastern Arctic is considerably better. Differences between the model and observations also shows temporal coherence from month to month and within a given season. For example the largest differences are observed in the Beaufort Sea during the early part of 1996. In contrast in the last 3 month of 1996 model and observed ice thicknesses show reasonable agreement in the eastern Beaufort with larger differences occurring on either side.

These comparisons can provide potentially valuable insights into the deficiencies in current model parameterisations and forcing fields. The fact that differences are larger in the Western Arctic, for example, suggests that the representation of forcing related to dynamics dynamic (which are more prevalent in the Western Arctic), rather than thermodynamics, may be in error. On the other hand the month-month correlation of differences suggests perhaps errors in the initial state of ice thickness for example at the end of the summer.

Figure 1.15. **a:** Differences between Kiel model and UCL ice thicknesses October 1995 – March 1996; **b:** Differences between Kiel model and UCL ice thickness October 1996 – November 1997.

1.8.2 Comparison with HADCOM

In this section we present comparisons of ERS ice thickness estimates with simulations from the UK Hadley Centre Coupled Climate Model (HADCM). For this analysis mean ice thicknesses in selected geographical boxes are computed from the radar altimeter estimates. These can then be compared with the output of the mean Hadley Centre climatology.

Figures 1.16 (a), (b) and (c) show comparisons of the seasonal and interannual variability of ice thickness observed by ERS and simulated by HADCM. In the Fram Strait ERS shows a much larger amplitude seasonal cycle of ice thickness than the HADCM with slightly lower minima but much larger maxima. In the Kara Sea the amplitude of the seasonal cycle and the minimum and maximum values of ice thickness are remarkably similar. In the Beaufort Sea, as with the Kiel model, the ice thicknesses are considerably larger in HADCM as compared with the observations. This region also shows a high degree of interannual variability in the observed thicknesses, probably caused by higher variability in atmospheric/oceanic forcing than is represented by the model.

a

b

c

Figure 1.16 **a**: Comparison of ERS and HADCM ice thickness in the Fram Strait; **b**: Comparison of ERS and HADCM ice thickness in the Kara Sea; **c**: Comparison of ERS and HADCM thickness in the Beaufort Sea.

Figure 1.17 shows the minimum and maximum ice thickness observed in the ERS data during the period 1993-1998 as compared with the long term min/max ice thickness observed in the HADCM. This shows that, whilst the long term inter-annual variability in ice thickness predicted by HADCM is reasonable, the mean thickness of ice exiting the Fram Strait is under-predicted by a factor of two. Under-prediction of ice mass transport through the Fram Strait will lead to errors in the prediction of fresh water input to the Greenland Sea and subsequent impacts on ocean deep overturning in the region.

Figure 1.17. Maximum/Minimum monthly long term ice thickness in the Fram Strait.

1.8.3 Trends in Arctic ice thickness

The derivation of a time-series of ice thickness estimates from the ERS-1/2 altimeters has enabled the determination of trends in ice thickness during the period 1993-1999. Trends are determined using a linear regression of ice thickness estimates for a series of grid points covering the Arctic Ocean. Figure 1.18 shows trends in ice thickness for all months from 1993-1999 with locations of SCICEX submarine draft data overlaid.

Table 1.3 compares the overall trend in Arctic ice thickness with results from Russian ice floe tilt experiments (Johannessen, 1999) and submarine draft data (Rothrock, 1999). Our overall trend of -1.1 cm yr^{-1} is in close agreement with trends observed in the Russian data but is significantly less than that observed in the submarine data. In addition climate prediction models predict an average decrease of $\sim 1 \text{ cm yr}^{-1}$ over the period 1960-2060.

(<http://www.gfdl.gov/~kd/KDwebpages/NHice.html>)

Fig. 1.18. Trends in Arctic Ice thickness 1993-1999 from ERS-1/2 altimetry. Monthly ice thickness grids are generated by averaging all altimeter thickness estimates in 2°lat x 5° long grid cells. A linear least squares fit is then used to determine trends at each grid cell point. Also shown are the locations of SCICEX submarine drafts gathered between 1993 and 1997.

Table 1.3. Trends in Arctic Ice thickness from ERS, swell propagation and submarine draft data

Reference	Source	Trend	Period
Laxon and Peacock, 2000	ERS-1/2	- 1.1 cm yr ⁻¹	1993-1999
Johannessen, <i>et. al.</i> , Science, 1999	Swell Propagation	- 1 cm yr ⁻¹	1972-1990
Rothrock, <i>et. al.</i> , GRL, 1999	Submarine	- 4 cm yr ⁻¹	1958-1997

4.9 DATA ASSIMILATION ASPECTS

The first application of Kalman smoothing to passive microwave ice concentration estimates was demonstrated by Thomas and Rothrock (1989, 1993), who used a simple ice model driven by velocities optimally interpolated from buoy motions, to form independent model-derived concentration estimates that are optimally blended with the concentration data. Thomas et al (1996) extended this work by using observed buoy motions, wind-driven, free-drift velocities to drive the advective and ridging parts of the model, while climatological growth and melt rates determined the ice thickness. The model adjusted the thickness distribution so that the modeled concentrations of open water, firstyear ice and multiyear ice matched the concentrations derived by Kalman filtering of the satellite passive microwave data. With this methodology Thomas et al (1996) and Steele et al (1996) estimated the ice velocities, volume fluxes and freshwater balance for the Arctic Ocean as a whole and for eight subsections.

Assimilation of ice data in fully coupled ice-ocean models have not yet been done, but the framework for use of this technique has been developed at the Nansen Center through the so-called Ensemble Kalman Filter (Evensen 1994, 1997; Evensen and van Leeuwen, 1996, 1999). In the DIADEM project, funded by EU, data assimilation of SSM/I data into the coupled ice-ocean model is under development. In this project, assimilation of ice thickness data will be addressed in Task 5.

Task 2: Basic model scenario

2.1	Introduction	1
2.2	Model description	3
2.3	Validation data	6
2.4	Sea-ice extent and area	6
2.4.1	Monthly averages	6
2.4.2	Trends from anomalies	7
2.4.3	Trends for the entire Arctic from satellite	12
2.5	Temporal and spatial distribution of the model error in ice concentration	13
2.6	Multi-year ice area and ice thickness	16
2.7	Discussion	21
2.8	Perturbed fresh water experiments	23
2.9	The control simulation	23
2.9.1	Ocean circulation	23
2.9.2	Transports of mass and heat	26
2.10	The perturbed simulations	28
2.10.1	Salinity and temperature	28
2.10.2	Sea ice and velocity	30
2.10.3	Transports of mass and heat	30
2.10.4	Intermediate and deep water formation	32
2.11	Discussion	33
2.12	Conclusion	37

TASK 2. Basic model scenario

The objective of this task is simulate fluctuations in Arctic sea ice concentration, extent, thickness and mass, using an existing dynamic-thermodynamic model. The simulations should include seasonal, annual and interannual variations. The results of the simulations as well as the forcing fields shall be assessed by comparison with observations.

The work in this task covers:

- Description of model simulations showing spatial and temporal variability in ice parameters (concentration, extent, thickness and mass/volume)
- Description of model assumptions, forcing data and output data
- Delivery of model output data sets
- Assessment of model output, atmospheric/ocean forcing data, by comparison with observation
- Compilation and analysis of data to be used in model assessment
 - extent and concentration
 - thickness
 - velocity

2.1 Introduction

Sea ice is an important component of the Arctic climate system. Its presence modifies heat and momentum exchanges between the atmosphere and the ocean, and snow and ice reflects 70%–80% of the incoming solar radiation. Results from nearly all coupled atmosphere-ice-ocean numerical modeling studies of greenhouse gas scenarios indicate that global warming will be enhanced in the polar regions, especially in the northern hemisphere (Manabe *et al.*, 1992), with a predicted warming of about 3–4°C in the next half-century (Mitchell *et al.*, 1995), and a drastic decrease of the sea ice in the Arctic Ocean (Cattle and Crossley (1995), Vinnikov *et al.* (1999).

Recent analyses of the ice cover in the Arctic Ocean have established that significant changes have occurred in the latter part of the 20th century. Analysis of upward looking sonar observations from US nuclear submarines indicates that the average ice thickness has decreased from 3.1 m in the 1958–1976 period to 1.8 m in the 1990s, in average 4 cm per year, or totally 40% of the total ice volume (Rothrock *et al.*, 1999). However, these measurements are in contrast to spatially averaged ice thickness estimates obtained from surface elastic-gravity wave measurements carried out by the Russian “North Pole” drifting stations during the period 1970–1991 (Nagurnyi *et al.*, 1999). The average ice thickness during this 21 year period is 2.85 m with a reduction of 0.5 cm yr⁻¹; or a factor 8 less than the trend observed by Rothrock *et al.* (1999) over a 10 year longer period.

Furthermore, analysis of microwave satellite observations has established that the total sea ice area has decreased by 6% over the last two decades (Johannessen *et al.* (1995), E. *et al.* (1997), Parkinson *et al.* (1999)), while the multi-year ice area has decreased by 14% over the same period (Johannessen *et al.*, 1999). Comparison of observations (*in situ* and satellite)

since 1900 with trends seen in two coarse resolution global climate models, incorporating the effects of observed greenhouse gases and tropospheric sulphate aerosols correlates very well. As stated in Vinnikov *et al.* (1999), this is “suggesting strongly” that the observed decrease in sea ice extent since 1950 is related to the anthropogenic global warming. Prediction by these two coarse resolution global climate models furthermore suggest a substantial decrease of the sea ice extent in the 21st century (Vinnikov *et al.*, 1999). However, the elevated indices of the North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO) (Hurrell, 1995) and the Arctic Oscillation (AO) (Thompson and Wallace, 1998), indicate a pumping of warm air and water masses into the Arctic from the North Atlantic region causing ice melt as well as a mechanism for exporting multi-year ice through the Fram Strait (Hurrell (1995), Thompson and Wallace (1998), Rothrock *et al.* (1999)). Even some effects on the variability of the sea ice from El Niño has been reported (Gloersen, 1995). Therefore, the decreasing ice cover is probably caused by a combined effect of greenhouse warming (century time scale), high indices of the AO/NAO index (decadal time scale) and even the Atlantic Multidecadal Oscillation (AMO) (Kerr, 2000). For a review of the state of art regarding the Arctic ice cover see e.g. Johannessen and Miles (2000).

The melting and freezing of sea ice leads to changes in the density of the underlying water, and these changes can have a negative or positive effect on convection. Sea ice formation in the Arctic Ocean and the shelf seas around it leads to increased water density and contributes to the formation of Arctic intermediate and deep waters (Midttun (1985), Anderson *et al.* (1989), Aagaard, K. and Carmack (1989), Yang and Neelin (1993)), whereas a melting ice cover can prohibit deep water formation by stabilizing the water column and by advecting fresh water into neighboring regions. Advection of fresh water from the Arctic Ocean into the Greenland Sea and the North Atlantic is an example of the latter. The Arctic Ocean and its peripheral seas are therefore of importance for the global thermohaline circulation (the Global conveyor belt, (Broecker *et al.*, 1985)), and make Arctic sea ice a climate component also in a global perspective.

The role sea ice plays in the climate system suggests that sea ice models should be evaluated and compared before they are included in coupled climate models. Currently such an effort is being carried out in the Sea Ice Model Intercomparison Project (SIMIP) (Lemke *et al.*, 1997), which attempts to determine the best currently available sea ice model when it comes to dynamic realism, thermodynamic realism and computational efficiency. The major objective of our paper is to validate ice variables from a coupled sea ice and ocean model using sea ice concentrations derived from passive microwave satellite sensors and sea ice thickness estimates from submarine upward looking sonars.

Validation data for the sea ice concentration were acquired from the Scanning Multimeter Microwave Radiometer (SMMR) carried on board the NASA Nimbus 7 satellite and the Special Sensor Microwave/Imager (SSM/I) carried on board satellites F8, F11 and F13 of the US Defense Meteorological Satellite Program (DMSP). The combined data set now spans two decades and represents a reliable day-to-day description of the sea ice concentration in the polar regions. Compared to data sets of other parameters of sea ice, for instance ice thickness, the data set of sea ice concentration is superior when it comes to the spatial coverage and the length of the time series. This makes it well suited for validation of sea ice models. The sea ice concentration has a significant effect upon the thermodynamic part of the sea ice model, but sea ice concentration is also important for the dynamic part since the strength/pressure parameterization in sea ice rheologies depends upon it. The validation with sea ice concentration is carried out over the time period 1978–1998, and a special emphasis has been put on checking whether trends in the passive microwave data sets are recreated. In

the validation with sea ice concentration it is also presented statistical methods that are well suited for an objective quantification of the skill of a sea ice model. Additionally, comparisons have been made with ice thickness estimates from upward looking sonars mounted onboard US and British Navy submarines. Submarine cruises carried out in the 1980s and 1990s have been used in our validation.

The coupled ice-ocean model used here is an Atlantic-Arctic version (Drange *et al.*, 1999) of the Miami Isopycnic Coordinate Ocean Model (MICOM) (Bleck *et al.*, 1992), coupled with the dynamic sea ice model of Harder (1996) and the thermodynamical module of Drange (1996).

The ocean model was chosen as it has proven to do well in modeling studies of the Atlantic Ocean, e.g. Bleck *et al.* (1992) and New *et al.* (1995). A favorable aspect of isopycnic models is their ability to provide high vertical resolution in regions with strong vertical density gradients and to suppress numerical diffusion across isopycnals. A drawback is low vertical resolution in weakly stratified regions, such as in the central Arctic ocean and on the Arctic shelves. However, an isopycnic model by Oberhuber [1993] used in the Arctic and the Nordic seas (Holland *et al.* (1996), Aukrust and Oberhuber (1995)), has shown that this type of ocean model has the capability of doing well in these regions. The dynamic ice model uses the Viscous-Plastic rheology, which was pioneered by Hibler [1979]. Results from the SIMIP and other similar studies indicate that variants of plastic rheologies give the most realistic large scale flow of sea ice Arbetter *et al.* (1999), Kreyscher *et al.* (2000).

For validation of the model system it is of utmost importance that the atmospheric forcing fields are of reliable quality. For the model simulation we had the choice between forcing from 1) the National Centers for Environmental Prediction (NCEP)/National Center for Atmospheric Research (NCAR) Reanalysis project for 1958–1998 and, 2) the European Center for Medium range Weather Forecasting (ECMWF) reanalysis project (ERA-15) for the period December 1978–February 1994. To ensure minimal effects of model spinup on our results, and because of the greater overlap with the time span of SSMI–SMMR data, we used the NCEP/NCAR reanalysis in the simulation reported here.

The paper is organized as follows: In section 2 and 3 the coupled ice-ocean model and the satellite data set are presented. In section 2.4, the total sea ice extent and area are examined, and it is demonstrated that trends in the satellite data are generally well reproduced by the model. The spatial and temporal differences between the data sets are studied in section 2.5, with the aim to locate the majority of the model error. The correspondance between observed and simulated multi-year ice area and ice thickness are given in section 2.6, and in the last section conclusions and suggestions for improvement of the sea ice model are drawn.

2.2 Model description

As already stated, the model used is an Atlantic-Arctic version of MICOM (Drange *et al.*, 1999). Atmospheric forcing, provided by NCEP (Kalnay *et al.*, 1996), was applied at the marine interface, and the model was integrated from 1958 until 1998 after a 30 year spinup integration initialized with salinity and temperature climatologies from Levitus *et al.* (1994) and Levitus and Boyer (1994), respectively.

The dynamic part of the sea ice model is based upon the viscous-plastic rheology of Hibler III (1979), where sea ice is considered as a two-dimensional continuum. The dynamic ice model used in this study has been further modified by Harder [1996] to include description

of sea ice roughness and the age of sea ice, and utilizing the advection scheme of *Smolarkiewicz* [1984].

The parameterization of internal stress in ice is usually what distinguishes the dynamics of sea ice models. The internal stress tensor σ_{ij} is based upon the mechanical properties of ice, and represents a parameterization of contact forces between individual ice floes. The viscous-plastic rheology impose the following constitutive law on the sea ice

$$\sigma_{ij} = 2\eta(\dot{\epsilon}_{ij}, P)\dot{\epsilon}_{ij} \quad (2.1)$$

$$+[\zeta(\dot{\epsilon}_{ij}, P) - \eta(\dot{\epsilon}_{ij}, P)]\dot{\epsilon}_{kk}\delta_{ij} - \frac{P}{2}\delta_{ij}, \quad (2.2)$$

where $\dot{\epsilon}_{ij} = \frac{1}{2}(\partial u_i/\partial x_j + \partial u_j/\partial x_i)$ is the strain rate tensor, and repeated indices denote summation. Furthermore, $\zeta(\dot{\epsilon}_{ij}, P)$ and $\eta(\dot{\epsilon}_{ij}, P)$ are bulk and shear viscosities respectively, and P is the internal pressure of the ice, or ice ‘‘strength’’ (equation 2.7). The viscosities ζ and η are given as in *Hibler* [1979]

$$\zeta(\dot{\epsilon}_{ij}, P) = \frac{P}{2\Delta(\dot{\epsilon}_{ij})}, \quad (2.3)$$

and

$$\eta(\dot{\epsilon}_{ij}, P) = \frac{\zeta(\dot{\epsilon}_{ij}, P)}{e^2}, \quad (2.4)$$

where

$$\Delta(\dot{\epsilon}_{ij}) = [(\dot{\epsilon}_{11}^2 + \dot{\epsilon}_{22}^2)(1 + \frac{1}{e^2}) + 4e^{-2}\dot{\epsilon}_{12}^2] \quad (2.5)$$

$$+ 2\dot{\epsilon}_{11}\dot{\epsilon}_{22}(1 - \frac{1}{e^2})]^{1/2}. \quad (2.6)$$

Here e is the eccentricity of the elliptic yield curve which determines the onset of the plastic regime of the viscous-plastic rheology. The eccentricity is set to 2.0 in the model, a commonly used value for this parameter *Hibler III* (1979). The rheology causes ice to strongly resist convergent motion while giving little resistance to divergent motion. For small strain rates the sea ice moves as a fluid with large viscosities, while for high strain rates the stresses are situated upon an elliptic yield curve in stress space.

In the model, each grid cell is splitted into one fraction with ice of thickness h_i and one with open water. The pressure or ice strength P is determined by F , the concentration of ice and \bar{h}_i , the mean ice thickness in a grid cell

$$P = P^*\bar{h}_i e^{-C(1-F)}, \quad (2.7)$$

where the mean ice thickness is related to the actual ice thickness through the relation: $\bar{h}_i = h_i F$. Here the empirical constant C is set to 20 and P^* is set to 27500 N m⁻². The model advects the ice thickness, the concentration and snow thickness with source terms reflecting freezing and melting of ice and accumulation of snow.

The thermodynamic part of the ice model balances heat fluxes at the water-ice-air interfaces and deduces the freezing and melting rates. The conductive fluxes are linear in ice and snow, so no thermal inertia occurs in the ice. A lead parameterization is included by keeping the total ice concentration less than $F_{max} = 0.99$. Details of ice thermodynamics and lead parameterization are found in *Drange* (1996), and are briefly given in the appendix.

Figure 2.1: Projection of the numerical grid from the coupled ocean-sea ice model upon the same map as used with SMMR/SSMI data. The model sea mask (grey) has an artificially wide channel that connects Baff in Bay with the central Arctic Ocean.

The ocean model MICOM is a layer model using potential density as the vertical coordinate, and the uppermost layer is a mixed layer with freely evolving density. The model is hydrostatic in each layer and has prognostic equations for horizontal momentum and layer thicknesses. Interior layer temperatures are determined prognostically, and salinities are determined diagnostically by the equation of state, given potential density and temperature. In the mixed layer, temperature and salinity are both determined prognostically. The mixed-layer thickness is determined from an energy equation where turbulence is maintained against viscous dissipation, buoyancy fluxes and wind stress (Gaspar *et al.*, 1990). In addition to entrainment/detrainment between the mixed-layer and interior layers a diapycnal mixing is prescribed between the interior layers, with mixing coefficient $10^{-7}/N$ ($\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-2}$), where N (s^{-1}) is the Brunt-Väisälä frequency (Roland W. Grawood *et al.*, 1985).

The model equations are discretized on a C-grid constructed with a mapping similar to the conformal mapping of Bentsen *et al.* (1999), and the momentum equations are solved with a split-explicit numerical scheme (Bleck and Smith, 1990). If we examine the model grid for the same area as that of the SMMR/SSMI data (Figure 2.1), we see that the model has highest resolution at about 67°N with grid sizes down to 45 km. The model domain includes the Arctic Ocean and extends to 20°S latitude. The domain is considered as a closed basin with relaxation towards monthly climatological values of salinity and temperature at the boundaries (Levitus *et al.* (1994), Levitus and Boyer (1994)). Vertically the model has 23 layers, with potential density ranging from 24.04 to 28.11. The time step used in the computations was 20 minutes for ocean model and sea ice thermodynamics, the sea ice dynamics was updated every 24 hours, whereas the atmospheric forcing was updated every 12 hours.

2.3 Validation data

The National Snow and Ice Data Center (NSIDC) provides the SSMI/SMMR brightness temperatures necessary to calculate sea ice concentrations. They are distributed on 304×448 pixel grids where the Earth is projected onto the grids using a polar stereographic projection true at 70°N . Due to satellite orbits and swath widths a circular region near the Arctic pole is out of sensor range. For the SMMR sensor this is the region poleward of 84.6°N and for the SSMI sensors it is the region poleward of 87.6°N . The NORSEX algorithm Svendsen *et al.* (1983) was used to calculate sea ice concentration from brightness temperatures, and the resulting data sets from the SSMI and SMMR sensors were merged as in E. *et al.* (1997). When we created the combined time series from November 1978 to July 1998 the entire region poleward of 84.6°N was excluded from the SSMI data set, as in the SMMR data set.

Additionally the sensors can be used to discern between Multi-Year Ice (MYI) and First-Year Ice (FYI) because these ice types have different emissivity characteristics. During summer the melting snow layer on the ice becomes the dominant emitter and therefore it is not possible to distinguish FYI and MYI by microwave characteristics at this time of year Comiso (1990). A merged data set describing MYI in the winter months November–March from 1978–1998 was created as in Johannessen *et al.* (1999).

In addition we have compared the ice thickness fields of the model with data from US and British submarine cruises. The data sets were obtained from the NSIDC, and they are referred to by their cruise reference names given on the NSIDC web site, <http://nsidc.org>. The cruise reference names and sailing periods are given in Table 3.

2.4 Sea-ice extent and area

The parameters examined in this section are *ice extent*, the area within the ice-ocean margin limited by the 15 % ice concentration contour; and *ice area*, the area of ocean covered by ice within the 15% ice concentration contour.

To properly compare the model data with the satellite sensor data the comparison was done over a region that was common to both. This was achieved in three steps, first by projecting the model land mask onto the satellite land mask so that areas seen as land in the model were not included in the satellite-derived data. This region still contained some land areas, so if a model grid cell contained islands or shore lines, this area was subtracted from the grid cell area when calculating model sea ice area and extent. Finally, the area poleward of 84.6°N not included in the satellite data was excluded from the model data. In the following the model and satellite-derived sea ice concentrations will be compared over this common region.

2.4.1 Monthly averages

The time series of monthly averaged sea ice extent from the satellite and model data are shown in Figure 2.4.1. The period covered is November 1978–July 1998, and the inset shows the average seasonal cycles for this time period. A corresponding figure for sea ice area is shown in Figure 2.3. From the two figures we see that the model consequently underestimates the sea ice extent and area. From the inset in Figure 2.4.1 we observe that, on average, the model error in sea ice extent lies between $1\text{--}2 \times 10^6 \text{ km}^2$ for most of the year, and is largest in winter and summer. The model error in sea ice area (Figure 2.3) is somewhat smaller during

Figure 2.2: Time series of sea ice extent from satellite sensors (thick line) and model (thin line). The inset shows the average seasonal cycles.

winter ($\sim 1 \times 10^6 \text{ km}^2$), but increases to about $2 \times 10^6 \text{ km}^2$ in summer. The seasonal variation in sea ice area and extent is reasonably well described by the model, although the values are too low.

Having obtained sea ice area and extent we can examine the quantity

$$A_p = \frac{\text{Sea-ice area}}{\text{Sea-ice extent}}, \quad (2.8)$$

which is a measure of the average sea ice concentration within the 15% ice concentration contour. A time series of this quantity is shown for model and satellite derived data in Figure 2.4 along with an inset showing the average seasonal cycles. From this figure we see that the model on average shows too low sea ice concentrations within the ice pack in summer, and to high concentrations in winter.

The miscalculation of sea ice concentrations in the model can create large errors in the heat fluxes between the ocean and atmosphere. In summer a too large open water area within the ice pack will receive short wave radiation. The actual lead parameterization the model uses will influence the error in A_p in summer through lateral melt, and the error in sea ice area will also be influenced by this. The too high average model concentrations in winter occurs because the model shows no spatially smooth transition from 15% to 100% ice concentration, a feature that is present in the satellite-derived data. This could be caused by the larger grid cell size of the model as compared to the satellite data.

2.4.2 Trends from anomalies

The error in the model follow a similar pattern every year, both in sea ice area and extent (Figures 2.4.1 and 2.3). This suggests that long term trends present in the satellite data are present in the simulated sea ice field too. The anomalies in sea ice extent from model and

Figure 2.3: Time series of sea ice area from satellite sensors (thick line) and model (thin line). The inset shows the average seasonal cycles.

satellite data are shown in Figure 2.6. The anomalies were calculated by subtracting the average seasonal cycle (inset in Figure 2.4.1) from the monthly means. On the basis of these anomaly plots we can estimate trends in sea ice extent using linear least squares fit (LSF) analysis. We focus on sea ice extent because the sea ice area has a similar behavior regarding the anomalies. The following results should not be directly compared to results from other studies of SMMR/SSMI-derived sea ice area and extent, e.g. E. *et al.* (1997), Parkinson *et al.* (1999), because here we consider these parameters over a region common to the model domain and the satellite coverage. As already mentioned this means excluding the area poleward of 84.6°N and some regions containing ice in the satellite data.

For the entire time series November 1978 to July 1998, the LSF trends from the model and satellite sea ice extent are markedly different. The trend from the satellite data is $-12 \times 10^3 \text{ km}^2 \text{ yr}^{-1}$ for the period November 1978 to July 1998. The negative trend is significant, as the hypothesis of a positive trend is rejected at the 99% confidence level. In the region considered and for this time period (1978–1998), this adds up to a decrease of 3% relative to a yearly mean value of sea ice extent. The trend from the model data is $0.2 \times 10^3 \text{ km}^2 \text{ yr}^{-1}$, and the correlation coefficient between the model and satellite sea ice extent time series is 0.48. A reason for the difference in trends is visible in the anomaly plot in Figure 2.6: In the period from 1981 to 1983 the anomaly curves differ considerably, while the period before and after show better agreement. That the model has large errors in this period is also visible in sea ice extent and area (Figures 2.4.1 and 2.3), and in the pseudofraction A_p (Figure 2.4).

The mismatch between model data and satellite data in 1981–1983 was studied by examining the applied forcing fields. Air temperature is an important factor for creation of sea ice for most regions in the Arctic, and examination of the NCEP temperature fields revealed high temperatures in regions along the coast of Siberia, Alaska and Canada in the winter of 79/80, 80/81 and 81/82. These regions are close to the Novosibirskiye islands, south of

Figure 2.4: Time series of the pseudofraction (equation 2.8) from satellite sensors (thick line) and model (thin line). The inset shows the average seasonal cycles.

Novaja Zemlja, north of Point Barrow and close to Banks Island.

A comparison of the NCEP temperature data with temperature data from the European Center for Medium-range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) shows that the two fields are quite different in the Arctic for the winters 79/80, 80/81 and 81/82. Figure 2.7 shows the mean monthly temperature anomalies for January 1981 from the NCEP data set. Along the coast of Siberia and Canada we see large anomalies in the NCEP temperature field, features which are nonexistent in the ECMWF temperature field. Ice production along the Siberian Coast is particularly important for the net Arctic ice production, because of the Transpolar Drift Stream (TPDS). The TPDS transports ice away from the Siberian Coast towards Fram Strait, and this divergence leads to high growth rates on the Siberian Coast. As a consequence, high surface air temperatures in this region could have a large impact upon the total Arctic ice production.

The high-temperature areas in the NCEP field do not cause a significant reduction in the winter sea ice extent of the model, but the reduced ice production due to high temperatures causes a more rapid decay of the ice cover and low values of summer sea ice extent. The situation is most dramatic in the winter 80/81, when the temperature anomalies not only cause a low sea ice extent in the model, but a significant reduction in total sea ice volume (Figure 2.8). The discrepancy between sea ice concentrations from the NCEP-forced model and satellite data, and the discrepancy between NCEP and ECMWF temperature fields suggests that the winter time NCEP temperatures used in the period 1979–1982 are in error at the specified locations.

If we exclude the above mentioned period of disagreement, the satellite-derived and simulated sea ice extent trends are closely matched. When we choose the period January 1984 to July 1998 the LSF trend from model and satellite sea ice extent is $-12 \times 10^3 \text{ km}^2 \text{ yr}^{-1}$ and $-11 \times 10^3 \text{ km}^2 \text{ yr}^{-1}$, respectively. For both model and satellite data the hypothesis of a

Figure 2.6: Time series of sea ice extent anomalies from model (thin line) and satellite data (thick line). The anomalies are based on the average seasonal cycle.

Figure 2.7: NCEP temperature anomaly field for January 1981. The field shows unrealistic temperature anomalies (up to 30 K) along the Siberian and Canadian coasts.

Figure 2.8: Anomalies in total sea ice volume from the model. The anomalies are based on the average seasonal cycle.

Table 2.1: Trends from least square fit of satellite and model data. Trends are estimated from both model and satellite data. The change in percent per decade $\Delta\%$ is based on mean yearly values of parameters examined. Confidence levels are based on rejection of the hypothesis of a 0 slope. '-' denotes that 95% confidence is not reached.

Parameter	T_{obs}	Model data			Satellite data		
		Trend ($\times 10^3 \text{ km}^2/\text{yr}$)	$\Delta\%$ pr. dec. (%)	Confidence level(%)	Trend ($\times 10^3 \text{ km}^2/\text{yr}$)	$\Delta\%$ pr. dec. (%)	Confidence level(%)
Ice Area	Nov78-Jul98	1 ± 3	0.1	-	-18 ± 3	-2.5	99
Ice Area	Jan84-Jul98	-14 ± 3	-2.0	99	-17 ± 4	-2.3	99
Ice Extent	Nov78-Jul98	0 ± 4	0.0	-	-12 ± 3	-1.5	99
Ice Extent	Jan84-Jul98	-12 ± 4	-1.5	99	-11 ± 4	-1.4	99

positive trend is rejected at the 99% confidence level, and the correlation coefficient between the model and satellite data sea ice extent time series is now 0.68. The close match of the trends is not entirely representative of the level of agreement between model and satellite sea ice extent, because the individual trends are dependent upon the time period considered.

To examine this further we estimated the sea ice extent trends over the time interval T_{start} to July 1998, and varied the starting time T_{start} . Figure 2.9 displays the results for model and satellite data sea ice extent, and shows that the close match between sea ice extent trends over the period January 84–July 98 was close to being the best one. However, the trends show reasonably good agreement for T_{start} between 1982 and 1986, with both model and satellite data showing approximately the same negative trends. As T_{start} get closer to July 1998, the 95% confidence intervals for each trend gets very large, and comparison of the slopes proves less. As the time series get shorter the trends become more dependent upon individual anomalies. From Figure 2.6 we see that some extreme anomalies in the 1990s are not properly captured by the model. This causes a tendency towards positive model trends for T_{start} close to 1990.

For the sea ice area we see similar results as for sea ice extent, and the trends from both sea ice area and extent are given in Table 1.

Figure 2.9: Estimated trend in linear least square fit of sea ice extent anomalies from model (thin line) and satellite (thick line) data. The trends are estimated over the time period T_{start} –July 1998, and the curves are created by varying T_{start} .

Table 2.2: Trends from least square fit of satellite data. Symbols are explained in Table 2.1. Trends are estimated over the period November 78–July 98.

Parameter	Trend ($\times 10^3 \text{ km}^2/\text{yr}$)	$\Delta\%$ pr. dec.(%)	Confidence level(%)
Ice Area	-33 ± 3	-3.5	99
Ice Extent	-25 ± 3	-2.3	99

2.4.3 Trends for the entire Arctic from satellite

Table 2 contains trends from the LSF analysis when we consider only the satellite data from the entire Arctic region, with exception of the region poleward of 84.6°N . The trends for the period November 1978 to July 1998 are $-25 \times 10^3 \text{ km}^2\text{yr}^{-1}$ and $-33 \times 10^3 \text{ km}^2\text{yr}^{-1}$ for sea ice extent and area, respectively. The hypothesis of a positive trend is rejected at the 99% confidence level for both sea ice extent and area. The trends represent a reduction of 2.3% per decade in sea ice extent and a reduction of 3.5% per decade in sea ice area, where the percentages are relative to mean values of sea ice extent and area for the entire Arctic. The trends are comparable to those of E. *et al.* (1997) and Parkinson *et al.* (1999), although the latter has a greater decrease in sea ice extent than in sea ice area.

2.5 Temporal and spatial distribution of the model error in ice concentration

To obtain information on the spatial and temporal distribution of the model error in sea ice concentration, we used Principal Component (PC) analysis. The first step in PC analysis is to convert the original data set into a data set describing anomalies. The anomaly data set can be written as a time dependent p -dimensional vector $\mathbf{c}_a(t)$, which can be considered as a time dependent spatial map, with each component corresponding to a scalar value in position $\mathbf{x}_j, j = 1, \dots, p$:

$$\mathbf{c}_a(t) = [c_a(t, \mathbf{x}_1), c_a(t, \mathbf{x}_2), \dots, c_a(t, \mathbf{x}_p)]^T, \quad (2.9)$$

where T denotes transpose.

In the PC analysis approach we represent our data set with p points in space and n points in time as a $n \times p$ matrix

$$\mathbf{Z} = [\mathbf{c}_a(\mathbf{t}_1) \ \mathbf{c}_a(\mathbf{t}_2) \ \dots \ \mathbf{c}_a(\mathbf{t}_n)]^T. \quad (2.10)$$

By using the eigenvectors of the covariance matrix $\frac{1}{n-1} \mathbf{Z}^T \mathbf{Z}$, we are able to decompose the data set in the following manner

$$\mathbf{c}_a(t_k) = \sum_{j=1}^p a_j(t_k) \mathbf{e}_j. \quad (2.11)$$

The PC analysis splits our data set into orthogonal eigenvectors \mathbf{e}_j of the covariance matrix and time dependent parts $a_j(t_k)$ given through the dot product $a_j(t_k) = \mathbf{c}_a(t_k) \cdot \mathbf{e}_j$. What separates this from many similar looking splittings is that the time dependent parts $a_j(t_k)$ are uncorrelated and the vectors \mathbf{e}_j are orthogonal in p -space, this makes it possible to sort the modes ($a_j(t_k) \mathbf{e}_j$) according to their contribution to the total variance of the data set. Following the terminology of Preisendorfer (1988), the components $a_j(t_k)$ are called Principal Components (PCs) and the vectors or spatial maps \mathbf{e}_j are called Empirical Orthogonal Functions (EOFs).

To examine the model error we created the following data set: For a given month we calculated the mean sea ice concentration from the satellite data for each model grid cell. This involves both temporal and spatial averaging as the model grid is coarser than the satellite grid. These values were subtracted from the monthly averaged model sea ice concentration for the respective grid cells, and the resulting data set describes the model deviation from the satellite data for each month in the period November 1978 to July 1998.

The mean deviation of the model relative to the satellite data for the entire time interval is shown in Fig. 2.10.

This plate shows the areas that have a bias towards too low or too high sea ice concentrations. It is evident, as it was from sea ice extent and sea ice area, that the model has generally too low sea ice concentrations. In the Barents Sea, the Fram Strait and along the coast of east Greenland the model shows, on average, an ice concentration deficit in excess of 30%. The mean model deviation is less pronounced (a deficit of 10-15%) in the Davis Strait, along the coast of Newfoundland, and in a sector from the Beaufort Sea along the Siberian Coast towards the Laptev Sea. There are also some regions with positive deviation, but these are small compared to the regions with negative values.

The anomaly data set used in the PC analysis was created by subtracting the mean model deviation (Fig. 2.10) from the model-deviation data set. The resulting data set contains

Figure 2.10: Mean deviation of model sea ice concentration relative to satellite derived sea ice concentrations (model minus satellite). Concentration is measured in percentages (%).

information on the seasonal variation in the model deviation. The first and strongest mode (measured as contribution to the variance of the data set) explains 28% of the model-deviation variance. The first EOF is shown in Plate 2.11, and the first PC is shown in Figure 2.12 with an inset of its average seasonal cycle. The first PC shows a similar pattern from year to year, and the first mode describes the seasonal variation of the model deviation.

By using the mean deviation and the first PC analysis mode, a reconstruction of the model deviation is obtained. The mean value of the first PC has negative values in the period November–May (see inset in Figure 2.12). This means that the red/yellow areas in the first EOF in Plate 2.11 contribute negatively to the model deviation for this time of the year. Since the mean deviation in Plate 2.10 is mostly negative in the regions which are red/yellow in the first EOF, the red/yellow areas in Plate 2.11 indicate too low sea ice concentrations in the model during winter. The blue areas in the first EOF contribute positively in November–May, but since the mean deviation is negative in these areas the resulting approximation to the model deviation is close to zero. From these observations we conclude that the model has too low winter time sea ice concentrations in the Barents Sea and the Southeast Coast of

Figure 2.11: First empirical orthogonal function in model deviation from satellite data (model minus satellite).

Greenland (up to ~60% underestimate), off the coast of Newfoundland, in the Labrador Sea and in the Odden ice tongue between Iceland and Spitsbergen (up to ~30% underestimate).

A similar analysis for the period June–October show that the first PC multiplied with its EOF give values in the red/yellow regions in Plate 2.11 which more or less cancels with the values in the same regions in the model mean deviation, whereas the blue regions in Plate 2.11 will have too low sea ice concentrations in summer. This means that the model has too low summer time sea ice concentrations in the Fram Strait (up to ~80% underestimate), and in the blue area stretching from the Beaufort Sea to the Kara Sea (up to ~50% underestimate).

From the PC analysis we see that the strongest model underestimate (in summer and winter) occurs along the sea ice margin. The regions with the strongest underestimate from the PC analysis indicate a receded ice edge as compared to satellite data. In addition the model show too low sea ice concentrations within the ice pack in summer.

Figure 2.12: First principal component of model deviation from satellite data. First mode contributes 28% to the total variation of the model deviation. The inset shows the average seasonal cycle.

2.6 Multi-year ice area and ice thickness

Ice thickness is a prognostic variable in the sea ice model, but ice thickness observations are not possible to obtain from the SMMR/SSMI sensors. To quantify changes in the composition of the ice cover using passive microwave data, the area of Multi-Year Ice (MYI) can be considered. With MYI we mean sea ice which has survived at least one melt season. We still consider sea ice in the region common to both satellite coverage and model domain as presented in the beginning of section 2.4.

To obtain an estimate of the MYI area from the model we consider two approaches: The first approach is based on the results of Johannessen *et al.* (1999), which propose that the minimum summer ice area is a good estimate of the MYI area. In this approach, the MYI area in the model is set equal to the area of sea ice with a thickness in excess of 0.5 m at the time of sea-ice area minimum. The minimum sea ice area may not be entirely descriptive of the area of ice that survives summer melt, since the ice still melts or freezes in different parts of the ice pack. This is the reason for choosing the 0.5 m cutoff thickness, as it ensures that we really have ice surviving the melt season in our calculations.

The second method for calculating MYI area calculates the time of the Local Temporal Minima (LTM) in each grid cell of the model. LTM is the time during summer when the local sea ice concentration starts to increase, and will be different for different locations in the ice pack. The total sea ice area from this approach is the sum of the model grid cell sea ice areas at LTM. The LTM approach gives a sea ice area that corresponds well with the MYI area (Gloersen *et al.*, 1992).

In Figure 2.13 we have plotted the two model derived estimates of MYI area along with SMMR/SSMI MYI area, the latter taken from Johannessen *et al.* (1999). For the SMMR/SSMI MYI area, each of the five individual monthly means from November to March are plotted each winter, along with the average winter-MYI area estimated from these five monthly means. As we can see the two methods for the model (the bars in the figure) give approximately the same results and show the same variation, with the LTM area being slightly

Figure 2.13: Estimated MYI area from model and satellite data. Bars are from model, where the white bar is from LTM procedure and the black bar is obtained with cutoff thickness of 0.5m at the time of minimum sea ice area. The broken lines are individual measurements of MYI area each winter from SMMR/SSMI sensors, whereas the dashed line is the mean value of the individual SMMR/SSMI MYI areas each winter.

smaller. The satellite MYI area differs considerably from the model MYI area ($\sim 2 \times 10^6$ km²). This is to be expected because the largest errors and largest anomalies of the sea ice area occur during summer, and because the model MYI area is highly dependent upon the minimum sea ice area in summer.

Note the low values of MYI area in winter 81/82 and 82/83, corresponding with minimum in sea ice extent and volume in 1982 (see Figures 2.6 and 2.8). The model needs several years to rebuild the ice volume lost due to the high temperature anomalies in the NCEP forcing in 1979–1982, but in the period starting at about 1984 the model performs better. For the entire period November 1978–July 1998 the correlation between the model MYI area and winter-averaged satellite-derived MYI area is 0.48, while for the period 1984–1998 the correlation is 0.59.

The MYI area is related to the total volume of the sea ice. Since MYI is typically thicker than FYI, a reduction of MYI area could reflect changes in the mean thickness of the perennial ice (Johannessen *et al.*, 1999). The trend in the simulated MYI area over the time period 1984–1998 is -30×10^3 km² yr⁻¹, whereas the reduction in MYI area from satellite data over the same time period is -32×10^3 km² yr⁻¹, which corresponds well with that of the model.

To assess changes in the simulated ice thickness we start by considering two estimates of model MYI thickness. First, a mean spatial MYI thickness which is the MYI volume divided by MYI extent, this will include the zero thickness of open water areas when calculating the mean thickness. Secondly, we consider a mean intrinsic MYI thickness which we define as MYI volume divided by MYI area, an estimate of the average thickness of the MYI ice floes. The trend of the model in both mean spatial and intrinsic MYI thickness is -2 cm yr⁻¹ for the time period 1984–1998.

In Rothrock *et al.* (1999) it is estimated that there has been an average reduction in ice thickness of approximately 4 cm yr⁻¹ from the 1958–1976 period to the 1990s, a result based on sonar drafts obtained during submarine cruises. The data is mostly gathered in September months and data gathered in nearby months are extrapolated to September values by utilizing a modeled seasonal cycle of ice thickness. Ice thickness estimates are also available from the Russian “North Pole” drifting stations (Nagurnyi *et al.*, 1994), for the time period 1970–1991. The Russian data are based on surface measurements of elastic-gravity waves in the ice. Utilizing a dispersion relation one can find spatially-averaged estimates of ice thickness and the measurements indicate a reduction of the average ice thickness of 0.5 cm yr⁻¹ over the time period 1970–1991. We find that the simulated MYI thickness trends (-2 cm yr⁻¹) is of the same sign and comparable magnitude as the two measured trends (-4 cm yr⁻¹ and -0.5 cm yr⁻¹), but the different time periods considered for model and measurements restrict a more rigorous comparison.

In order to directly validate the simulated ice thickness we used sonar measurements gathered during American and British Navy submarine cruises in the 1980s and 1990s. While not providing the same continuous time series as the SMMR/SSMI derived sea ice concentration, the comparison with sonar thickness estimates provides a good indication of how well the model describes the large scale thickness distribution in the Arctic ice pack. In order to compare model output with sonar measurements we extracted the thickness from the model along the submarine tracks. In doing this, we used the mean value of the simulated field for the duration of the submarine cruise. Finally, we smoothed the data with a running mean of 200 km distance along the track.

The plots of the ice thickness from sonar estimates and model are shown in panels a–f in Fig. 2.14 and panels a–c in Fig. 2.15. Inset in the panels are plots of the tracks, where the

Figure 2.14: Panels a–f show model ice thickness (thin line) compared with ice thickness estimates from upward looking submarine sonars (thick line). The horizontal axis show the distance covered along the track (only including segments where measurements are performed). The letters 'S' and 'E' denote start and endpoints of the submarine cruise, respectively.

Figure 2.15: As Fig. 2.14. Panel d shows the scatter plot of model versus submarine sonar estimated ice thickness for all cruises, along with the regression line.

Table 2.3: Correlation between model and sonar data. The cruise identifiers are identical to the ones used at the NSIDC web site (http://nsidc.org/NOAA/ULS_Drafts). The overall correlation is 0.80.

Cruise:	UK87	1988a	1991	UK91	L2-92	SCICEX93	1994	SCICEX96	SCICEX97
Month :	May	May	March	April	April	September	April	September	September
r	0.72	0.98	0.76	-0.58	0.92	0.78	0.87	0.93	0.74

distance (x -axis) is increased only when measurements are reported. It is apparent that there is a high level of correlation in most of the tracks in Figure 2.14. The correlation between model and sonar data is 0.72 or higher in all but one of the tracks (panel d), which shows a correlation of -0.58 . It is probably not a coincidence that this happens for the shortest track. The low ice thickness in the model at the start of the cruise in panel d heavily influences the correlation of the data sets, while after a 300 km distance into the cruise the model show results in agreement with the submarine data. The correlations between model and sonar data are given in Table 3. Panel 15d summarizes the comparison with a scatter plot of thickness from model versus sonar thickness estimates, the overall correlation is found to be 0.80.

Generally, the agreement present in the correlation and in the ice thickness estimates indicates that the two components of the ice model are fairly realistic. In fact, the overall comparison with data from submarine cruises shows an unexpected level of realism in the simulated ice thickness field, and the simulated thickness seems to depict the real thickness field equally well in summer (September) as in late winter (March and April).

2.7 Discussion

In this study we have validated a coupled sea ice-ocean model using data from satellite-borne passive microwave sensors. The sea ice model is similar to one of the models in the SIMIP project (Kreyscher *et al.*, 2000), so our results should be of general interest for users of this type of sea ice model.

The first conclusion is that the model underestimates sea ice concentration in the Arctic. This can be seen through the too low values of sea ice extent and area (Figures 2.4.1 and 2.3). The underestimate of these values vary between 1×10^6 km² and 2×10^6 km², which is significant compared to the total values of sea ice area and extent which lie between 5×10^6 km² and 10×10^6 km² over the area studied. As a consequence, the model estimate of MYI area is too low by about 2×10^6 km², which is significant compared to the satellite derived MYI area of approximately 4×10^6 km².

Using principal component analysis the locations of the model errors in sea ice concentration in winter and summer are identified. In winter and summer we find that some of the error occur along the sea ice margin with a too receded ice edge. In summer we also see that there is too low sea ice concentrations within the ice pack, resulting in too much open water.

The analysis of sea ice area and extent is carried out over the period 1984–1998 instead of the entire available period 1978–1998 due to apparent errors in the NCEP temperature fields for the period 1979–1982. The observed anomalies in sea ice area and extent are picked up by the model, with a correlation coefficient between model and satellite sea ice extent of 0.68 over

the period 1984–1998. The model and satellite trends in sea ice extent are also very similar for this period with values of $-12 \times 10^3 \text{ km}^2 \text{ yr}^{-1}$ and $-11 \times 10^3 \text{ km}^2 \text{ yr}^{-1}$, respectively. It is also shown that the model performs well in describing trends in MYI area for this period: The model predicts a MYI area trend of $-30 \times 10^3 \text{ km}^2 \text{ yr}^{-1}$, while the satellite data give a MYI area trend of $-32 \times 10^3 \text{ km}^2 \text{ yr}^{-1}$.

Although the model underestimates the sea ice concentration, it is encouraging that the trends are so accurately represented by the model, and that there is a high correlation between model and satellite sea ice extent.

We briefly considered the average thickness of MYI and compared this to measurements from submarine sonar data (Rothrock *et al.*, 1999), and surface elastic-gravity waves (Nagurnyi *et al.*, 1994). The simulated MYI thickness trend of -2 cm yr^{-1} over the period 1984–1998 is bracketed between the trend of Rothrock *et al.* (1999) (-4 cm yr^{-1} , 1950s–1990s) and that of Nagurnyi *et al.* (1994) (-0.5 cm yr^{-1} , 1970–1991). Although the considered time periods are different, this shows that the model thickness trend is of comparable magnitude and the same sign as the measured thickness trends.

A direct comparison of ice thickness from the model and sonar data along several submarine cruises showed a high level of agreement. The correlations were > 0.7 in eight out of nine tracks, and the ice thicknesses were similar in the model and sonar data.

There can be several reasons for the detected model error in sea ice extent and area. First of all the model is relatively coarse, which naturally restricts its comparison with the more well-resolved satellite data. The parameterization of leads might be improved by using lateral melting rates as in Maykut and Perovich (1987), which could correct the model error within the ice pack in summer. In addition the thermodynamic part of the sea ice model (see appendix) does not include the effect of thermal inertia. For smoothly varying atmospheric forcing, thermal inertia is less important, but for the forcing used in this study the lack of thermal inertia could explain some of the error. The rheology used in the sea ice model could also lead to errors, due to slow response in numerical implementations of the Viscous-Plastic rheology. The Elastic-Viscous-Plastic rheology of Hunke and Dukowicz (1997) could perhaps give some improvement here, although this is speculations at the present stage.

Aside from the inherent aspects of the sea ice model, one should not forget that the forcing fields of the ocean-sea ice model also can lead to errors. For instance, apparent errors in the temperature fields were detected for the winters 1979–1982. In addition, the downward short wave radiation from NCEP data seems to be too high (e.g. Maslanik *et al.* (2000)), which is of importance for the sea ice concentration in summer. The latter observation can be partly compensated by adjusting the snow and ice albedo values, but such an adjustment would most likely fail if other forcing fields are applied. Furthermore, errors in the sea ice field can also be introduced by the ocean component of the model system, through errors in the water mass characteristics.

We conclude that the coupled ice-ocean model gives a good description of the sea ice variation and trends in the Arctic, with the main problem being an underestimate of the sea ice concentration. We also conclude that the presented model can be implemented in a fully coupled climate model as it is, possibly with some performance tuning integrations using some of the suggested modifications.

Finally, for the validation exercise, we have presented updated trends of sea ice area and extent from the entire Arctic derived from satellite data (Section 2.4.3). These trends confirm the negative trends from E. *et al.* (1997) and Parkinson *et al.* (1999).

2.8 Perturbed fresh water experiments

The model is first spun up for 40 years using a baroclinic time step of 1350 s. To prevent possible drift in the simulated thermodynamic fields, relaxation towards observed sea surface temperature (SST) and sea surface salinity (SSS) was applied during the spin up.

After the spin up period, the model was run for another year, with relaxation applied to temperature and salinity. The contribution to the change in surface salinity caused by relaxation for this year was then stored, with a temporal resolution of 30 days. A total of three simulations were then carried out, starting from year 40, in the following way:

Control simulation: No changes in the freshwater fluxes from the Arctic rivers. The simulation is run for 50 years by using the diagnosed surface salinity flux from year 41 as boundary condition for salinity.

PX2 simulation: The same as for the control simulation, but the freshwater fluxes from the Arctic rivers are increased by a factor of 2.

PX5 simulation: The same as for the control simulation, but the freshwater fluxes from the Arctic rivers are increased by a factor of 5.

The factors of 2 and 5 were motivated as follows: Simonsen (1996) computed the meltwater fluxes into the Atlantic Ocean, the Nordic Seas and the Arctic Ocean based on the paleo topography reconstruction of Peltier (1994). The obtained 1000 year mean meltwater fluxes into the Nordic Seas and the Arctic Ocean were comparable with the modern freshwater input during the last deglaciation (14-15 kyr BP). However, paleodata records indicate that the major melting lasted only 300-500 years (Fairbanks, 1989; Jones and Keigwin, 1988). Following Simonsen (1996), let us assume the major melting lasted for, say 500 years, and that for the remainder of the 1000 year period the meltwater flux was about 25% of the modern runoff. This would result in meltwater fluxes of about 0.2 Sv, i.e. a doubling of the modern river runoff.

An increase in the freshwater input to the Arctic Ocean of 0.4 Sv could be accomplished by melting about 13,000 km³ of ice during one year. For comparison, this is about half of the modelled total ice volume in the Arctic in March. Such a large input of freshwater is surely unrealistic for the present climate system. However, recent studies provide evidence for an ongoing melting in the Arctic Ocean (Johannessen *et al.*, 1999). Large changes in the Arctic freshwater budget can therefore not be ruled out in future climate scenarios.

2.9 The control simulation

2.9.1 Ocean circulation

The model describe the major current systems in the Arctic Ocean, the Nordic Seas and the north Atlantic Ocean (Figure 2.16). In the Arctic Ocean, two main features characterize the surface currents (Carmack, 1990). The first is the Transpolar Drift (TD), in which the surface waters of the Eurasian Basin move across the basin towards the North Pole and then towards the Fram Strait. The second is an anticlockwise flow in the Canadian Basin, the so called Beaufort Gyre (BG). Both of these currents are captured by the model.

In the Nordic Seas, two major currents characterize the circulation. These are the Norwegian Atlantic Current (NwAC) in the east, and the East Greenland Current (EGC) in

Figure 2.16: Sea surface velocity (cm s^{-1}) for March in year 1 of the control simulation.

the west, both of which are captured by the model (Figure 2.16). In the northern part of the Norwegian Sea there is a splitting of the NwAC. One branch continues into the Barents Sea through the Barents Opening while another continues north towards the Fram Strait as the West Spitsbergen Current (WSC) (Hopkins, 1991). In the vicinity of the Fram Strait there is a further splitting of the WSC. One branch turns southwest and continues toward the Greenland Strait as the Return Atlantic Current (RAC) (Manley, 1995), while another branch enters the Arctic Ocean through the Fram Strait.

In addition, a zonal, eastward flow between the EGC and the NwAC can be seen northeast of Iceland, often referred to as the East Iceland Current (EIC). All of these currents describe a large cyclonic circulation pattern in the Nordic Seas. In the Labrador Sea, a relatively strong Labrador Current (LC) can be seen to flow southward towards New Foundland. In the Irminger Basin, a branch of the NAD, the Irminger Current (IC), flows north towards the Greenland Strait where most of it is captured by the strong EGC, thus forming a cyclonic circulation pattern in this area.

Water masses and sea ice

The upper waters of the Arctic Ocean are characterized by a shallow mixed layer at or near the freezing point, overlying a pronounced cold halocline (Rudels *et al.*, 1996). The halocline is a layer with temperatures $< -1^\circ\text{C}$ and salinities between 30.4-34.4 psu, leading to a stable vertical density structure in the central Arctic. The model obtain a halocline at a depth of about 100 m (Figure 2.17a), which agree quite well with observations.

Figure 2.17: Salinity and temperature distribution for March in year 1 of the control simulation for a transect from Scotland to Alaska. **a** Salinity (psu) in contour intervals of 0.1 psu and **b** temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) in contour intervals of 0.3 $^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Another feature of the Arctic Ocean is related to a warm, saline intermediate layer at 200-900 m depths (Carmack, 1990). The origin of this water is the Atlantic Ocean, and it fills much of the Arctic at this depth. In the model, the Atlantic layer is not well reproduced (Figure 2.17b). The water at intermediate depths in the Arctic is too cold (by about 1°C). The reason for this is not yet understood, but it could be linked to a too intense cooling, and consequently surface mixing in the WSC south of the Fram Strait leading to cooling of the Atlantic water.

Warm and saline Atlantic Water (AW) ($T \sim 8^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $S \sim 35.2$ psu) can be seen to enter the Nordic Seas north of Scotland through the FSC (Figure 2.17). On its way northwards the water is cooled by various processes and subsducts to intermediate (500-1000 m) and deep levels. This modified AW often termed Atlantic Intermediate Water (AIW) (Manley, 1995), can be seen to enter the Arctic Ocean at about 700 m ($T \sim 0.2^{\circ}\text{C}$).

The north Atlantic is of major importance to the THC because it is one of the few places where deep water renewal takes place. Most of this deep water formation is believed to take place in the Greenland and Labrador Seas. The simulated mixed layer thickness can serve as an indicator of deep convection in the model. A relatively deep mixed layer is observed in the Greenland and Labrador Seas in winter, reaching as much as 1100 m just south of Svalbard (Figure 2.18b). The model is therefore at least qualitatively able to reproduce the formation of subsurface water masses in these regions. The model is also able to generate ice cover in fairly good agreement with climatologies derived from observations (Lisæter *et al.*,

Figure 2.18: **a.** Sea ice thickness (m) for March in year 1 of the control simulation. Contour intervals of 0.3 m. **b.** Mixed layer thickness (m) for March in year 1 of the control simulation. Contour intervals of 100 m. In addition the 50 m contour line is shown.

2000). In winter, the ice covers all of the Arctic Ocean, the Kara Sea and the western part of the Barents Sea (Figure 2.18a). Furthermore, there is an accumulation of sea ice in the Arctic Archipelago due to the BG.

2.9.2 Transports of mass and heat

The exchange of water masses between the Arctic Ocean and the North Atlantic takes place through three passages, the Arctic Archipelago, the Fram Strait, and the Barents Opening. The Arctic has a loss of about 1.2 Sv through the Arctic Archipelago, and a bigger loss of about 1.6 Sv through the Fram Strait (Figure 2.19a). However, there is a net inflow through the Barents Opening of about 2.8 Sv, yielding a balance of mass for this domain. Some seasonal variation can be seen in the transports through the Fram Strait and the Barents Opening, but not so much in the outflow through the Arctic Archipelago. In the model, the heat transport to the Arctic Ocean and the Barents Sea amounts to about 81 TW. Most of this transport occurs through the Barents Opening, where a net northward heat transport of about 64 TW occurs (Figure 2.19b). This is in good agreement with Simonsen and Haugan (1996) where the heat transport is estimated to be 60-80 TW.

In the Greenland Strait, there is a total southward volume transport of about 2.1 Sv (Figure 2.19a). Of this, about 0.9 Sv is due to transport in the intermediate and deep layers, while the export with the EGC in the surface is about 1.2 Sv. These estimates are lower than expected from literature where transport estimates of 3 Sv are found for both the EGC and the deep overflow (Hopkins, 1991). A too coarse resolution may be one of the reasons for this. A resolution of about 50 km is probably not enough to resolve all the features that is of importance for the circulation in this area. Also, the use of climatological forcing fields rather than synoptic fields gives too small transports (H. Drange, pers. comm.). On the other hand, literature estimates are often based on measurements *downstream* from the Greenland Iceland ridge, where the volume transports are larger. It is therefore not unlikely that an estimate of 6-

Figure 2.19: Total transports of mass and heat for the most important passages in the Nordic Seas and the Arctic Ocean in year 1 of the control simulation. **a** Volume transport (Sv) and **b** heat transport (TW). The annual mean northward (N) and southward (S) transports are also shown.

Figure 2.20: Difference in sea surface salinity from the control simulation in March year 50. **a** PX2 simulation, and **b** PX5 simulation. Dotted lines represent negative anomalies. Contour intervals of 0.5 psu. In addition the ± 0.1 contour lines are shown.

7 Sv (Worthington, 1970; Hopkins, 1991) for the net southward transport through Greenland Strait is too high. In view of this, it could be that the model is more consistent with nature than comparison with some literature estimates would indicate.

The model gives an inflow of Atlantic water over the IFR of about 2.6 Sv (Figure 2.19a). This is in good agreement with an estimate of 2.9 Sv for the Faroe Current based on current measurements (Hansen *et al.*, 1998), but 1.1 Sv below a 4 Sv estimate reported for the IFR in Hansen and Østerhus (2000). Estimates of the deep overflow through the FSC varies between 1.1-1.9 Sv in literature (Simonsen and Haugan, 1996). The model obtain a intermediate and

Figure 2.21: Difference from the control simulation in temperature (K) for the perturbed simulations for a transect from Alaska, through the Arctic Ocean, Fram Strait and the Nordic Seas to northern Scotland. **a** PX2 simulation and **b** PX5 simulation. Contour intervals of 0.2 K.

deep overflow of about 1.8 Sv, which is inside this range. Estimates of the inflow of Atlantic water through the FSC have varied a lot over the years, from about 2 Sv to as much as 10 Sv. Recent estimates based on observations is about 3 Sv (Hansen and Østerhus, 2000). The model obtain a total inflow to the Norwegian Sea of about 2.2 Sv in the surface and intermediate layers (Figure 2.19a), which is somewhat lower than expected from observations.

The heat transport over the Greenland-Scotland ridge amounts to about 158 TW (Figure 2.19b), which is too low compared to estimates given in literature (Simonsen and Haugan, 1996; Hansen and Østerhus, 2000). The major part of the heat transport takes place over the IFR (85 TW), which is in reasonable agreement with a 115 TW estimate given in Hansen and Østerhus (2000). The heat transport accross the FSC amounts to 65 TW in the model, which is only half that found in Hansen and Østerhus (2000).

Although the model is far from perfect, the control run still reproduces the major features of the modern ocean circulation in the north Atlantic, the Nordic Seas and the Arctic Ocean, and should therefore provide a fairly realistic oceanic state for perturbation experiments.

2.10 The perturbed simulations

2.10.1 Salinity and temperature

In the Arctic Ocean the major differences in the surface layer salinity compared to the control run can be seen in the vicinity of the river discharge areas in Canada, Siberia and Russia (Figure 2.20), and after 50 years all of the Arctic Ocean is influenced. Outside the Siberian coast, a freshwater belt follows the TD towards Fram Strait. A large part of this flow

Figure 2.22: Difference from the control simulation in the mixed layer thickness (m) in March year 50. **a** PX2 simulation and **b** PX5 simulation. Dotted lines is reduced mixed layer thickness. Contour intervals of 40 m.

enters the Canadian Basin, where it accumulates in the BG. Furthermore, positive salinity anomalies are found north of the Fram Strait and in the Eurasian Basin, caused by an increased inflow of Atlantic water through the Fram Strait (see below).

In the Nordic Seas, a slight increase in temperature can be seen in the NwAC at surface (Figure 2.21). This positive temperature anomaly can be seen all the way up to Fram Strait, where it subducts to about 500 m and enters the Arctic Ocean. However, at intermediate depths (500-1000 m) in the Nordic Seas, negative temperature anomalies are obtained. Part of the explanation for the negative temperature anomalies is found in the southwestern Greenland Sea and in the northern part of the Iceland Sea, where the mixed layer thickness increases compared to the control run (Figure 2.22). The increased maximum mixed layer thickness leads to increased loss of heat from the entrained waters. In this way, mass is added and heat is removed from the ventilated subsurface layers. For the PX5 simulation, an increased layer thickness can be seen in a belt extending from the Fram Strait through the western Greenland Sea and into the Iceland Sea in year 20 (Figure 2.23a). In year 50, this belt can be seen to extend further eastwards with the EIC before it turns and heads northward ending up in the eastern Greenland Sea (Figure 2.23b). Negative temperature anomalies are thus transported from intermediate depths in the western part of the Nordic Seas, to the eastern Greenland Sea (Figure 2.24).

The negative temperature anomalies are especially large at about 700 m depth just south of Fram Strait. The reduced mixed layer thickness in the central Greenland Sea (Figure 2.22) implies that the AW descends down to shallower depths in the perturbed simulations, and thus enters the Arctic ocean further up in the water column. A large portion (about 2/3) of this AIW will be recirculated with the RAC in the vicinity of the Fram Strait (Manley, 1995). A shallower recirculation of AW is therefore also a part of the explanation for the negative temperature anomalies seen at intermediate depths in the Nordic Seas.

Figure 2.23: Difference between the PX5 simulation and the control simulation in the thickness (m) of layer 14 for March in **a** year 20 and **b** year 50. Solid lines means increased thickness. Contour intervals of 30 m.

2.10.2 Sea ice and velocity

The reduced salinity in the Arctic Ocean modifies physical properties of the sea water. While pure freshwater freezes at 0°C , addition of salt lowers the freezing point of water to about -1.9°C at 35 psu. In the model, the freezing point of water is calculated as

$$T_f = 273.216 - 0.057 * S_m,$$

where T_f is the freezing point of sea water and S_m is the mixed layer salinity. A reduced salinity in the Arctic Ocean will therefore raise the freezing point of sea water, and consequently lead to an increased sea surface temperature in ice covered regions. In the Arctic Archipelago, the reduced salinity is accompanied by an increase in sea surface temperature of 0.10 K and 0.18 K for the PX2 and PX5 simulations, respectively (Figure 2.25).

The increased sea surface temperature in the Canadian Basin leads to melting of ice here (Figure 2.26). This reduced sea ice thickness in the central Arctic Ocean has a strong impact on the sea surface velocity (Figure 2.27). When the ice is reduced the sea ice velocity increases (not shown). The increased momentum is transferred to the ocean and leads to an intensified BG in the Arctic Ocean. In the PX5 simulation, the velocity can be seen to increase as much as 10 cm s^{-1} some places. The intensified BG also leads to more accumulation of ice in the Arctic Archipelago (Figure 2.26). Also, more water will accumulate at the center of the BG due to increased Ekman pumping, depressing the mixed layer in this area (Figure 2.22).

2.10.3 Transports of mass and heat

Due to the intensified BG, there is a gradual increase in the net southward transport across the Arctic Archipelago throughout the whole integration period, reaching almost 0.3 Sv and 0.5 Sv in year 50 of the PX2 and PX5 simulations, respectively (Figure 2.28). This increase in the southward transport is compensated further east through the Fram Strait where the net southward transport is reduced and through the Barents Opening where an increase in the net

Figure 2.24: Difference in temperature (K) between the PX5 simulation and the control simulation in layer 14 for March in **a** year 20 and **b** year 50. Dotted lines represent negative temperature anomalies. Contour intervals of 0.3 K.

Figure 2.25: Difference in **a** temperature (K) and **b** salinity (psu) between the perturbed simulations and the control simulations for the Arctic Archipelago. Negative values indicate reduced temperature (salinity). Solid lines are the PX2 simulation, while dotted lines are the PX5 simulation.

northward transport is evident during the last 10 years of the integration period (not shown). In the Greenland Strait, the most salient feature is a gradual increase in the net southward transport for the last 15 years of the integration period (Figure 2.28). In the PX5 simulation

this is particularly evident with an increased southward transport in excess of 0.2 Sv in year 50.

The net northward transport of Atlantic water across a section from the southern tip of Greenland to Ireland increases gradually throughout the integration period, reaching about 0.3 Sv and 0.5 Sv for the PX2 and PX5 simulations, respectively (Figure 2.29). This increased northward transport thus compensates for the increased southward transport of mass through the Arctic Archipelago.

Figure 2.26: Difference from the control simulation in sea ice thickness (m) for **a** the PX2 simulation and **b** the PX5 simulation. Dotted lines are reduced sea ice thickness. Contour intervals of 0.3 m.

Most of the Atlantic water enters the Nordic Seas through the FSC, where an increase in the net northward transport water can be seen from year 20 and onwards in both the perturbed simulations, reaching 0.2 Sv and 0.4 Sv for the PX2 and PX5 simulations, respectively (Figure 2.29). As a consequence of this, the heat transport to the Nordic Seas through this passage increases to about 8 TW and 16 TW in year 50 in the PX2 and PX5 simulations, respectively (Figure 2.30). The changes in the transports across the IFR are similar, but somewhat smaller than for the FSC.

2.10.4 Intermediate and deep water formation

The modelled mixed layer thickness is the best measure of the formation of subsurface water masses in the model. In the Labrador Sea, the initial response to the increased fresh-water input is a rapid decrease in the mixed layer thickness (Figure 2.31a). However, from year 10 and onwards a gradual recovery can be seen almost restoring the mixed layer to its original thickness in year 50. In the Greenland Sea the major reduction in the mixed layer thickness takes place between year 10 to year 20 in the perturbed simulations, while for the rest of the period the mixed layer thickness remain relatively stable (Figure 2.31b).

The reason for the recovery and stabilization of the mixed layer thickness in the Labrador Sea and Greenland Sea, respectively, is the increased northward transport of saline water with the NAD (Figure 2.27 and 2.29). As a result of the intensified NAD, more salt will

Figure 2.27: Difference from the control simulation in the annual mean surface velocity (cm s^{-1}) in year 50 for **a** the PX2 simulation and **b** the PX5 simulation. Shaded areas indicate an increase in absolute velocity greater than 1 cm s^{-1} .

be transported with the subpolar gyre into the Labrador Sea and northward into the Nordic Seas, increasing the density, and thus compensating for the increased freshwater input.

2.11 Discussion

The model results indicate that increased river runoff in the Arctic Ocean have a stabilizing effect on the THC in the North Atlantic. The reason for this is linked to the thermodynamic and dynamic response to the increased freshwater in the central Arctic Ocean (Figure 2.32). The reduced sea surface salinity increases the freezing point of sea water, leading to melting of ice in the Canadian Basin. As a result of this, momentum is transferred to the surface layer, followed by an intensified BG. This in turn increases the southward transport of mass through the Arctic Archipelago. Since the Arctic Ocean, the Barents Sea and the Nordic Seas constitute a closed system, this water has to be replaced. In the model, this is accomplished through an intensified NAD.

In global warming scenarios a typical response in climate models is increased evaporation at low latitudes due to heating of the surface waters, and increased precipitation model runoff at high latitudes (Latif *et al.*, 2000). Some of these models show substantial reductions in the overturning circulation with possible large climatic impacts in northern Europe in the next century (e.g., Manabe and Stouffer (1994), /incitewoo99). However, in Latif *et al.* (2000) a different model response is found. There, large-scale air-sea interactions in the tropics lead to anomalously high salinities in the tropical Atlantic. These anomalies are advected northward into the sinking regions, thereby increasing the surface density and compensating the effects of the local warming and freshening. A similar mechanism is operating in the model experiments presented here.

Figure 2.28: Timeseries showing the difference from the control simulation in the annual mean net southward volume transport (Sv) for **a** the PX2 simulation and **b** the PX5 simulation through the Arctic Archipelago (solid), Fram Strait (dashed) and Greenland Strait (dotted). Negative values indicate reduced transport.

Figure 2.29: Timeseries showing the difference from the control simulation in the annual mean net northward volume transport (Sv) for **a** the PX2 simulation and **b** the PX5 simulation through the Greenland-Ireland section (solid), the Iceland-Faroe Ridge (dashed) and the Faroe Shetland Channel (dotted). Negative values indicate reduced transport.

The results furthermore highlights the importance of the Arctic Archipelago in controlling the freshwater budget of the Arctic Ocean, supporting the findings of Goosse *et al.* (1997). Many ice-ocean models with coarse grids do not have a good representation of the complicated

Figure 2.30: Timeseries showing the difference from the control simulation in the annual mean net northward heat transport (TW) for **a** the PX2 simulation and **b** the PX5 simulation through the Greenland-Ireland section (solid), the Iceland-Faroe Ridge (dashed) and the Faroe Shetland Channel (dotted). Negative values indicate reduced transport.

Figure 2.31: Timeseries showing the deviation in the mixed layer thickness (m) compared to the control simulation in **a** the Greenland Sea and **b** the Labrador Sea. Solid lines are the PX2 simulation, while dotted lines are the PX5 simulation.

bathymetry in the archipelago area, and as a consequence, the passage through the Arctic Archipelago is generally considered to be closed in these models (e.g., Prange and Gerdes (1999)). Several studies (e.g., Aagaard, K. and Carmack (1989), /inciteste96) suggest that the freshwater flux through this passage is larger than the one associated with the water export through the Fram Strait, so based on this it would be wrong to ignore the Arctic Archipelago

Figure 2.32: An Arctic stabilization of the THC. To compensate for increased southward transport of mass through the Arctic Archipelago, the NAD is intensified and more salt and heat is transported northwards. This intensified drift counteract the influence from the increased river runoff in the Arctic and tend to stabilize the THC.

passage. A closing of the Arctic Archipelago would force the freshwater to escape through Fram Strait, and most likely trigger a different ocean response than the one found in the present model.

In order to explain the relative warm Allerød-period during the last deglaciation, Berger and Jansen (1995) introduced the concept of the “Super-fjord heat pump”. This concept is inspired by the observations from fjords, where every summer meltwater discharged at the head of the fjord initiates an estuarine circulation considerably stronger than the freshwater input. Berger and Jansen (1995) suggested a similar mechanism for the Nordic Seas at least during periods with major melt water inflow, thereby providing a positive feedback on deglaciation by northward flux of warm water. However, based on theoretical considerations of the governing equations for a fjord, this theory was rejected by Stigebrandt (2000). The results presented here offer another way to achieve a positive feedback on warming, as increased freshwater input is seen to increase the heat transport to the Nordic Seas. However, due to the lowered sea level during the ice ages (Fairbanks, 1989) the transport through the Arctic Archipelago was likely reduced compared to the modern climate used in the model. At this stage, the connection to a possible heat pump mechanism therefore remains an open question. Nevertheless, the results points to the Arctic Archipelago as a key passage in determining the Arctic freshwater budget. A better knowledge of the paleodepths and ocean circulation for this passage could therefore be important in explaining climate changes in the past.

The results could also have implications for future climate scenarios. Recent studies show that the ice in the Arctic is melting (e.g., Johannessen *et al.* (1999)) and climate models

points to possibly increased precipitation at high northern latitudes (Latif *et al.*, 2000). This would add large amounts of freshwater to the high northern seas. Whether or not such a freshwater input would lead to a doubling of the modern river runoff in the Arctic Ocean, as in the PX2 simulation, can only be speculation. However, the results show that such an increased freshwater supply to the Arctic, fictitious or real, do not necessarily have a negative feedback on the THC.

2.12 Conclusion

A 3D-isopycnal ocean model coupled to a dynamic and thermodynamic sea ice model has been used to examine the effect of increased freshwater flux from the Arctic on decadal timescales. Two 50 year model simulations are examined: one with a doubling of the modern Arctic river runoff, and a second more extreme case, where the river runoff is five times the modern. In both simulations the modelled ocean response is qualitatively the same (see Figure 2.32): Sea surface salinity (SSS) is reduced, and sea surface temperature (SST) increases in the central Arctic. This leads to melting of ice and an intensified Beaufort Gyre (BG), which in turn increases the volume transport through the Arctic Archipelago. To compensate for this southward transport of mass, more warm and saline Atlantic water is carried northward with the NAD, leading to an increased heat transport to the Nordic Seas. The increased transport of salt to the northern North Atlantic and the Nordic Seas thus counteract the impact of the increased freshwater runoff in the Arctic, and tends to stabilize the THC.

This study has focused on the circulation and the thermodynamics of the North Atlantic, the Nordic Seas and the Arctic Ocean, and their role in the climate system both at present and in the past. A continuation of this study is planned with a global model domain, where the global THC will be studied on long time scales (>100 yrs). This would be useful to validate theories on glacial circulation and to examine the natural variability of the ocean system.

Task 3: Mission capabilities for sea ice thickness retrieval

Contents

3.1 INTRODUCTION	1
3.2 INSTRUMENT SURFACE MODEL GENERATION.....	1
3.2.1 Floe geometry models.....	1
3.2.1.1 Floe Geometry Model (FGM) generation.....	1
3.2.1.2 Floe Geometry Model Set	3
3.3 SURFACE ELEVATION AND REFLECTIVITY MODEL	8
3.4 INSTRUMENT SURFACE MODELS	12
3.5 DATA PROCESSING AND RETRIEVAL RESULTS	13
3.5.1 Simulation Results	14
3.5.1.1 Retrievals with different elevation PDF's and backscatter contrast	14
3.5.1.2 Retrievals for different FGM's.....	16
3.6 STATISTICAL ANALYSIS OF RESULTS	22
3.6.1 Statistical summary.....	22
3.6.2 Retrievals versus Ice Concentration.....	24
3.6.3 Retrievals versus Backscatter Contrast	26
3.6.4 Retrievals versus Ice Elevation.....	28
3.7 SUMMARY	31

Objectives of Task 3: Mission capabilities for sea ice thickness retrieval

The objective of this task is to establish a correlation between altimeter measurements and sea ice thickness. This will be done by generating synthetic observations of sea ice using a number of mission scenarios combined with models describing the statistical and surface properties of sea ice which may affect the quality of the observations.

3.1 INTRODUCTION

This task report describes results from the simulation of a CryoSat type instrument over realistic models of sea ice and water mixtures. Typical two dimensional distributions of ice and water are obtained from imagery, elevations are derived from submarine draft statistics and values for radar backscatter are based on observations with ERS altimeters. Synthetic observations of sea ice have been generated using a number of mission scenarios combined with models describing the statistical and surface properties of sea ice which may affect the quality of the observations. The ultimate aim is to provide a look up table which, for a given instrument, describes the error in ice thickness retrieval for a given ice/snow thickness, ice concentration and surface melt state. There are three key elements to the generation of an instrument surface model. The first is the generation of a realistic model (Floe Geometry Model) for the two dimensional geometry of an ice field which describes the horizontal distribution of ice and water within the instrument field of view. The second is to superimpose realistic vertical topography based on a given mean snow and ice thickness. The third is to attribute backscatter characteristics to the ice and water surfaces within the footprint depending on snow cover and the state of surface melt.

The method used to derived the surface models is described in § 3.2. The results of the simulations are described in § 3.3 and a statistical summary is presented in § 3.4. Finally we summarise the results in § 3.5.

3.2 INSTRUMENT SURFACE MODEL GENERATION

To perform realistic simulations of the satellite system requires the generation of three dimensional Instrument Surface Models (ISM) with appropriate horizontal and vertical representations of typical sea ice surfaces and their backscatter characteristics. This is achieved using high resolution imagery to provide the horizontal representation and submarine upward looking sonar for the vertical representation of ice topography. Backscatter characteristics are based on observations by the ERS-1/2 satellite radar altimeters

3.2.1 Floe geometry models***3.2.1.1 Floe Geometry Model (FGM) generation***

The purpose of the FGM is to generate a high resolution synthetic representation of an ice floe field for various ice concentrations. The model output is a series of binary (0 or 1) grids, at the same resolution as the Instrument Surface Model (ISM), indicating whether ice is present or absent in any particular cell. The chosen model resolution was 20 m×20 m. FGMs were generated using high resolution airborne or satellite imagery. Images were then contrast stretched and thresholded to provide the required FGM. The first set of floe geometries were obtained from high resolution optical images (1 m resolution) from a US reconnaissance satellite during the SHEBA campaign in

the Beaufort Sea. The available images cover different seasons and ice conditions from September 1997 to September 1998, the example presented here being acquired on 28 September 1998. The original optical image is shown in Fig 3.1. This was then scaled and cropped to provide the required areal coverage of 29.4 km \times 59.9 km and then reflected to allow the ground track to pass over a large lead. The resulting Floe geometry Model (FGM) is shown in Fig. 3.2.

Figure 3.1 High resolution optical image from US reconnaissance satellite obtained on 28 September 1998 in the Beaufort Sea, covering approximately 30 by 60 km.

Additional images acquired from airborne photography during the Marginal Ice Zone Experiment (MIZEX) 1984 in Fram Strait were also used. Similar scaling, reflecting and thresholding was required. These images provided FGMs with lower ice concentration than those acquired by satellite in the Canada Basin.

Figure 3.2 FGM1 derived from image in Figure 3.1, after appropriate scaling, reflection and thresholding.

3.2.1.2 Floe Geometry Model Set

A total of nine realistic, and one test, FGM's were used to perform instrument simulations. Fig. 3.3 to Fig. 3.12 show the floe geometry models used in the simulations. The first model (FGM0) is a simple lead test model representing an idealised transition from ice to open water and back to ice. FGM's 1 and 2 are derived from the image shown in Figure 3.1 and represent the complex geometry which can occur in an area of moderate ice concentration. FGM's 3 and 4 are at high ice concentration with open water occurring in only narrow leads, providing a test of the instrument capability to determine water elevation in almost continuous ice cover. FGM's 5 and 6 are similar in morphology to FGM's 1 and 2 but are obtained from MIZEX imagery collected East of Greenland. FGM's 7-10 represent a more broken ice cover consisting of smaller floes which tends to occur in the Marginal Ice Zone. In these cases the instrument may be expected to have difficulty in obtaining estimates of the ice elevation owing to interference by the much higher backscatter water surface.

Figure 3.3 FGM0 : Source SHEBA imagery 28 Sep 98

Figure 3.4 FGM1 : Source SHEBA imagery 28 Sep 98

Figure 3.5 FGM2 : Source SHEBA imagery 28 Sep 98

Figure 3.6 FGM3 : Source SHEBA imagery 29 Sep 97

Figure 3.7 FGM4 Source SHEBA imagery 08 Oct 97

Figure 3.8 FGM5 : Source SHEBA imagery 12 Sep 98

Figure 3.9 FGM6 : Source MIZEX imagery

Figure 3.10 FGM7 : Source MIZEX imagery

Figure 3.11 FGM8 : Source MIZEX imagery

Figure 3.12 FGM9 : Source MIZEX imagery

3.3 SURFACE ELEVATION AND REFLECTIVITY MODEL

The surface elevation and reflectivity characteristics are combined with the FGM to generate corresponding Instrument Surface Models (ISM's). Where the FGM indicates water is present (pixel value = 0), the surface elevation is set to zero, the backscatter is set to the either 30dB or 40dB, and the polar angle is set to 0.005 radians. Where ice is present, values of surface elevation are drawn from a submarine ice draft profile number 093 acquired in the Canada Basin (at 77.7°N, 162.5°W) on 12 October 1996 as part of the SCICEX '96 campaign. The draft profile is 16 km long with a spatial sampling interval of 1 m, and is shown in Figure 3.13. Drafts of less than 30 cm were considered as open water and discarded from the ice draft probability density function (pdf).

Figure 3.13 Submarine ice draft profile 093 acquired as part of the SCICEX '96 campaign.

The initial stage in producing the ISM ice elevation model was to generate an ice surface with a PDF close to that observed in the submarine draft profiles. This was achieved by scanning the FGM horizontally, and for each grid cell where the FGM indicates the presence of ice (pixel value = 1), a surface draft was randomly selected from the submarine draft pdf. This process was repeated using vertical scans, and the two drafts in each cell averaged. A backscatter value of 10dB was assigned to each ice cell, along with a polar angle of 0.08 radians. Using the submarine PDF provides the correct vertical statistics but does not provide a proper horizontal representation of topographic variation, in particular the spatial covariance of ice elevation.

To achieve this we synthesised ridges on the surface of the ice, again based the same ice draft profile. In order to control the amount of ridging which was allowed on the surface, a deformed ice volume, $V_{deformed}$, of 20% was chosen.

Ridges were added to the surface in the manner described below until the following condition was met:

$$\frac{V_{ridged}}{V_{ridged} + V_{level}} \times 100 \geq V_{deformed} \quad (1)$$

V_{level} was computed from the level ice draft surface as:

$$V_{level} = \Delta x \Delta y \sum_i h_i \quad (2)$$

where Δx and Δy are the horizontal and vertical resolutions of the ISM respectively, and h_i are the individual drafts in each cell. Each ridge was initialised by choosing a random length, between 250 m and 2500 m, a random starting point, and a random initial direction. After ensuring that this initial pixel was labelled as ice in the FGM, a ridged draft value was computed. It can be shown theoretically that the most likely distribution of ridge heights is an exponential. An alternative empirical distribution can be used, as described by [Wadhams, 1981]:

$$P_r(h)dh = B \exp(-bh)dh \quad (3)$$

where

$$B = b \exp(bh_0) \quad (4)$$

and

$$b = (\bar{h} - h_0)^{-1} \quad (5)$$

$P_r(h)$ is the probability that the draft lies between h and $h + dh$, \bar{h} is the mean draft, and h_0 is a low value cut-off. From section 093 of the SCICEX '96 cruise, values of 8.97 m and 5.66 m were determined for \bar{h} and h_0 respectively. It can then be shown that h , the ridged draft value in the ISM, can be computed using:

$$h = h_0 - (\bar{h} - h_0) \ln u \quad (6)$$

where u is a number randomly selected from between 0 and 1. This ensures that the ridged draft distribution takes the required exponential form. The location of the next ridged pixel was then

chosen, ensuring that the ridge once fully developed was a linear feature. Calculation of the subsequent draft values was computed in a similar manner until the ridge reached its randomly selected length. This process of adding ridges to the surface continued until the condition given in (1) was met.

The surface was then filtered spatially using a 2-dimensional moving average filter in order to develop a realistic auto-correlation of ice elevation. Either a 2×2 or 3×3 filter was used to achieve this depending on the exact FGM used. The final stage in the development of the ISM was to convert from draft to elevation, using a constant draft to elevation ratio of 7.35 as specified by [Vinje *et al.*, 1998]. The draft pdf of the ISM based on the FGM in Fig. 3.2 can be seen in Fig. 3.14 along with that of the source submarine draft pdf. Two further PDF's were defined, and are shown in Fig. 3.15 and 3.16, approximating 0.5x and 2x the mean ice thickness of the standard PDF model. Fig. 3.17 shows the auto-correlation of the ISM compared with that of the original submarine draft profile.

Figure 3.14 Draft pdf of the ISM (blue) along with that of the source submarine pdf (red).

Figure 3.15 Draft pdf of the ISM (blue) along with that of the source submarine pdf (red).

Figure 3.16 Draft pdf of the ISM (blue) along with that of the source submarine pdf (red).

Figure 3.17 Auto-correlation of the ISM (blue) compared with that of the original submarine draft profile (red).

3.4 INSTRUMENT SURFACE MODELS

The resulting ISMs were generated at a resolution of 20 m, with a (swath) width of 29.4 km and a length of 59.9 km. For the FGM acquired on 28 September 1998, as discussed in this section, the resulting ISM is shown in Figure 3.18, along with the nadir track of the altimeter used in the simulation.

Figure 3.18 ISM developed from FGM1. Superimposed topography is shown as greyscale variability over the image. The white line indicates the position of the altimeter nadir track in the simulation.

3.5 DATA PROCESSING AND RETRIEVAL RESULTS

For each ISM, the simulator generated 113 estimates of surface elevation, along with a mean power echo calculated from between 25 and 49 stacked complex echoes. The stacked waveforms were retracked using a simple 50% threshold retracker as described by [Laxon, 1994] to obtain more accurate estimates of sea surface height. The bin width of the resulting waveforms corresponds to an elevation of 45.3 cm, with a fine waveform shift of 7.1 mm, which essentially defines the vertical resolution of the simulator. Fig. 3.19 shows the resulting retracked elevation profile along with the peak power on a logarithmic scale.

Figure 3.19. Retracked elevation profile (black) for FGM0, the standard elevation model and water backscatter = 40db. Corresponding peak power profile (red) on a logarithmic scale.

In order to distinguish between retrievals from open water and those from ice, a simple thresholding algorithm was applied to the peak power. From experiments with the simulator output from an ISM containing both flat ice and water, waveforms with a peak power greater than -110dB were considered to originate from open water with backscatter set to 40 dB. For open water with backscatter set to 30 dB, a threshold of -120 dB was selected. A waveform was considered to originate from the ice surface if the peak power was less than -130 dB . Waveforms between these threshold values were rejected as complex.

3.5.1 Simulation Results

The following plots show elevation and power retrievals for a selection of model scenarios. Fig. 3.20 and 3.21 show retrievals over the test scenario for the 0.5x and 2x elevation distributions Fig. 3.22 shows the retrieval for the standard elevation model but for $\sigma_{\text{water}}^0 / \sigma_{\text{ice}}^0 = 20\text{dB}$ (water backscatter $\sigma_{\text{water}}^0 = 30\text{dB}$).

3.5.1.1 Retrievals with different elevation PDF's and backscatter contrast

Figure 3.20 FGM0 elevation retrieval, x0.5 elevation distribution, and water backscatter = 40db

Figure 3.21 FGM0 elevation retrieval, x2 elevation distribution, and water backscatter = 40db

Figure 3.22 FGM0 elevation retrieval, standard ($\times 1$) elevation distribution, and water backscatter = 30db

The four lead test models presented show the principle of ice/water discrimination and ice/water elevation retrieval. Retrieved elevations over the water surface, which in the model is flat, provide an indication of the noise error retrieval due to speckle and its effects on the retracking algorithm. Over the ice surface a higher variability is observed since due to the effects of this noise combined with the random distribution of surface elevations. The results do show however, that for this idealised situation the instrument is capable of resolving different ice elevation, and hence thickness, distributions.

Changing the backscatter contrast between ice and open water has little effect on the retrievals for this idealised model. However in section 3.6 it will be seen that decreasing the water/ice contrast does significantly effect the percentage of ice retrievals for some scenarios.

3.5.1.2 Retrievals for different FGM's

Figs. 3.23 to 3.31 show the retrieved elevation and echo power for each of the floe geometry models using the standard ice elevation PDF and backscatter contrast ratio. The figures are presented first followed by a discussion of the results.

Figure 3.23 FGM1 elevation retrieval, standard elevation distribution, $\sigma_{water}^0 / \sigma_{ice}^0 = 30dB$.

Figure 3.24 FGM2 elevation retrieval, standard elevation distribution, $\sigma_{water}^0 / \sigma_{ice}^0 = 30dB$.

Figure 3.25 FGM3 elevation retrieval, standard elevation distribution, $\sigma_{\text{water}}^0 / \sigma_{\text{ice}}^0 = 30\text{dB}$.

Figure 3.26 FGM4 elevation retrieval, standard elevation distribution, $\sigma_{\text{water}}^0 / \sigma_{\text{ice}}^0 = 30\text{dB}$.

Figure 3.27 FGM5 elevation retrieval, standard elevation distribution, $\sigma_{water}^0 / \sigma_{ice}^0 = 30dB$.

Figure 3.28 FGM6 elevation retrieval, standard elevation distribution, $\sigma_{water}^0 / \sigma_{ice}^0 = 30dB$.

Figure 3.29 FGM7 elevation retrieval, standard elevation distribution, $\sigma_{water}^0 / \sigma_{ice}^0 = 30dB$.

Figure 3.30 FGM8 elevation retrieval, standard elevation distribution, $\sigma_{water}^0 / \sigma_{ice}^0 = 30dB$.

Figure 3.31 FGM9 elevation retrieval, standard elevation distribution, $\sigma_{water}^0 / \sigma_{ice}^0 = 30dB$.

Almost all of the simulations exhibit strongly negative elevation retrievals on the transitions between open water and ice. This is a well known phenomena of ‘snagging’ where the radar tracks to bright targets off nadir in preference to the less bright nadir surface. In such cases an accurate elevation cannot be retrieved and the majority of such data is discarded through the use of the upper and lower thresholds on returned Peak Power.

For FGM1 although ice is present in much of the instrument nadir track the floe geometry means that some open water is almost always present close to the track and therefore within the instruments view. In this case, despite a quite high overall ice concentration, no ice elevation retrievals were possible.

FGM2 is based on the same image but the track passes over a much more consolidated area of ice in the central part of the track. The presence of open water off nadir still compromises ice retrievals at the transitions but a short sequence of ice elevations is retrieved in the centre part of the track.

FGM3 presents the instrument with almost continuous ice cover with the exception of two leads lying close to the centre of the track. In this case the number of ice elevation retrievals is high and, despite the very sparse coverage by open water, some estimates of water elevation are still possible.

FGM4 is similar the FGM3 except that one of the narrow leads runs diagonally across the ground track rather than perpendicular. The effect of the diagonal lead is to cause a much longer disruption to the retrievals, illustrating that snagging can occur in both the along track and across track directions. The orientation of leads with respect to the ground track is therefore an important factor in governing the quality of ice elevation retrievals at high ice concentration.

FGM5 is also at fairly high ice concentration but here with a much more broken pack and mixtures of large and small ice floes. Here the ground track, which is necessarily located along the centre of

the image, almost always encounters a mixture of water and ice and in this case no ice elevation and only a very small percentage of water retrievals are obtained.

FGM6 is the first example from the Greenland sea and presents a morphology similar to that for FGM's 1&2. Both water and ice elevations are retrieved again the effect of the diagonal lead can be seen in the slow decrease of power from Y=10 to 15km along the track.

FGM7 shows a much more broken but more homogeneous collection of ice floes. In this case sufficient open water is present within the footprint for water echoes to dominate the majority of the track. A high percentage of water retrievals is therefore obtained although the effect of ice floes lying at nadir can be seen at Y=12 and 22km.

FGM8 is based on the same image as FGM7 but with some ice floes removed to lower the overall ice concentration. This results in a slightly less contaminated water elevation retrieval but overall similar results.

FGM9 is similar to the previous two scenarios but with an ice/water distribution which is somewhat more homogeneous mixture of ice and water. A perhaps surprising result is that no retrievals were obtained over the relatively large floe centred on the ground track at Y= 20km. This may represent a limiting case in terms of the minimum floe size over which ice elevations can be retrieved but this probably requires further investigation.

3.6 STATISTICAL ANALYSIS OF RESULTS

3.6.1 Statistical summary

Table 3.1 shows the retrieved statistics from the full set of model runs. Light blue shading indicates scenarios where both water and ice elevation were retrieved within a single scenario. Dark blue shading indicates that only water elevation were retrieved.

Table 3.1 Retrieved Ice/Water/Freeboard statistics for all model runs.

FGM	SCENARIO				ICE					WATER					FREEBOARD			
	Ice Conc	Elev	sig0	Actual	Retrieved	Data	Ret-Act	SD	Actual	Retrieved	Data	Ret-Act	SD	Actual	Retrieved	Ret-Act	SD	
	%		dB	cm	cm	%	cm	cm	cm	cm	%	cm	cm	cm	cm	cm	cm	
0 lead_test	80.20	1	30	37.11	60.90	55.80	23.79	3.52	0	1.71	32.70	1.71	1.98	37.1	59.19	22.08	4.38	
1 98SEP28	86.30	1	30	37.12					0	16.05	30.10	16.05	3.12					
2 98SEP28_2	83.90	1	30	37.12	68.17	27.40	31.05	5.38	0	30.68	30.10	30.68	4.92	37.1	37.49	0.37	7.48	
3 97SEP29	97.00	1	30	31.33	39.95	66.40	8.62	2.25	0	2.64	3.50	2.64	7.26	31.3	37.31	5.98	7.79	
4 97OCT08	97.70	1	30	31.34	45.22	72.60	13.88	2.14	0	21.70	2.70	21.70	10.20	31.3	23.52	-7.82	10.6	
5 98SEP12	91.20	1	30	34.85	38.60	5.30	3.75	5.84	0	7.68	4.40	7.68	5.64	34.9	30.92	-3.93	8.29	
6 mizex1	86.90	1	30	34.08	68.17	37.20	34.09	3.63	0	15.92	25.70	15.92	4.03	34.1	52.25	18.17	5.68	
7 mizex2	58.50	1	30	37.12					0	21.13	70.80	21.13	1.79					
8 mizex 3	43.50	1	30	37.12					0	19.82	73.50	19.82	2.08					
9 mizex 4	49.20	1	30	37.12					0	19.16	72.60	19.16	2.21					
0 lead_test	80.20	1	40	37.11	60.90	55.80	23.79	3.52	0	1.68	32.70	1.68	2.00	37.1	59.22	22.11	4.39	
1 98SEP28	86.30	1	40	37.12					0	16.21	30.10	16.21	3.07					
2 98SEP28_2	83.90	1	40	37.12	72.72	11.50	35.60	9.35	0	31.78	29.20	31.78	4.86	37.1	40.94	3.82	10.7	
3 97SEP29	97.00	1	40	31.33	39.61	58.40	8.28	2.40	0	3.46	3.50	3.46	6.47	31.3	36.15	4.82	7.1	
4 97OCT08	97.70	1	40	31.34	48.03	52.20	16.69	2.28	0	15.50	1.80	15.50	14.05	31.3	32.53	1.19	14.3	
5 98SEP12	91.20	1	40	34.85					0	6.73	4.40	6.73	5.29					
6 mizex1	86.90	1	40	34.08	65.72	11.50	31.64	8.51	0	15.64	25.70	15.64	3.98	34.1	50.08	16	9.55	
7 mizex2	58.50	1	40	37.12					0	20.94	69.90	20.94	1.86					
8 mizex 3	43.50	1	40	37.11					0	19.91	74.30	19.91	2.07					
9 mizex 4	49.20	1	40	37.12					0	19.42	70.80	19.42	2.22					
0 lead_test	80.20	2	30	67.75	92.81	59.3	25.06	3.44	0	2.5	33.6	2.50	2.33	67.8	90.31	22.56	4.49	
1 98SEP28	86.30	2	30	67.78					0	19.92	28.3	19.92	3.27					
2 98SEP28_2	83.90	2	30	67.78	97.4	27.4	29.62	5.61	0	27.04	32.7	27.04	3.32	67.8	70.36	2.58	6.73	
3 97SEP29	97.00	2	30	62.33	70.01	69.9	7.68	2.23	0	22.41	3.5	22.41	3.59	62.3	47.6	-14.7	4.55	
4 97OCT08	97.70	2	30	62.33	71.88	75.2	9.55	2.05	0	13.01	1.8	13.01	22.83	62.3	58.87	-3.46	23	
5 98SEP12	91.20	2	30	65.77	65.14	6.2	-0.63	4.94	0	7.96	4.4	7.96	4.67	65.8	57.18	-8.59	7.01	
6 mizex1	86.90	2	30	65.06	85.28	36.3	20.22	4.37	0	11.99	25.7	11.99	3.28	65.1	73.29	8.23	5.72	
7 mizex2	58.50	2	30	67.76					0	22.45	69.9	22.45	1.86					
8 mizex 3	43.50	2	30	67.72					0	21.44	73.5	21.44	2.22					
9 mizex 4	49.20	2	30	67.77					0	19.91	72.6	19.91	2.11					
0 lead_test	80.20	2	40	67.75	92.81	59.30	25.06	3.44	0	2.43	33.6	2.43	2.33	67.8	90.38	22.63	4.49	
1 98SEP28	86.30	2	40	67.78					0	19.54	28.3	19.54	3.31	67.8				
2 98SEP28_2	83.90	2	40	67.77	98.04	11.50	30.27	5.39	0	27.31	31.9	27.31	3.30	67.8	70.73	2.96	6.54	
3 97SEP29	97.00	2	40	62.33	71.33	60.20	9.00	2.41	0	23.02	3.5	23.02	3.51	62.3	48.31	-14	4.58	
4 97OCT08	97.70	2	40	62.33	73.60	59.30	11.27	2.08	0	12.97	1.8	12.97	23.32	62.3	60.63	-1.7	23.5	
5 98SEP12	91.20	2	40	65.77					0	8.31	4.4	8.31	4.63	65.8				
6 mizex1	86.90	2	40	65.06	78.15	15.90	13.09	6.29	0	12.02	25.7	12.02	3.28	65.1	66.13	1.07	7.29	
7 mizex2	58.50	2	40	67.76					0	22.35	69.9	22.35	1.87					
8 mizex 3	43.50	2	40	67.72					0	21.7	71.7	21.70	2.22					
9 mizex 4	49.20	2	40	67.77					0	19.42	69.9	19.42	2.17					
0 lead_test	80.20	0.5	30	21.41	48.58	59.3	27.17	2.98	0	1.72	32.7	1.72	1.96	21.4	46.86	25.45	3.95	
1 98SEP28	86.30	0.5	30	21.41					0	19.18	30.1	19.18	3.81	21.4				
2 98SEP28_2	83.90	0.5	30	21.41	49.72	27.4	28.31	4.45	0	31.26	31.9	31.26	4.32	21.4	18.46	-2.95	6.43	
3 97SEP29	97.00	0.5	30	15.02	28.16	61.1	13.14	2.33	0	17.79	5.3	17.79	3.41	15	10.37	-4.65	4.46	
4 97OCT08	97.70	0.5	30	15.02	29.3	66.4	14.28	1.84	0	12.56	1.8	12.56	7.45	15	16.74	1.72	7.86	
5 98SEP12	91.20	0.5	30	19.02	22.27	3.5	3.25	5.00	0	2.24	6.2	2.24	5.04	19	20.03	1.01	7.3	
6 mizex1	86.90	0.5	30	18.22	49.49	35.4	31.27	4.01	0	16.4	23	16.40	4.92	18.2	33.09	14.87	6.57	
7 mizex2	58.50	0.5	30	21.41					0	22.03	64.6	22.03	1.93					
8 mizex 3	43.50	0.5	30	21.41					0	22.34	77	22.34	2.20					
9 mizex 4	49.20	0.5	30	21.42					0	16.97	69	16.97	2.08					
0 lead_test	80.20	0.5	40	21.41	48.58	59.30	27.17	2.98	0	1.67	32.7	1.67	1.98	21.4	46.91	25.5	3.96	
1 98SEP28	86.30	0.5	40	21.41					0	20.18	28.3	20.18	3.75					
2 98SEP28_2	83.90	0.5	40	21.41	49.06	12.40	27.65	6.27	0	31.68	31.9	31.68	4.59	21.4	17.38	-4.03	7.95	
3 97SEP29	97.00	0.5	40	15.02	29.59	51.30	14.57	2.49	0	17.42	5.3	17.42	3.65	15	12.17	-2.85	4.73	
4 97OCT08	97.70	0.5	40	15.02	28.49	54.00	13.47	2.10	0	12.98	1.8	12.98	7.03	15	15.51	0.49	7.53	
5 98SEP12	91.20	0.5	40	19.02					0	1.81	6.2	1.81	4.92					
6 mizex1	86.90	0.5	40	18.22	53.49	13.30	35.27	6.73	0	16.2	23	16.20	4.88	18.2	37.29	19.07	8.48	
7 mizex2	58.50	0.5	40	21.41					0	21.58	65.5	21.58	1.98					
8 mizex 3	43.50	0.5	40	21.41					0	22.35	75.2	22.35	2.22					
9 mizex 4	49.20	0.5	40	21.42					0	16.96	69	16.96	2.09					

3.6.2 Retrievals versus Ice Concentration

Figure 3.32 Retrieved versus actual Ice freeboard

Figure 3.33 Retrieved – Actual Freeboard versus Ice Concentration

Fig. 3.32 shows retrieved versus actual freeboard demonstrating that single scenarios can provide both water and ice elevation retrievals sufficient to derive freeboard estimates close to the input values. Fig. 3.33 shows the difference between retrieved and actual elevation versus ice concentration. Optimum retrievals are obtained for ice concentrations between 90-95%.

Figure 3.34 Percentage water retrievals versus Ice Concentration

Figure 3.35 Water elevation error versus Ice Concentration

The percentage of water retrievals (Fig. 3.34) and corresponding error in the mean water elevation (Fig. 3.35) are strongly dependant on ice concentration. It is noticeable that the percentage of water retrievals can be up to 60% even where the percentage of water cover is less than 30%.

Figure 3.36 Percentage of ice retrievals versus ice concentration

Figure 3.37 Ice Elevation error versus Ice Concentration

The percentage of ice retrievals increases (Fig. 3.36) and the error in ice elevation retrieval decreases (Fig. 3.37) with increasing ice concentration. Between 80-90% ice concentration the percentage of ice retrievals is highly variable indicating a strong covariance, not only with concentration, but also with the morphology of the ice cover, for example the orientation of leads.

3.6.3 Retrievals versus Backscatter Contrast

Figure 3.38 Percentage water retrievals water backscatter. Lines are shown joining points from the same scenarios with different backscatter contrast.

ing points from the

yn joining points

November 2001

Figure 3.41 Ice elevation error versus water backscatter. Lines are shown joining points from the same scenarios with different backscatter contrast.

The effect of changing backscatter contrast on water elevation retrieval error is minimal (Fig. 3.38 and 3.39). For ice elevation estimates however, the percentage of water retrievals decreases (Fig. 3.40) and the error increases (Fig 3.41) significantly for a high water backscatter with some scenarios. This is mainly due to the greater interference of water returns for a higher water/ice backscatter ratio. In some cases where only a few % of ice retrievals are obtained for water backscatter of 30dB this drops to zero as water backscatter is increased to 40dB.

3.6.4 Retrievals versus Ice Elevation

Figure 3.42 Percentage water retrievals versus Ice Elevation.

Figure 3.43 Water elevation error versus Ice Elevation

Figure 3.44 Percentage Ice Retrievals versus Ice Elevation.

Figure 3.45 Ice elevation error versus Ice Elevation.

For most of the scenarios the effect of ice elevation is marginal on water and ice retrieval accuracy. The water elevation is error seen to increase significantly with ice elevation for the two scenarios using FGM4. It appears therefore for scenarios where water occurs only in very narrow leads that

the ice surface either side may be interfering with the water retrieval for high ice elevations. The ice elevation retrieval degrades for the standard elevation model (Elevation = 1) for FGM's 2 and 6. There is no clear reason for this but it presumably involves some sort of non-linear interaction between the ice topography and the horizontal distribution of ice and water.

3.7 SUMMARY

We have presented a number of simulations over realistic ice surfaces using a prototype of the CryoSat instrument simulator. Retrieval results and statistical analysis is presented for a variety of different ice/water mixtures, ice elevation distributions and two levels of ice/water backscatter contrast.

Overall it is shown that, using a simple processing scheme, that the instrument is capable of retrieving useful ice freeboard estimates even within single scenarios runs. Optimum retrievals are obtained for ice concentration between 90% and 95%

The percentage of water retrievals decreases and ice retrievals increases with increasing ice concentration. The corresponding error in the mean water elevation increases and that for the ice elevation decreases with increasing ice concentration. For water elevation there is a clear relationship between ice concentration and retrieval accuracy. For ice elevation it is apparent that lead orientation with respect to the ground track will play a significant role and hence the relationship to ice concentration is less definitive. A much larger model run with ground tracks at many different orientations would provide a clearer statistical picture. Nevertheless the approximate relationship with ice concentration is considered sufficient for the next stage of the study.

Varying the backscatter contrast has a marginal effect on water retrievals but a significant effect on ice retrievals. This shows that a higher water/ice backscatter contrast can degrade ice retrievals in some instances due to the interference of reflections from open water.

Varying the ice elevation has a marginal effect on water elevation retrievals except in the case of FGM4 where open water occurs only very narrow leads. For the ice elevation retrievals larger errors are encountered for FGM's 2 and 6 probably due to some non-linear interaction between the ice topography and ice/water distribution.

Overall the simulations provide the first comprehensive and quantitative view of likely CryoSat performance under a variety of different ice conditions. The simulation techniques and scenarios could also be combined with additional imagery and elevation data to provide further tests. Varying the location of the ground track on the image and extending the simulations could in the future also provide a more comprehensive view of the error statistics. Additionally the scope of this project allowed only the development of first order processing schemes for ice and water elevation retrieval. The data sets generated could provide the basis for the development and optimisation of more sophisticated processing systems required for CryoSat level 1.5 and 2 processing.

Task 4.1: Simulated ice thickness data from radar altimeter

Contents

4.1 INTRODUCTION	1
4.2 CRYOSAT ORBIT	1
4.3 DATA GENERATION PROCEDURES	2
4.3.1 Generation of null data.....	2
4.3.2 Ice Thickness Error Modulation.....	3
4.3.3 Estimation of backscatter contrast	4
4.4 ESTIMATION OF FREEBOARD VARIANCE	5
4.4.1 Probability of Ice/Water Retrievals	6
4.4.2 Ice/Ocean elevation retrieval error variance dependence on model parameters.....	7
4.5 SYNTHETIC CRYOSAT ICE THICKNESS DATA	10
4.5.1 Synthetic CryoSat data output format.....	10
4.5.2 Input/Output thicknesses.....	12
4.5.3 Temperature effects	13
4.5.4 Ice Concentration effects	13
4.5.5 Ice Elevation Error Variance	14
4.5.6 Ocean Elevation Error Variance.....	16
4.6 SUMMARY	17

4.1 INTRODUCTION

This document describes the generation of synthetic data on freeboard and thickness measurements by the CryoSat altimeter system. The raw thickness data are derived from model outputs supplied by NERSC which are then modulated to account for the instrumental and geophysical errors which are likely to be introduced for the real system. The errors are derived from the instrument simulations carried out in Task 3 and broadly depend on surface state parameters including ice concentration, thickness, temperature and backscatter co-efficient. The surface state parameters also govern circumstances where no retrieval is possible according to experience gained from the ERS radar altimeters. The spatial and temporal sampling characteristics are achieved using a synthesised CryoSat orbit for a period of 12 months.

4.2 CRYOSAT ORBIT

Figure 4.1 shows the CryoSat ground tracks generated by the MSSL simulator for a period of 14 days. The complete data set consisted of 12 months of data giving time (in Julian seconds from Jan1) and latitude and longitude along the orbit tracks. Points along the ground track are generated at 1 second intervals, equivalent to the typical sampling for satellite altimeter geophysical products. The first stage of the simulation was to extract the model ice state for each location and time for which a CryoSat observation is predicted. Model parameters are provided at two weekly intervals throughout the year and therefore the model grids corresponding to the particular two week period are extracted. The model parameters of interest are :

- (i) Model ice thickness
- (ii) Model Ice Fraction (Concentration)
- (iii) Model Snow Thickness
- (iv) Model Ice Temperature

These parameters control whether or not a retrieval of water or ice elevation is possible and if so what the retrieval error will be. A fifth parameter required is the backscatter contrast between ocean and atmosphere which is obtained using an empirical relationship between ice backscatter and thickness.

Figure 4.1 Cryosat ground tracks for a 14 days of data gathered during the 09th fortnight of the year.

4.3 DATA GENERATION PROCEDURES

4.3.1 Generation of null data

Under certain conditions retrieval of ice elevations is not possible. Observations from ERS indicate that as the surface temperature approaches the melting point the location of the surface reflection becomes ambiguous. This is likely to occur once the surface snow layer passes through one thaw/melt cycle. Comparisons of ERS ice thickness time-series with surface temperatures suggest this transition occurs when the mean surface temperature exceeds -5°C . The second condition under which ice retrievals will not be possible occurs when ice concentrations fall below a certain threshold. The instrument simulations in Task 3 suggest a lower limit of 70% is a reasonable lower limits. If either of these thresholds is exceeded a 'null' value of ice thickness (-999) is generated.

Fig. 4.2 shows a flowchart of the algorithms used.

h_i = Ice Thickness
 c = Ice Fraction
 h_s = Snow Depth
 T = Surface Temp

$$T_{\max} = -5_j C$$

$$C_{\min} = 0.7$$

Figure 4.2 Flowchart showing 'null' data logic. Null returns are generated where surface temperature(ice concentration) fall above(below) the thresholds required for an ice return. X represents a random number with a uniform distribution between 0 and 1.

Null data are also generated at random according to the inverse of the probability of an ice return occurring at any given location. Hence for $P_{ice} = 0.1$ a null return will be generated for 9 out of ten data points even if they satisfy the concentration and temperature requirements (Task 3). P_{ice} is determined using to the input model ice concentration according to the relationship shown in Fig. 4.6. The changing probability of an ocean return does not influence the generation of 'null' data since an ocean return is never in any case co-incident with an ice return. It is assumed that the ocean used in any ice elevation retrieval to be obtained using an average over a distance of 100 km either side of the ice elevation estimate. Instead the ocean return probability affects the error in ocean.

4.3.2 Ice Thickness Error Modulation

Fig. 4.3 shows the logic employed where the 'null' data test indicates that ice thickness data should be generated. The first step is to compute the model ice thickness to ice freeboard, that is the level above the water surface of the snow/ice interface. Snow thickness h_s is obtained from the model

and fixed values are used for the densities of snow ($\rho_s = 300\text{kgm}^{-3}$), ice ($\rho_i = 915\text{kgm}^{-3}$) and water ($\rho_w = 1025\text{kgm}^{-3}$).

Figure 4.3 Error modulation flowchart.

Once calculated a random error is applied to the model freeboard according to the error variance σ_f^2 to obtain the output ice freeboard. This modulated freeboard f' is then converted back to thickness using the same material densities and the model snow thickness but this time with a random error to account for the likely error in snow thickness estimation (currently 0.2 cm). Calculation of the ice elevation error variance ($\sigma_{E_{ice}}^2$) is described in equation 2 and the mean ocean elevation error variance ($\sigma_{E_{ice}}^2$) in equations 3 and 4.

4.3.3 Estimation of backscatter contrast

The radar backscatter contrast between ocean and ice affects the accuracy of retrievals and therefore must be estimated for any particular location and time of year. A fixed backscatter co-efficient of 40 dB was adopted for the smooth ocean surface/new ice which are frequently encountered in the polar regions and in the absence of other information is considered reasonable. To estimate ice backscatter we derived an empirical relationship using data from the ERS altimeter shown in Fig. 4.4

Figure 4.4 Observed ice backscatter co-efficient (dB) and ice thickness (metres) from ERS observations obtained between Jan-Mar 1997. The large scatter in points is due to noise on individual retrievals.

The LSQ fit to the data shown in Fig. 4.4 yields the following relationship between ice thickness and normal incidence backscatter co-efficient at 13 GHz :

$$\sigma^0 = 15.5 - 0.45h_i$$

Equation 1

This is used to estimate ice backscatter from the input model ice thickness and hence ice-ocean backscatter contrast.

4.4 ESTIMATION OF FREEBOARD VARIANCE

Assuming that an ice thickness estimate is obtained (i.e. not a ‘null’ measurement) then the error variance in ice freeboard must be computed which in turn depends on the error variances of the water and ice elevations. These are derived from the model surface state using the instrument simulation results (Task 3). As an example we now deal with these estimates. The error variance is then used to randomly select a value from a normal distribution. Fig. 4.5 is an example of the distribution of ice thickness which would be expected for a mean of 2 metres and a standard error of 1 metre.

Figure 4.5 Example of output ice thickness for a mean thickness of 2 metres and standard deviation of 1 metre. The figure shows that the output data can include negative ice thickness.

4.4.1 Probability of Ice/Water Retrievals

The probability of ice retrievals is used in the ‘null’ return logic whilst the ocean probability is used in the ocean elevation error variance, hence we deal with these here. The simulations indicate that the probability of an ocean/ice retrieval is dominated by the ice concentration and that other effects (due to backscatter contrast, ice thickness) are negligible.

Figure 4.6 Ice/Ocean retrieval probabilities determined from instrument simulations. For the ice retrievals the regression is $m = 2.26 \pm 0.51$ and $c = -155.9 \pm 47.3$. For the ocean retrievals the regression is $m = -1.37 \pm 0.04$ and $c = 140.9 \pm 3.4$.

Fig. 4.6 shows the percentage retrievals from the model simulations. The linear fits shown are taken to represent a reasonable estimate of the first order dependence on ice concentrations. The regression coefficients shown are used to estimate the probabilities of ice/ocean returns using the input model ice concentrations.

4.4.2 Ice/Ocean elevation retrieval error variance dependence on model parameters

Instrument simulations provided estimates of the RMS differences between input and retrieved elevations of the ocean and ice surface elevation for a given instrument surface model. This enables us to estimate the total error due to the different combinations of ice concentration, thickness and backscatter contrast. One consequence however is that it is not possible to estimate the error contribution of each effect independently.

Figure 4.7 Ice/Ocean elevation variance dependence on ice concentration.

Fortunately one variable, ice concentration dominates the error variance of retrievals. With backscatter contrast and ice thickness playing a much more minor role. The strategy adopted therefore was to first estimate the total error variance according to ice concentration alone and then modulate using the backscatter contrast and thickness. Linear fits were used to estimate the partial derivatives of error variance against the three controlling parameters as shown in Fig. 4.7, Fig. 4.8 and Fig. 4.9. The fits are used to estimate the partial derivatives of error variance as shown in Table 4.1 .

	$\partial\sigma_{E_{ice}}^2$	$\partial\sigma_{E_{ocean}}^2$	Range
\mathcal{C}	-1.24	-0.0215	70-100
$\partial\sigma^0$	0.262	0.0058	30-40
∂h_i	0.0611	0.1439	1.6 – 6.4

Table 4.1 Ice/Ocean partial derivatives of error variances versus Ice concentration (C), backscatter contrast (σ^0) and ice thickness (h_i). The partial derivative when coupled with the ranges, indicate that ice concentration dominates the error in retrievals.

Figure 4.8 Ice/Ocean elevation variance dependence on backscatter contrast.

Figure 4.9 Ice/Ocean elevation variance dependence on ice thickness.

The ice/ocean elevation error variances are calculated as follows :

$$\sigma_{Eice}^2(c, h_i, \sigma^0) = \sigma_{Eice}^2(c, \bar{h}_i, \bar{\sigma}^0) + \frac{\partial \sigma_{Eice}^2}{\partial h_i} (h_i - \bar{h}_i) + \frac{\partial \sigma_{Eice}^2}{\partial \sigma^0} (\sigma^0 - \bar{\sigma}^0)$$

Equation 2

$$\sigma_{Eocean}^2(c, h_i, \sigma^0) = \sigma_{Eocean}^2(c, \bar{h}_i, \bar{\sigma}^0) + \frac{\partial \sigma_{Eocean}^2}{\partial h_i} (h_i - \bar{h}_i)$$

Equation 3

The ice elevation error variance is used directly in the calculation shown in Fig. 4.3. The dependence of ocean elevation error variance on backscatter co-efficient is negligible and is therefore neglected. The error required for the ocean surface is the error in the mean ocean elevation error variance (σ_{Eice}^2), i.e. the error in the ocean elevation averaged over some distance around the ice elevation observation. This error is dependent on the error variance of an individual ocean elevation estimate σ_{Eice}^2 , the averaging distance L and the percentage of ocean retrievals P_{ocean} available in the area. The error is calculated as follows :

$$\sigma_{Eocean}^2 = \frac{\sigma_{Eice}^2}{P_{ocean} \times L}$$

Equation 4

L is currently taken to be 28 seconds corresponding to 100 km either side of the ice elevation observation.

4.5 SYNTHETIC CRYOSAT ICE THICKNESS DATA

We now describe the output data format and present examples of the synthetic ice thickness data generated as a result of the model inputs and error modulation described above. All of the plots presented are examples of synthetic output given model input for the year 1982. Each data file of synthetic CryoSat data is grouped into 24 fortnightly periods corresponding to the 24 fortnightly periods of NESRC model output. The file naming convention following this fortnightly division so the file *cryosat.87.01.dat* contains data for 1-15 Jan 1987 and *cryosat.87.24.dat* contains data for 15-31 Dec Jan 1987.

4.5.1 Synthetic CryoSat data output format

The synthetic data produced are output in plain ASCII text with one record per line corresponding to 1 second of flight time. The data files contain parameters in columns running from left to right. Table 4.2 describes the individual parameters provided in the data file. The Warren snow depth climatology is also provided although it is not used in the current implementation.

Parameter	Description	Units	Mathematical expression
Time	Time in seconds since 00:00 Jan 1	seconds	

Period	Model Fortnight Period	Two weeks	
Lat	Latitude	degrees	
Long	Longitude	degrees	
hmodel(i,j)	NERSC Model Thickness	metres	h_i
cmodel(i,j)	NERSC Model Ice Fraction	0-1	c
snow(i,j)	NERSC Model Snow Thickness	metres	h_s
temp(i,j)	NERSC Model Ice Temperature	°C	T
hice	Synthesised ice thickness	metres	h'_i
pice	Probability of Ice return	0-1	P_{ice}
var_ice_elev_concn	Variance in ice elevation due to ice fraction	Cm^2	$\sigma_{Eice}^2 (c, \bar{h}_i, \bar{\sigma}^0)$
var_ice_elev_thk	Variance in ice elevation due to ice thickness	Cm^2	$\frac{\partial \sigma_{Eice}^2}{\partial h_i} (h_i - \bar{h}_i)$
var_ice_elev_sig0	Variance in ice elevation due to backscatter	Cm^2	$\frac{\partial \sigma_{Eice}^2}{\partial \sigma^0} (\sigma^0 - \bar{\sigma}^0)$
var_ice_elev	Total variance in ice elevation (1s average)	Cm^2	$\sigma_{Eice}^2 (c, h_i, \sigma^0)$
pocean	Probability of ocean return	0-1	P_{ocean}
var_ocean_elev_concn	Variance in ocean elevation due to ice concentration	Cm^2	$\sigma_{Eocean}^2 (c, \bar{h}_i, \bar{\sigma}^0)$
var_ocean_elev_thk	Variance in ocean elevation due to ice thickness	Cm^2	$\frac{\partial \sigma_{Eocean}^2}{\partial h_i} (h_i - \bar{h}_i)$
var_ocean_elev	Total variance in ocean elevation (1s average)	Cm^2	$\sigma_{Eocean}^2 (c, h_i, \sigma^0)$
var_mean_ocean_elev	Variance in mean ocean elevation (pocean*28secs)	Cm^2	$\sigma_{E_{ocean}}^2$
war_snow	Warren climatology snow depth	metres	

Table 4.2 List of output parameters for CryoSat synthetic data.

Although the estimated error variance in ice thickness is not provided it can be simply calculated as follows :

$$\sigma_{h_i}^2 = \frac{1024^2 \left[\sigma_{E_{ocean}}^2 (c, h_i, \sigma^0) + \sigma_{E_{ice}}^2 (c, h_i, \sigma^0) \right] + 300^2 \sigma_{h_s}^2}{(1025 - 915)^2}$$

Equation 5

where the variance in snow depth $\sigma_{h_s}^2 = 0.0004 \text{cm}^2$.

4.5.2 Input/Output thicknesses

Figure 4.10. NERSC model input (left) and synthetic output ice thickness (right) for the 09th fortnight (1-15 May) at 1 second sampling.

Fig. 4.10 shows the input model ice thickness and output synthetic thickness for the two week period corresponding to 1-15 May. The pattern of ice thickness seen in the model data is obscured in the one second synthetic data due to the high frequency noise. Gridding the data in 5 degree blocks however shows that the output data broadly mimics that of the input data.

Figure 4.11. NERSC model input (left) and synthetic output ice thickness (right) for the 09th fortnight (1-15 May) gridded on a 5x5 degree grid.

4.5.3 Temperature effects

During the late spring surface melting acts to change the snow cover lying on sea ice in such a way as to compromise altimetry ice elevation retrievals. Fig. 4.12 shows this effect represented in the synthetic CryoSat data with data loss occurring in various regions on the ice margin even though ice concentrations are sufficient to permit retrieval.. All ice thickness retrievals are ‘null’ for the following (11th) fortnightly period and continue through mid-summer.

Figure 4.12. Model ice temperature (left) and probability of ice return (right) for the 10th fortnight period (16-31 March). The probability drops to zero in the Fram Strait, east of Novaya Zemla and north-eastern Baffin bay due to the ice temperature exceeding the threshold of -5°

4.5.4 Ice Concentration effects

Figure 4.13. Model ice surface temperature (left) and probability of ice retrieval (right) during the 19th fortnightly period (1-15 Oct). Data losses due to low ice concentration can be seen in the North eastern Baffin bay and Barents Sea.

During the first half of October model surface temperatures fall low enough to permit ice retrievals over most ice areas. Ice concentration in the marginal zones is however too low to permit retrievals leading to data loss in some areas. Fig. 4.13 shows how this effect is represented in the synthetic data.

4.5.5 Ice Elevation Error Variance

Fig. 4.14 shows the total ice elevation error variance and the separate components. The four plots (a), (b), (c) and (d) refer to the different components listed from left to right in Equation 2. The largest component is due to ice concentration with the next most important variation due to variability in the backscatter co-efficient which acts to reduce the ice elevation error variance in areas of ice thinner than 3 metres due to the reduced ocean/ice backscatter contrast.

Figure 4.14 (a) the total ice elevation error variance and due to the individual components (b) Ice concentration, (c) Backscatter contrast and (d) Ice Thickness.

Figure 4.15 (a) the total ocean elevation error variance and due to the individual components (b) Ice concentration and (c) Backscatter contrast . The error variance in the mean ocean elevation estimate (Equation 4) is shown in (d).

4.5.6 Ocean Elevation Error Variance

Fig. 4.15 shows the total ocean elevation error variance along with the two components due to ice concentration and backscatter (Equation 3). The spatial variability is considerably less than for the ice case reflecting the reduced dependencies of ocean elevation determination on the surface state variables. Also shown is the error variance of the water elevation averaged over a distance of 100 km on either side of the ice elevation estimate (Equation 4). This is additionally modulated by variability in the probability of ocean return parameter P_{ice} .

4.6 SUMMARY

In this document we have described the method by which synthetic CryoSat geophysical data have been generated. The dependencies of retrieval error on model surface state parameters including ice concentration, ocean/ice backscatter contrast and ice thickness have been determined. We have also generated a dataset with realistic spatial and temporal sampling characteristics though using a CryoSat simulated orbit coupled with criteria for the generation of ‘null’ data where temperature or concentration criteria are not satisfied. Within areas of valid data the percentage of ice retrievals is used to control the percentage of additional null data and the percentage of ocean retrievals is used to modulate the error in average ocean level determination.

The limitations of this study can be summarised as follows and provide possible directions and opportunities for future work :

- The major limitation of this study concerns the realism of the error variances used which were determined using a very limited set of simulation scenarios. Determination of the relationship between retrieval error and surface state is limited by the fact that insufficient statistics were available to fully understand the contributions both independent and coupled of each of the surface state parameters. A much larger set of instrument simulations could be achieved by, for example, using small shifts in the location and orientation of the instrument ground tracks. However the computational cost of this would be extremely high and we consider that the current study has at least provided estimates of the retrieval errors to first order.
- A second limitation is that the instrument simulations were performed using the prototype CryoSat simulator which did not take into account phase information. A more comprehensive simulator is now under development but using this will involve an increase of two orders of magnitude in terms of computational cost. The trade off for the purposes of future studies between realism of the instrument simulator and the improved statistics which may be provided by a larger set of runs has yet to be considered.
- Other more minor points include :
 - The accuracy and temporal resolution of the surface temperature provided by the model may not truly represent transitions at the start and end of the melt season.
 - The accuracy to which the snow depth can in fact be estimated is still unknown and may be a significant factor in the retrievals from the real instrument.
 - The effect of varying water, ice and snow densities has also not been taken into account although these are likely to have a relatively smaller effect.

Task 4.2: Assimilation of simulated ice thickness data into a coupled ice-ocean model

5.1	Introduction	2
5.2	Model description	3
5.3	Assimilation procedure	4
5.3.1	The analysis	4
5.3.2	Error statistics from an ensemble of model states	5
5.3.3	Optimal Interpolation	5
5.3.4	The state vector ψ^f	6
5.3.5	Preparation of observations	6
5.3.6	Error statistics from the model ensemble	7
5.4	Impact of ice assimilation	11
5.4.1	Ice volume	11
5.4.2	Spatial distribution of the ice thickness update	12
5.4.3	Impact of ice thickness assimilation on other variables	12
5.4.4	A measure of the update strength	13
5.5	Summary and Conclusion	17

5.1 Introduction

Sea ice is an important component in the high latitude climate system. The presence of ice has significant effects upon the exchanges of mass, heat and momentum between the ocean and atmosphere. The ice also has a strong impact on the buoyancy forcing of the ocean surface because sea water is distilled in the freezing process; this results in increased (reduced) surface density during freezing (melting), effects which are important for the convective processes at high latitudes.

Additional effects of the sea ice is the complex dynamical processes which makes the associated heat fluxes and buoyancy forcing nonlocal as ice is transported out of the regions where it is formed. These effects have high importance for the thermohaline circulation, with a good example being the export of sea ice out of Fram strait into the Greenland and Iceland seas, and the subsequent export of freshened surface waters into the Labrador sea.

Assimilation of sea-ice thickness in coupled ice-ocean models is an interesting approach to improving model results suffering from model deficiencies (e.g. model resolution and model physics). The sparseness of sea ice thickness estimates has made assimilation with this variable a more difficult task than assimilation of sea ice concentration, where good datasets are now available back to 1978 from passive microwave sensors.

In this study focus will be put on the assimilation of sea ice thickness into a coupled sea ice/ocean model, and the thicknesses used here are the synthetic ice thicknesses generated from WP 4100 (Chapter 4). Several experiments will be performed to assess the impact assimilation of sea ice thickness will have upon the model state by varying observation error covariance. Specifically we vary the observation error variances between a factor 0.25 up to a factor 100 to find if the resulting observation error covariance leads to a strong update of the model or not.

Part 5.2 deals with the coupled ice/ocean model used in this study, while part 5.3 describes the assimilation procedure. The impact of the data assimilation is examined in section 5.4 while section 5.5 give the conclusions of the study.

5.2 Model description

The model used consists of the Hybrid Coordinate Ocean Model (HYCOM) [Bleck] coupled with a dynamic-thermodynamic sea ice model. The dynamic sea-ice model used is based on the Elastic-Viscous-Plastic rheology formulation of Hunke and Dukowicz [1997], while the thermodynamic formulation is similar to that in Drange and Simonsen [1996]. The model is set up on a 140×130 grid that includes the Atlantic and the Arctic ocean, the grid is generated with the conformal mapping package of Bentsen et al. [1999]. A short description of the model components is given below, for a fuller description the reader is directed to the references given.

In WP2000 the Miami Isopycnic Coordinate Model (MICOM) [Bleck and Smith, 1990, Bleck et al., 1992] was used for the model runs (chapter 2.2). The HYCOM model used for the assimilation experiments in this chapter is a continuation of the MICOM model. The main differences between HYCOM and MICOM is that the layer density in HYCOM is allowed to deviate from the reference density of a layer, and each layer can be set to a minimum thickness. This is a major improvement and can be used to achieve a high vertical resolution near the surface boundary layer, where the coordinate layers become z-layers, while reverting to isopycnal layers in the interior. The higher resolution near the surface boundary layer allows the use of sophisticated vertical turbulent mixing parametrizations in place of the bulk mixed layer approach used in MICOM. One such parametrization is the K-Profile Parametrization scheme of Large et al. [1994], which is used for the simulations in this report.

The dynamic part of the sea ice model is based upon the Viscous-Plastic rheology of Hibler [1979], where sea ice is considered as a two-dimensional continuum. The rheology formulation of this model seems to be the best alternative when it comes to modeling large scale sea-ice dynamics [Kreyscher et al., 2000], but the traditional numerical formulation suffers from strong numerical constraints, forcing the use of implicit numerical methods. The EVP formulation solves this problem by introducing an elastic term in the ice stress tensor. This makes it practically possible to use explicit numerical methods, while still (approximately) achieving the same result as the VP rheology. We note that except for the rheology formulation the ice dynamics model is identical to the Hibler ice dynamics model described in chapter 2.2, see also the breakdown of different sea ice rheologies given in chapter 1.2. The thermodynamic part of the model is the same as used in W2000, and has also been briefly described other places in this report (chapter 2.2 and appendix A).

The model equations are discretized on a C-grid constructed with a mapping similar to the conformal mapping of Bentsen et al. [1999], and the surface boundary conditions are provided from ECMWFR reanalysis fields. The map in figure 5.2 shows the bathymetry of the Arctic ocean.

Figure 5.1: The bathymetry of the Arctic, also shown is the section used in the section plots in figures 5.4 and 5.9

5.3 Assimilation procedure

Here we present the procedure followed when assimilating the ice thickness data into our coupled ice-ocean model. First we present some assimilation theory before we present the approach used in the experiments.

5.3.1 The analysis

The object of the data assimilation procedure is to combine the model state with observations to generate improved estimates of the model fields. The actual analysis is based on minimizing a cost function for the model error. This cost function is based on the errors in model prediction and measurements, so we begin with some definitions:

For a discrete model the actual model state $\boldsymbol{\psi}^f$ can be related to the true state $\boldsymbol{\psi}^t$ as

$$\boldsymbol{\psi}^f = \boldsymbol{\psi}^t + \mathbf{p}^f, \quad (5.1)$$

where \mathbf{p}^f is the model error, later we will refer to $\boldsymbol{\psi}$ as the state vector and the state vector $\boldsymbol{\psi}^f$ as the *forecast*. Note that the state vector can be defined to contain other variables than those we wish to assimilate into our model, and we will get back to the specification of $\boldsymbol{\psi}$ later. We may also relate the measurements (\mathbf{d}) to the true values ($\mathbf{H}\boldsymbol{\psi}^t$) as

$$\mathbf{d} = \mathbf{H}\boldsymbol{\psi}^t + \boldsymbol{\epsilon}. \quad (5.2)$$

Here the $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}$ is the measurement error, and the matrix \mathbf{H} is called the measurement matrix. The measurement matrix relates the state vector values to the observed values, and for our application the matrix $\mathbf{H}\boldsymbol{\psi}^t$ give us the ice thickness at the measurement locations. The analysis is based on the following assumptions on the errors in model and measurements:

$$\overline{\mathbf{p}^f} = 0, \quad (5.3)$$

$$\overline{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}} = 0, \quad (5.4)$$

$$\overline{\mathbf{p}^f(\boldsymbol{\epsilon})^T} = 0. \quad (5.5)$$

In other words we assume that the measurement error and the model error are uncorrelated, and that the model and observations are unbiased. In addition we define

$$\overline{\mathbf{p}^f(\mathbf{p}^f)^T} = \mathbf{P}^f, \quad (5.6)$$

$$\overline{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}(\boldsymbol{\epsilon})^T} = \mathbf{w}^{-1}. \quad (5.7)$$

An improved estimate of the state vector which takes into consideration the errors in model and observations can now be found through the *analysis* ($\boldsymbol{\psi}^a$) which minimizes the discrete cost function $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}$:

$$\boldsymbol{\Sigma}[\boldsymbol{\psi}^a] = (\boldsymbol{\psi}^f - \boldsymbol{\psi}^a)^T (\mathbf{P}^f)^{-1} (\boldsymbol{\psi}^f - \boldsymbol{\psi}^a) + (\mathbf{d} - \mathbf{H}\boldsymbol{\psi}^a) \mathbf{w} (\mathbf{d} - \mathbf{H}\boldsymbol{\psi}^a). \quad (5.8)$$

The result of the minimization procedure can be shown to be

$$\boldsymbol{\psi}^a = \boldsymbol{\psi}^f + (\mathbf{H}\mathbf{P}^f)^T (\mathbf{H}\mathbf{P}^f \mathbf{H}^T + \mathbf{w}^{-1})^{-1} (\mathbf{d} - \mathbf{H}\boldsymbol{\psi}^f). \quad (5.9)$$

From this expression we can see that the analysis update is dependent upon the difference between observations and model values (last parenthesis in (5.9)) at the measurement locations. The dependence upon measurement and model error statistics is also evident through the matrices \mathbf{P}^f and \mathbf{w}^{-1} . If the observations have larger (smaller) errors than the model we get a smaller (larger) update $\boldsymbol{\psi}^a - \boldsymbol{\psi}^f$. For instance, if we assume that the measurement error is negligible (in the limit $\mathbf{w}^{-1} \rightarrow 0$), and take the observation of the analysis we get:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{H}\boldsymbol{\psi}^a &= \mathbf{H}\boldsymbol{\psi}^f + \mathbf{H}(\mathbf{H}\mathbf{P}^f)^T (\mathbf{H}\mathbf{P}^f \mathbf{H}^T + \mathbf{w}^{-1})^{-1} (\mathbf{d} - \mathbf{H}\boldsymbol{\psi}^f) \\ &= \mathbf{H}\boldsymbol{\psi}^f + (\mathbf{H}(\mathbf{P}^f)^T \mathbf{H}^T) (\mathbf{H}\mathbf{P}^f \mathbf{H}^T)^{-1} (\mathbf{d} - \mathbf{H}\boldsymbol{\psi}^f) = \mathbf{H}\boldsymbol{\psi}^f + (\mathbf{d} - \mathbf{H}\boldsymbol{\psi}^f) = \mathbf{d}. \end{aligned} \quad (5.10)$$

The last step was achieved because \mathbf{P}^f is symmetric, and in effect, the observed analyzed field get the value of the measurements at the measurement locations. The use of the model covariances for the error matrix \mathbf{P}^f ensures that we get a spatially smooth update. The analysis (5.9) is at the root of many data assimilation schemes, what separates them is how we choose the error matrix \mathbf{P}^f .

5.3.2 Error statistics from an ensemble of model states

Since we do not know the precise form of the matrix \mathbf{P}^f , we must assume something about the form of the error. One way of achieving knowledge of model statistics, and later on model error statistics is through an ensemble of model states. Such an ensemble for a numerical model can be written in matrix form in the following manner

$$\mathbf{A} = [\boldsymbol{\psi}_1, \boldsymbol{\psi}_2, \dots, \boldsymbol{\psi}_{N-1}, \boldsymbol{\psi}_N] \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times N}. \quad (5.11)$$

Here the $\boldsymbol{\psi}_i, i = 1, \dots, N$ are the members of the ensemble. The number of rows in the matrix, n , is the dimension of the ensemble members. We also define the matrix $\overline{\mathbf{A}}$ as

$$\overline{\mathbf{A}} = [\overline{\boldsymbol{\psi}}, \overline{\boldsymbol{\psi}}, \dots, \overline{\boldsymbol{\psi}}, \overline{\boldsymbol{\psi}}] \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times N}. \quad (5.12)$$

In other words, $\overline{\mathbf{A}}$ contains the ensemble mean in each coloumn. We will also need the ensemble perturbations, defined as

$$\mathbf{A}' = \mathbf{A} - \overline{\mathbf{A}} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times N}. \quad (5.13)$$

It follows that the sample error covariance matrix for the model can be written as

$$\mathbf{P}^f = \overline{(\boldsymbol{\psi} - \boldsymbol{\psi}^t)(\boldsymbol{\psi} - \boldsymbol{\psi}^t)}. \quad (5.14)$$

This equation is of little use since we still do not know the true model state, $\boldsymbol{\psi}^t$. However, our best estimate of the true model state is the mean value of the ensemble, so it becomes natural to use the spread of the ensemble around the mean value as an estimate of the error, this gives us the following estimate of the error covariance matrix:

$$\mathbf{P}^f \simeq r_s^2 \mathbf{P}_e = r_s^2 \overline{(\boldsymbol{\psi} - \overline{\boldsymbol{\psi}})(\boldsymbol{\psi} - \overline{\boldsymbol{\psi}})} = r_s^2 \frac{\mathbf{A}'(\mathbf{A}')^T}{N-1} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n} \quad (5.15)$$

where we expressed the ensemble covariance matrix in terms of the ensemble perturbations (5.13). The factor r_s^2 is a modulating factor connected to our choice of ensemble members, described in the next section.

5.3.3 Optimal Interpolation

As we have a way of getting model error statistics from an ensemble of model states, we only have to define how to choose these members. A method such as the Ensemble Kalman Filter [EnKF; Evensen, 1994] integrate several model states, and estimate statistics from these states. This method is very good for estimating the true error statistics as it captures the temporal development of the error covariance matrix. Another method is the Optimal Interpolation (OI) method, which is based on a fixed sample of model states, typically from a model integrated over a year.

The use of a ensemble members from a seasonal cycle to estimate error statistics is a crude approximation of the real error covariance matrix. Since OI has a fixed ensemble of model states, the error covariances are constant in time and it can not be expected to give as good results as EnKF. However, OI demands much less computer resources than the EnKF and was chosen for the several experiments performed in this study.

To generate the model ensemble used, the model was integrated for the year 1986, and samples were taken every third day. This way we sampled a total of 123 model states which were used to generate error statistics from equation (5.15). Also, since the covariances from the seasonal cycle probably overestimate

the real error covariances, we used a modulating factor, r_s to reduce the covariances. The equation (5.9) can now be expressed in terms of the ensemble perturbations as

$$\boldsymbol{\psi}^a = \boldsymbol{\psi}^f = \boldsymbol{\psi}^f + r_s^2 \frac{\mathbf{A}'(\mathbf{A}')^T \mathbf{H}}{N-1} \left(\frac{\mathbf{H}\mathbf{A}'(\mathbf{A}')^T \mathbf{H}^T}{N-1} + \mathbf{w}^{-1} \right)^{-1} (\mathbf{d} - \mathbf{H}\boldsymbol{\psi}^f), \quad (5.16)$$

where we used (5.15) for the model error covariance matrix \mathbf{P}^f . The modulating factor r_s was set to 0.25 for the experiments. As can be seen from equation (5.16), the analysis update can be considered as a linear combination of the ensemble perturbations \mathbf{A}' .

5.3.4 The state vector $\boldsymbol{\psi}^f$

The state vector $\boldsymbol{\psi}$ was chosen to include both ocean variables and ice variables as these are closely related, and was chosen as follows for each model grid cell:

For each layer (3D) of the ocean model:

- Salinity
- Temperature
- Hybrid layer thickness
- Horizontal velocity components (2)

And from the ocean and ice model these 2D variables were included:

- Barotropic velocity components (2)
- Barotropic pressure
- Ice concentration
- Ice thickness

This gives a total of 115 variables for each grid cell. The analysis (5.16) can be calculated for the full model state vector $\boldsymbol{\psi}$, i.e. all grid points. For this application the dimension for the state vector $\boldsymbol{\psi}$ would be approximately

$$\dim \boldsymbol{\psi} = 140 \times 130 \times (22 \times 5 + 5) \approx 2 \times 10^6 \quad (5.17)$$

Which clearly will result in problems if we only have a 123 ensemble members forming a basis for this vector space (the analysis update is a linear combination of the ensemble perturbations). A common practice in data assimilation is therefore to look at the problem locally, i.e. each grid cell value is updated by using observation values in a radius of influence around the grid point. This way the 123 ensemble members will span the vector space (with dimension 115) if it can be combined to form a basis. Thus the local analysis makes the problem much better behaved and was chosen for this study. Note that the inclusion of variables other than ice thickness will also force an update of these variables because they can be negatively or positively correlated with ice thickness through the ensemble covariance matrix (equation (5.16)).

5.3.5 Preparation of observations

Since the synthetic ice thickness data obtained from workpackage 4100 were generated with a specified variance some preparations were done before the experiments were performed. The procedure was as follows:

The observations were interpolated to the model grid for each observation period (14-15 days), and only model grid cells with more than 10 observations were used in the assimilation for that period. The mean value was then calculated from the observations and used as the observation value:

$$\bar{h}_{obs} = \frac{1}{N_{obs}} \sum_{j=1}^{N_{obs}} h_{obs,j}, \quad (5.18)$$

where h_{obs} is observed ice thickness and N_{obs} is the number of observations in the grid cell. The variance of the mean was calculated from the observations and used as observation error variance:

$$\sigma_{\bar{h}_{obs}}^2 = \sum_{j=1}^{N_{obs}} \left(\frac{1}{N_{obs}} \right)^2 \sigma_{h_{obs,j}}^2, \quad (5.19)$$

where $\sigma_{h_{obs}}^2$ is the variance of one observation. The calculated variance was finally multiplied with a factor for the different experiments (Table 5.4.1). The described averaging procedure ensure that the observation dataset is “consistent”, that is we do not specify a variance for the dataset that clearly contradicts the actual distribution of ice thicknesses in the synthetic data set.

The impact the data assimilation will have is as already mentioned highly dependent upon the variances in observed and modeled ice thickness. To get a first impression of the impact the observations will have on the final analysis, we plot in figure 5.2 the error variance of observed and modeled ice thickness. The observed error variances are given by equation (5.19) while the modeled error variances are the diagonal elements of the “double observed” matrix $\mathbf{HP}^f\mathbf{H}^T$. Note that the observation of the model covariance matrix calculates the model error variances in the same locations as the observations. The observation error variance in the figure was taken for experiment E11 (see table 5.4.1) on julian day 8, whereas the model error variances are, as already mentioned, fixed in time. Also shown in figure 5.2 are the error variances of the original observed field before averaging over a model grid cell.

The main thing to observe from figure 5.2 is that the error variances of the observed field are much smaller than the corresponding field from the model, so in the following we expect the observations to have a large impact upon the analyzed field. We also note that the observed variances, when averaged over a model grid cell and the time periods used here, are lowest as we get closer to the north pole (figure 5.2(b)). This is a result of more observations present there for the 14 day observation period.

5.3.6 Error statistics from the model ensemble

The covariance between the model variables is described by equation (5.15). By taking the observation of this expression we get the covariance between ice thickness in the measurement locations, and all model variables described in the state vector $\boldsymbol{\psi}$. These covariances are used when we update the full model state variable (equation (5.15)).

We will now focus on the ensemble covariances between ice thickness and fields in the same point on the horizontal grid. This does not give the full picture as there can be covariances between neighbouring points on the horizontal grid, but the covariances explored here should be indicative of the connections we expect to arise in the assimilation scheme.

Since we expect the correlation to be greatest between ice thickness and ocean model values close to the surface we have plotted the covariance between the upper model layer salinity and temperature against ice thickness in figure 5.3(a) and figure 5.3(a), respectively. Also plotted is the covariance between ice thickness and ice concentration in figure 5.3(c).

As can be seen in figure 5.3 a lot of the strongest covariances are found in the seasonal ice zones of the model (Regions where the ice completely or almost disappears in summer), this can be seen for all covariance fields. Since the OI method uses samples from a seasonal cycle the statistics are not truly representable for the real errors. An example of possibly erroneous statistics can be seen from the covariances between ice concentration and ice thickness. In figure 5.3(c) we see mostly positive correlations between

Figure 5.2: Panel 5.2(a) shows the original observation variances of experiment E11 (see table 5.4.1), while panel 5.2(b) shows the observation error variances after the averaging procedure (5.19). Panel 5.2(c) shows the error variances for the model ensemble. Note that the scales are different in the panels.

Figure 5.3: Ensemble covariances in the same horizontal grid point. Panel 5.3(a) shows the covariance between ice thickness and ocean upper ocean layer salinity, panel 5.3(b) shows the covariances between ice thickness and upper ocean layer temperature and panel 5.3(c) shows covariances between ice thickness and ice concentration.

Figure 5.4: Ensemble covariances in the same horizontal grid point. Panel 5.4(a) shows the covariance between ice thickness and ocean layer salinities, panel 5.4(b) shows the covariances between ice thickness and ocean layer temperatures. The section is shown in figure 5.2. The contoured lines in panel 5.4(a) and 5.4(b) show the model layer interfaces (not necessarily isopycnal).

concentration and thickness, but we could perhaps expect a negative correlation through ice dynamic effects where convergence reduces ice concentration and increases ice thickness. Such behaviour is likely to be present in the ensemble, but the effects of it is reduced by the much stronger signal from the the seasonal cycle present in the ensemble (the covariances from the seasonal cycle are stronger than those from the ice convergence process). Another error in the covariance fields is the strong signal from the seasonal ice zone due to the seasonal cycle present in the ensemble. In reality we would expect smaller correlations between ice thickness and for instance temperature in winter in ice-covered areas far from the ice edge. Such small covariances are seen in the central Arctic, where ice is present all year round.

To further illustrate the properties of the multivariate assimilation scheme, we show in figure 5.4 vertical sections with covariances between ice thickness and salinity, and ice thickness and temperature. The covariances are also here estimated in the same point on the horizontal grid.

As expected the covariances are strongest close to the surface, and we generally see reduced values as we go deeper. Beyond the halocline in the Central Arctic there are very small covariance values. We also see that salinity covariances have some influence in the central Arctic, while temperature covariances generally have largest values in the seasonal ice zones. In the Barents sea we also see that the covariances between temperature and ice thickness have deeper signals than covariances between salinity and ice thickness. Finally it should be mentioned that the values at depths 300 to 500 meters, and grid position ~ 45 in figure 5.4 arise from massless layers and do not contribute to the analysed physical field.

As already mentioned the use of the OI method has some clear limitations, primarily related to the fact that the ensemble is really a fixed-in-time representation of the seasonal cycle. To reduce the covariances to a more realistic level we modulated them with a factor r_s^2 , but this is not enough to correctly portray the error statistics. The main concern is related to the absence of time varying covariance fields. In reality we would expect the error covariances to have relatively small magnitudes under the ice, and increase as we get closer to the ice edge. This is due to the possibly large variations of for instance temperature as we go from ice-free to ice-packed conditions, and model uncertainties in the positioning of this ice edge. The main unwanted effect of using the OI method will probably be to overestimate the magnitude of the update of associated variables when we update ice thickness, an effect that will be most noticeable in winter in the seasonal ice zones. The overestimate will probably be less when it comes to for instance temperature in the Central Arctic. This is because the model temperature is locked to the freezing point of water as long as

ice is present in a grid cell (small variations will occur, however, as freezing temperature is dependent upon salinity). On the other hand a variable such as salinity has a more marked seasonal cycle in the Arctic, which can again lead to overestimates of the magnitude in the assimilation updates.

An improvement of the OI method as used here could be to use different ensembles for different times of year, for instance seasonal or monthly ensembles. For this approach one could perform tighter sampling of model states over one year, or preferably run models over several years to generate a "climatology" of model states. The last approach should be preferred because it will generate a better "spread" of the model states, and so the largest computational resources will be on the generation of the ensembles. Some modification of the data assimilation routines would be required to perform experiments, so this approach was not tested at the time of the experiments.

Figure 5.5: Total ice volume for the Arctic from the different model experiments. Left plot shows ice volume for 1987 (low NAO year) and right plot shows for 1990 (high NAO year).

5.4 Impact of ice assimilation

To estimate the impact of varying degrees of uncertainty in the ice thickness observations, a number of assimilation experiments were run.

The experiments were divided between two years, 1987 and 1990. The integrations started with identical initial conditions one year prior to the year of the experiments. The model was then integrated for the year leading up to the year of the experiments, where no assimilation was applied. Additionally we mention that the model run for the year 1986 was used to generate the ensemble of model states used in equation (5.16) for all experiments. The resulting ensemble covariance matrix \mathbf{P}^f was also modified with a modulating factor r_s^2 to account for the fact that the seasonal variations are larger than those described by a more realistic error covariance matrix. In the experiments we set $r_s = 0.25$.

As we reached the years of the experiment, we did several model runs with data assimilation, and with a varying degree of uncertainty in the measurements. For the year 1990 we performed three experiments with different observation error variances, for the year 1987, we did four experiments. An overview of the experiments and the specified error variances are given in table 5.4.1. For all experiments, the data assimilation was performed each 15th day when measurements were available (no measurements are available in the melt season).

5.4.1 Ice volume

A first estimate of the effect of the data assimilation can be seen in the total volume of sea ice, which is shown in figure 5.5. From these figures we can see how the assimilation in the experiments with the lowest observation errors tend to have a stronger “pull” on the model state (experiments E13 and E23), than do the other experiments (most noticeably experiment E14). We also see that even for the experiment with highest error variances (E14) there is a cumulative effect of the assimilation, with the ice volume curve being different from the experiment without assimilation.

In all but experiment E14 we also see that the analysis update of the model state is strong enough to almost completely pull the model towards the observations in a only a few analysis steps. This can be seen in the way the ice volume seems to converge towards the same value in the experiments. This convergence is easier to see in figure 5.11. From the ice volume we also see that even though most of the experiments

Table 5.1: Overview of experiments performed. All experiments for a given year started with identical initial field. The variance $\sigma_{h_{obs}}^2$ is the variance of the mean with sample variances as specified from WP 4100 (see equation (5.19)).

Experiment ID	Year	Observation variance	Additional comments
E10	1987	-	No assimilation
E11	1987	$\sigma_{h_{obs}}^2 = 1 \times \sigma_{h_{obs}}^2$	
E12	1987	$\sigma_{h_{obs}}^2 = 4 \times \sigma_{h_{obs}}^2$	
E13	1987	$\sigma_{h_{obs}}^2 = .25 \times \sigma_{h_{obs}}^2$	
E14	1987	$\sigma_{h_{obs}}^2 = 100 \times \sigma_{h_{obs}}^2$	
E20	1990	-	No assimilation
E21	1990	$\sigma_{h_{obs}}^2 = 1 \times \sigma_{h_{obs}}^2$	
E22	1990	$\sigma_{h_{obs}}^2 = 4 \times \sigma_{h_{obs}}^2$	
E23	1990	$\sigma_{h_{obs}}^2 = .25 \times \sigma_{h_{obs}}^2$	

quickly converge towards the observations at the beginning of the year, there is a continuing systematic correction of the model at the end of the year, when the ice thickness in the model does not increase as fast as in the observations.

We also see that the impact of the assimilation upon total ice volume is significant for both model years, which can easily be seen in the difference between the base run (E10 and E20) and the assimilation experiments.

5.4.2 Spatial distribution of the ice thickness update

A spatial distribution of the update in ice thickness can be seen in figure 5.6(b), where the update is shown for day 8 in 1987 for experiment E11 along with the forecast field in figure 5.6(a). From figure 5.6(b) we see that the update is positive in most regions of the Arctic. Some regions also have a reduction in ice thickness, with the strongest signal in the Laptev sea. The resulting analysed ice thickness field in figure 5.6(c) has a spatial distribution that is much closer to the observed field (not shown).

The values for the observation error variance $\sigma_{h_{obs}}^2$ and the model error variance $\sigma_{h_{ens}}^2$ (the diagonal elements of $\mathbf{HP}^f\mathbf{H}^T$) are important factors for the analysis. $\sqrt{\sigma_{h_{obs}}^2}$ and $\sqrt{\sigma_{h_{ens}}^2}$ were shown in figure 5.2(b) and in figure 5.2(c) respectively. Because the error variances are much smaller in the observation than in the model the update strongly pulls the model ice thickness towards the observations for all regions of the Arctic.

5.4.3 Impact of ice thickness assimilation on other variables

Since the state variable ψ contains other variables than ice thickness, we will get that an update in ice thickness will also lead to an update in these variables. The connection between an ice thickness update and for example mixed layer temperature update will be given through the correlations in the matrix \mathbf{P}^f (also see the covariances in figures 5.3 and 5.4).

The update in ice concentration, upper ocean temperature and salinity for experiment E11 on day 8 (same day and experiment as in figure 5.6) is shown in figure 5.7. For the update in temperature (figure 5.7(b)) the spatial map looks pretty much as we would expect from the covariances shown in figure 5.3(c), with the largest updates in the seasonal ice zones. Also the salinity update looks as expected, with a larger influence of the salinity in the central Arctic than we saw with temperature. For the ice concentration update we see however, a different field than we would expect, with strong reduction in the central Arctic. It is clear that

Figure 5.6: Spatial update of the model for day 8 in experiment E11. Panel 5.6(a) shows original ice thickness forecast $\mathbf{H}\psi^f$, panel 5.6(b) shows locations and strengths of the ice thickness update, panel 5.6(c) shows the analyzed thickness field.

the reduction of ice concentration in the analysis is unrealistic for this time of year, and is a result of poor model error statistics from the OI ensemble.

In figure 5.8 we have plotted the updates of sea surface height, the sea surface density and sea surface velocity. We mention here that sea surface density and sea surface height are diagnostic variables in the model, and are not directly connected to the ice thickness assimilation through the matrix \mathbf{P}^f . We see that the sea surface density is mainly related to the salinity field, as density variations are mostly related to salinity in the temperature range found in the Arctic. For the updates of sea surface height we see a similarity with the density update in most regions (salinity increase corresponds to ssh decrease), which is appropriate if we consider the conservation of mass in the vertical. This picture is not valid for the entire Arctic however, most noticeable in the region of strong update North of Greenland.

To examine the update in the vertical, we have in figure 5.9 shown the update for the vertical section in figure 5.2. The updates correspond well with the covariances examined in figure 5.4 and a positive ice thickness update. Also the strength of the update is in general seen to decrease as we go deeper in the water column for this section. For temperature we notice that there are small updates of the water column in the 100 to 300 meter depth range in the Central Arctic.

5.4.4 A measure of the update strength

To obtain a simple measure on the quality of the update we examined the Root Mean Square (RMS) of the distance between measurements and observations before and after the analysis step.

$$\text{RMS}(\mathbf{d} - \mathbf{H}\psi^f) = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^m (d_i - (\mathbf{H}\psi^f)_i)^2}{m}} \quad (5.20)$$

$$\text{RMS}(\mathbf{d} - \mathbf{H}\psi^a) = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^m (d_i - (\mathbf{H}\psi^a)_i)^2}{m}}, \quad (5.21)$$

Figure 5.7: The update of ice concentration, upper oceanic layer temperature and salinity for day 008 in experiment E11. Corresponding updates for ice thickness (the assimilation variable) is shown in figure 5.6.

Figure 5.8: The update of ice concentration, upper oceanic layer temperature and salinity for day 008 in experiment E11. Corresponding updates for ice thickness (the assimilation variable) is shown in figure 5.6.

Figure 5.9: Section plot of the update of layer temperature and salinities for day 008 in experiment E11. The section is shown in figure 5.2.

where m is the number of measurement locations. A simple estimate of how much the analysis is pulled towards the measurements can now be obtained through the following property of an analysis step:

$$U(\mathbf{d}, \psi^a, \psi^f) = \frac{\text{RMS}(\mathbf{d} - \mathbf{H}\psi^a)}{\text{RMS}(\mathbf{d} - \mathbf{H}\psi^f)} \quad (5.22)$$

So that the function U is the RMS of the distance between observations and analysis, divided by the rms of the distance between observations and forecast. For an analysis update that give us the observations (i.e. $\mathbf{d} - \mathbf{H}\psi^a = 0$) U would have a value of 0, while for no update U would have a value of 1. This measure of the strength of the update removes some of the dependency upon the distance between the observations and the model values, and depends mostly upon the variances in the model and the measurements. When analyzing the value of U we should keep in mind that the difference between observations and model state will be taken at different locations for a given time period, depending on where observations are available.

A plot of the function U is shown in figure 5.10. As is to be expected U has the lowest values for the best update, and this is for the experiments where the observation error variance is lowest. Note however that a saturation effect is quickly evident in the experiments with the lowest observation error variances. As the distance between observations and model is reduced covariances between neighbouring points in the horizontal play a larger role, and can in effect increase the update parameter U . This effect is seen in its most extreme for the update after the melt season, with U -values above 1, meaning that the RMS-distance between observations and measurements is actually increased. This effect is not as drastic as it seems from figure 5.10, as can be seen from the RMS distance in figure 5.11.

In figure 5.10 we also see the effect of the seasonal variation of the observation error, as the quality of the update is reduced when we get closer to the melt period. This effect is mostly noticeable for experiment E14, where the saturation effect is not present to the same extent as in the other experiments. In experiment E14 we also see how the update improves a while after the melt period.

Let us now try to convert U into a time-related value. If we assume that the model has no systematic error between each update (a bold assumption), and the time between updates is Δt we have:

$$\text{RMS}(\mathbf{d} - \mathbf{H}\psi^f)_{t_0+\Delta t} = \text{RMS}(\mathbf{d} - \mathbf{H}\psi^a)_{t_0}. \quad (5.23)$$

This easily allows us to convert the value of U into the number of updates it takes to obtain an e -folding of the initial distance between observations and model state. For p updates we have:

$$\text{RMS}(\mathbf{d} - \mathbf{H}\psi^a)_{t_0+p\Delta t} = U^p \text{RMS}(\mathbf{d} - \mathbf{H}\psi^a)_{t_0} \quad (5.24)$$

Figure 5.10: Values for U (equation (5.22)) for the different experiments

Figure 5.11: RMS of distance between observations and model values ($d - H\psi^f$) for the different experiments

This yields the following relation for the e -folding time

$$T_e = \Delta t \left(\frac{-1}{\log(U)} \right) \tag{5.25}$$

For a value of $U = 0.90$ (typical value from experiment E14) we need at least 20 analysis steps to obtain a e -folding of the distance between observations and model, this results in a minimum e -folding time of 300 days. For experiment E11 and E21 we use a typical value of $U = 0.6$, which gives approximately 2 update steps to obtain an e -folding of the distance between observations and model. To put this into measurement errors, the E11 and E21 experiment has a typical measurement sample error of $\sim 0.5m$ (see figure 5.2(a)), while the E14 experiment would have a typical measurement sample error of $\sim 5m$.

The distance between observations and model result are plotted in figure 5.11(a) and 5.11(b) for the two experiment years. The RMS-distance between observation and model ice thickness has been calculated before and after the analysis steps, explaining the sawtooth-loke plot. From the figures we see that there is a large seasonal variation in $\mathbf{d} - \mathbf{H}\boldsymbol{\psi}^f$, which is due to changes in the number of measurement points used in $\mathbf{d} - \mathbf{H}\boldsymbol{\psi}^f$ and due to different spatial distribution in $\mathbf{d} - \mathbf{H}\boldsymbol{\psi}^f$ over the course of the season.

5.5 Summary and Conclusion

The experiments performed in this study have shown us that the synthetic observations from WP 4100 have an error variance which is low enough to have a strong impact on the analysed ice thickness fields in the analysis scheme. By studying the update parameter $U(\mathbf{d}, \boldsymbol{\psi}^f, \boldsymbol{\psi}^a)$ given by equation (5.22) we demonstrated that only a few assimilation steps were required to obtain e-folding of the RMS-distance between the thickness field of the model and the observations in the case with the original observation error variances. The same conclusion more or less held if we multiplied the original observation error variances by a factor 0.25 and 4. If we increased this factor to 100 we showed that it would take at least 20 analysis updates to obtain an e-folding of the RMS-distance. For the assimilation scheme presented here and the observation averaging period used (14-15 days) this means that a measurement error of $\sim 1m$ is likely to have a significant impact upon the analysed fields.

If we average the measurements over a 10^5 km^2 area and require 3000 km of track to obtain an estimate of the average ice thickness we will need approximately 400 measurements over this area. Then a sample measurement error of 0.5m translates into an error for the average of 2.5 cm. This is of the same order as the requirement for the Cryosat mission requirements, and indicate that data from the Cryosat sensors will have a high impact on the model in the assimilation step.

We also showed that the assimilation procedure had an effect on variables other than the ice thickness. For instance we saw a reduction in ocean surface temperature when ice was introduced close to the marginal ice zone, and the salinity fields were also updated in a reasonable manner. The ice concentration however, showed a decrease when we increased the ice thickness in the Central Arctic, an effect of poor error statistics. We note that the error statistics used in the analysis step are very important for the update. The OI method tries to estimate these error statistics by using an ensemble which is fixed in time, and with samples from a seasonal cycle of the model. The real error statistics for the Arctic regions should be expected to show strong spatial and temporal variations related among other things to the positioning of the ice edge. Such behaviour can not be correctly portrayed by the OI method used here.

Finally we mention that to our knowledge this type of multivariate data assimilation scheme has not been utilized with ice variables before. The results are encouraging, and the shortcomings of the scheme is mainly related to the choice of the ensemble members. Future work should try to utilize a more realistic ensemble of members to better be able to describe the error covariance matrix, this will give more realistic updates for model fields associated to ice thickness through covariances in this matrix.

Chapter 6. Summary and recommendations (Task 5)

Contents

6.1 STUDY OBJECTIVES	1
6.2 LINKS BETWEEN TASKS	1
6.3 REVIEW OF PROJECT TASK RESULTS	3
<i>Task 1. The status of sea ice models and data assimilation</i>	3
<i>Task 2. Basic model scenario including validation</i>	3
<i>Task 3. Mission capabilities for sea ice thickness retrieval</i>	5
<i>Task 4. Simulation scenarios</i>	6
Sub-task 4.1 Simulated ice thickness measurements from radar altimeter	6
Sub-task 4.2 Assimilation of simulated ice thickness data into a coupled ice-ocean model	6
6.4 WHAT HAS BEEN LEARNT...?	8
<i>On ice-ocean model simulations</i>	8
<i>On CryoSat instrument simulations</i>	8
<i>On assimilation of CryoSat-like data into ice-ocean model</i>	9
<i>On spatial and temporal requirements for CryoSat measurements</i>	9
6.5 LIMITATIONS OF CURRENT STUDY AND RECOMMENDATIONS FOR THE FUTURE	9
<i>Generation of synthetic CRYOSAT data</i>	9
<i>The assimilation exercise</i>	10
<i>Recommendations</i>	10

6.1 STUDY OBJECTIVES

The overall objective is to *quantify the importance of a better knowledge of sea ice budget on relevant climate processes such as freshwater budget, thermohaline circulation and deep water formation.*

The retrieval of the key parameter sea ice thickness from remote sensing techniques poses a major challenge compared with the observation of sea ice extent and ice concentration. The specific objectives of this study is

- To examine the sensitivity of state of the art dynamic-thermodynamic sea ice models to changes in sea ice thickness.
- To derive observation requirements (e.g. requirements for accuracy, repeatability and temporal-spatial coverage) scenarios for the estimation of sea ice thickness in the Arctic.
- Perform a sensitivity study of the importance of sea ice volume fluxes for freshwater budgets, thermohaline circulation and deep water formation in high latitude regions. Based on the results the observation requirements for ice thickness the analysis shall be updated and refined.

6.2 LINKS BETWEEN TASKS

6.3 REVIEW OF PROJECT TASK RESULTS

Task 1. The status of sea ice models and data assimilation

Objective

The objective of Task 1 was to provide an overview of the currently used dynamic-thermodynamic sea ice models, describing ice rheologies and to what extent satellite data are used in the models. The performance of the models was assessed as far as it was possible.

In Task 1 the fundamental physics and model formulations for dynamic-thermodynamic sea ice models are reviewed. The model equations are described including the most common rheologies. The coupled ice-ocean model at the Nansen Center, consisting of the MICOM ocean model and Hibler's viscous-plastic ice model, is described and used for the basic model scenario in Task 2. Satellite observation techniques and their use in sea ice models are discussed, emphasising the passive microwave data which is the only data set covering all sea ice areas globally and is obtained regularly for more than 20 years. The most important data sets are ice area and concentration from satellite passive microwave data and ice velocity data from drifting buoys and satellite data. Retrieval of ice thickness data from satellite altimeter is discussed based on recent analysis of ERS data carried out at UCL. The results of the Sea Ice Model Intercomparison Project (SIMIP) are reviewed where the performance of different ice rheologies are assessed. Finally, some aspects of satellite data assimilation in ice models are mentioned, reflecting that only limited work has been done in these fields.

Task 2. Basic model scenario including validation

The objective of this task is to simulate fluctuations in Arctic sea ice concentration, extent, thickness and mass, using an existing dynamic-thermodynamic model. The simulations should include seasonal, annual and interannual variations. The results of the simulations as well as the forcing fields shall be assessed by comparison with observations.

Task 2 describes the 40 years of simulations that have been done with the NERSC coupled ice-ocean model using NCEP forcing data. The most extensive model validation has been done for ice extent and area, where merged SMMR and SSMI data have been used to assess the basic model scenario. Trends and anomalies for the whole Arctic ice cover have been analysed for the model simulations and compared with data which suggest a decrease of about 3 % per decade of the ice area. The model simulations underestimate the sea ice area systematically, giving estimates of 1 – 2 mill km² below the observed values which range from 10 mill km² in winter to about 5 mill km² in summer. As a consequence, the model estimates of multiyear ice area is too low by about 2 mill km², which is significant compared to the satellite-derived estimates of about 4 km².

Some pronounced differences in ice extent anomalies between model simulations and data can be explained by too high air temperature in the NCEP forcing fields, especially in the winter of 1980-81. Errors in the NCEP winter temperatures on the period 1979 to 1982 were documented by comparison

with ECMWF fields. Apart from these discrepancies, the simulated and satellite-derived sea ice extent anomalies agree well for the period 1979 to 1999 when satellite data were available. For the period 1984 to 1998, which excludes the erroneous NCEP data, both data and model simulations show the same trend of about $-12 \times 10^3 \text{ km}^2$ per year decrease in total ice area. Also the multiyear fraction of the ice area show consistent trends: $-30 \times 10^3 \text{ km}^2$ for the model simulations and $-32 \times 10^3 \text{ km}^2$ for the satellite data. The spatial and temporal distribution of the model error in ice concentration has been studied using Principal Component (PC) analysis. This analysis shows that the strongest underestimate from the model occurs in the marginal ice zone both in summer and winter.

For validation of model ice thickness, data sets from Upward-Looking Sonars on submarines were compiled and compared with monthly mean thickness estimates from the model simulations, extracted along the same sections as the submarine profiles. The tracks covered most of the Arctic Ocean, the longest being more than 8000 km long, crossing the Eurasian and Canadian basin several times. Most of the profile comparisons showed reasonable correlation between model and sonar data, with an overall correlation of 0.80. Trends in ice thickness changes are more difficult to validate because observed thickness data from submarine sonars only exist in specific locations at selected months. Continuous thickness data from the Russian Arctic from 1970 – 1991, based on elastic-gravity wave measurements (Nagurny et al., 1994), suggest a decreasing trend of -0.5 cm per year, while Rothrock et al (1999) submarine data analysis from the 1950s to the 1990s suggest a much stronger decrease of -4 cm per year. The model simulations over the period 1984 to 1998, give a decrease of -2 cm per year for the multiyear fraction of the ice cover.

In addition to the inherent properties of the model (relatively coarse resolution, neglect of the effect of thermal inertia and properties of the viscous-plastic rheology), the detected errors in the model simulations can be explained by the errors in the NCEP forcing fields such as too high surface temperatures and too high downward shortwave radiation (Maslanik et al., 2000). The conclusion of the ice –ocean model simulations is that the coupled model gives a good description of the sea ice variations and trends in the Arctic, although some tuning of the performance might be necessary.

In addition to the baseline simulation experiment used to validate the sea ice model performance, parallel experiments have been conducted with perturbed freshwater discharge into the Arctic Ocean. Increased freshwater discharge as a result of reduced sea ice cover will have effects on temperature, salinity, ice drift and melting in the Arctic Ocean. Two 50 year simulation experiments have been performed and examined: one with a doubling of the modern Arctic river runoff, and a second more extreme case with a river runoff five times the modern. In both simulations the ocean response is qualitatively the same: sea surface salinity is reduced, sea surface temperature is increased in the central Arctic, leading to melting of ice and intensified Beaufort Gyre, which in turn increases the volume transport through the Arctic Archipelago. To compensate for this southward transport of mass, more warm and saline Atlantic Water is carried northward, leading to an increased heat transport to the Nordic Seas. The increased transport of salt to the North Atlantic and the Nordic Seas thus counteract the impact of the increased freshwater runoff in the Arctic, and tends to stabilize the thermohaline circulation.

Task 3. Mission capabilities for sea ice thickness retrieval

The objective of this task is to establish a correlation between altimeter measurements and sea ice thickness. This will be done by generating synthetic observations of sea ice using a number of mission scenarios combined with models describing the statistical and surface properties of sea ice that may affect the quality of the observations.

In this task a CryoSat type instrument performance over realistic models of sea ice and water mixtures have been simulated. Typical two-dimensional distributions of ice and water are obtained from imagery, elevations are derived from submarine draft statistics and values for radar backscatter are based on observations with ERS altimeters. Synthetic observations of sea ice have been generated using a number of mission scenarios combined with models describing the statistical and surface properties of sea ice that may affect the quality of the observations. The ultimate aim is to provide a look up table which, for a given instrument, describes the error in ice thickness retrieval for a given ice/snow thickness, ice concentration and surface melt state. There are three key elements to the generation of an instrument surface model. The first is the generation of a realistic model, FGM (Floe Geometry Model), for the two dimensional geometry of an ice field which describes the horizontal distribution of ice and water within the instrument field of view. The second is to superimpose realistic vertical topography based on a given mean snow and ice thickness. The third is to attribute backscatter characteristics to the ice and water surfaces within the footprint depending on snow cover and the state of surface melt.

The simulations have shown that, using a simple processing scheme, the instrument is capable of retrieving useful ice freeboard estimates even within single scenarios runs. Optimum retrievals are obtained for ice concentration between 90% and 95%

The percentage of water retrievals decreases and ice retrievals increases with increasing ice concentration. The corresponding error in the mean water elevation increases and that for the ice elevation decreases with increasing ice concentration. For water elevation there is a clear relationship between ice concentration and retrieval accuracy. For ice elevation it is apparent that lead orientation with respect to the ground track will play a significant role and hence the relationship to ice concentration is less definitive. A much larger model run with ground tracks at many different orientations would provide a clearer statistical picture. Nevertheless the approximate relationship with ice concentration is considered sufficient for the next stage of the study.

Varying the backscatter contrast has a marginal effect on water retrievals but a significant effect on ice retrievals. This shows that a higher water/ice backscatter contrast can degrade ice retrievals in some instances due to the interference of reflections from open water.

Varying the ice elevation has a marginal effect on water elevation retrievals except in the case of FGM4 (Floe Geometry Model) where open water occurs in only very narrow leads. For the ice elevation retrievals larger errors are encountered for FGM's 2 and 6 probably due to some non-linear interaction between the ice topography and ice/water distribution.

Overall the simulations provide the first comprehensive and quantitative view of likely CryoSat performance under a variety of different ice conditions. The simulation techniques and scenarios could also be combined with additional imagery and elevation data to provide further tests. Varying the location of the ground track on the image and extending the simulations could in the future also provide a more comprehensive view of the error statistics. Additionally the scope of this project allowed only the development of first order processing schemes for ice and water elevation retrieval. The data sets generated could provide the basis for the development and optimisation of more sophisticated processing systems required for CryoSat level 1.5 and 2 processing.

Task 4. Simulation scenarios

Objective: To simulate ice thickness information as input for sea ice models for study of dynamics and thermodynamics and subsequent evaluation of impact on freshwater budgets, thermohaline circulation and deep water formation.

The work is divided in two subtasks:

- 1) *Simulated ice thickness measurements from radar altimeter*
- 2) *Assimilation of simulated ice thickness data into a coupled ice-ocean model*

Sub-task 4.1 Simulated ice thickness measurements from radar altimeter

A set of synthetic data on freeboard and thickness measurements generated by the CryoSat altimeter system has been produced. The raw thickness data were derived from ice-ocean model outputs supplied by NERSC in Task 2, which also provided ice concentration, snow thickness and ice temperature. These data were then modulated to account for the instrumental and geophysical errors that are likely to be introduced for the real system. The errors are derived from the instrument simulations carried out in Task 3 and broadly depend on surface state parameters including ice concentration, thickness, temperature and backscatter co-efficient. The surface state parameters also govern circumstances where no retrieval is possible according to experience gained from the ERS radar altimeters. The spatial and temporal sampling characteristics are achieved using a synthesised Cryosat orbit for a period of 12 months. The dependencies of retrieval error on model surface state parameters including ice concentration, ocean/ice backscatter contrast and ice thickness have been determined.

We have also generated a dataset with realistic spatial and temporal sampling characteristics though using a CryoSat simulated orbit coupled with criteria for the generation of ‘null’ data where temperature or concentration criteria are not satisfied. Within areas of valid data the percentage of ice retrievals is used to control the percentage of additional null data and the percentage of ocean retrievals is used to modulate the error in average ocean level determination.

Simulated monthly mean ice thickness data sets have been generated for two years, based on simulation results in task 2: 1987 which had relatively much ice and 1990 with relatively little ice. Each data set was produced with three different variances to simulate various degrees of accuracy in satellite-derived ice thickness data.

Sub-task 4.2 Assimilation of simulated ice thickness data into a coupled ice-ocean model

In this study simulated sea ice thickness data were assimilated into a coupled sea ice/ocean model to investigate the sensitivity of using CRYOSAT-like data in sea ice modelling. Several experiments were performed to assess the impact of this assimilation on the model state by varying the observation error variance. The model experiments were performed for two years, 1987 (a year with relatively much ice – low NAO year) and 1990 (a year with relatively little ice – high NAO year). The observational data used was the synthetic Cryosat dataset from WP4100. Specifically we varied the observation error variance by multiplying it with factors in the range from 0.25 to 100 to examine the effect it had on the assimilation step. The assimilation scheme chosen for the experiment was the Optimal Interpolation (OI) scheme. The time step in the assimilation scheme was 15 days, except in the melt season when no data were available.

The experiments performed in this study have shown that the synthetic observations of ice thickness have an error variance which is low enough to have a strong impact on the analyzed ice thickness fields in the analysis scheme. The experiments showed that only a few assimilation steps were required to obtain e-folding of the RMS distance between the modeled and the observed ice thickness field, using the original error variance of the observations, which represent a typical measurement sample error of 0.5 m. In this case the experiments showed that the data had a strong “pull” on the model state. Similar results were obtained for the experiments where the error variance was multiplied by a factor of 0.25 and 4. However, when this factor was increased to 100 (corresponding to a typical measurement sample error of ≈ 5 m), the experiments showed that it would take at least 20 analysis updates to obtain an e-folding of the RMS distance. This translates into 1500 days of model run to obtain the e-folding, not taking into account the melt period when no observations are available, indicating that the data had much weaker “pull” on the model state.

The conclusion of the assimilation experiments for ice thickness, with the given assimilation method and data updated every 15 days, is that a data field with measurement error of ≈ 1 m will have significant effect on the analyzed fields.

The assimilation experiments showed that also other variables were affected. For example when ice was introduced close to the marginal ice zone, SST was reduced and SSS was increased. Also ice concentration is updated, with higher values in the marginal ice zone and lower values in the interior of the Arctic, where ice thickness was increased. The OI method tries to estimate these error statistics by using an ensemble which is fixed in time, and with samples from a seasonal cycle of the model. The real error statistics for Arctic regions should be expected to show strong spatial and temporal variations related among other things to the positioning of the ice edge. Such behaviour cannot be correctly portrayed by the OI method.

This type of multivariate data assimilation scheme has, to our knowledge, not been used with ice variables before. The results are encouraging, and the shortcomings of the scheme is mainly due to the choice of the ensemble members. Future work should try to utilise a more realistic ensemble of members to better be able to describe the error covariance matrix. This will give more realistic updates for model fields associated to ice thickness through covariances in this matrix.

6.4 WHAT HAS BEEN LEARNT...?

On ice-ocean model simulations

The simulation of four decades of Arctic sea ice using the coupled ice –ocean model at NERSC forced by NCEP data, followed by extensive validation of the model results, shows that this coupled model is capable of reproducing the trends and variability of the sea ice quite well. The best validation data are two decades of ice extent and area provided by satellite passive microwave data. Ice thickness data, on the other hand, were much more difficult use in model validation because of the lack of systematically sampled data. Random profiles of ice thickness from submarine, however, indicated that the model ice thickness was reasonably good (mean correlation of ≈ 0.80).

Parallel model experiments with variable freshwater input to the Arctic Ocean, simulating the effect of reduced ice cover, were carried out to study the impact on the thermohaline circulation in the Arctic Ocean and the Nordic Seas. The experiments showed that the increased freshwater runoff in the Arctic is counteracted by increased northward transport of salt, tending to keep the thermohaline circulation stable.

On CryoSat instrument simulations

Realistic three-dimensional models of mixed ocean/sea ice topography and backscatter characteristics have been used to generate synthetic echo data for a ‘CryoSat’ type radar altimeter system. The data have been processed using a prototype ground processing system to obtain estimates of the surface elevation. By comparing the input and output elevations statistics an estimate of retrieval accuracy has been obtained for the different scenarios. The processor also provides estimates of the percentage of water and ice retrievals for each scenario. Using a number of different scenarios, the dependence of retrieval accuracy and percentage of retrievals on ice concentration, ice thickness and backscatter characteristics have been determined.

A zero order result of the study is that the simulations demonstrate the capability of a ‘CryoSat’ type instrument to retrieve ice and water elevation, and hence freeboard, estimates for a number of varying ice conditions likely to be encountered in the Arctic. The strongest dependence for the percentage of water and ice retrievals was on ice concentration. The ice elevation retrieval accuracy also showed a marked improvement with higher ice concentrations. No ice retrievals are obtained for a concentration of less than $\sim 70\%$. For ice elevation the backscatter contrast also had a marginal affect on retrieval accuracy but little affect on water retrievals. Variability of ice thickness had a marginal affect on water elevation retrievals but very little effect on ice elevation retrievals.

An annual cycle of synthetic CryoSat data was generated using realistic cryosat orbit and surface state fields from the NERSC model. The results indicate both seasonal and regional differences in percentage of data acquired and retrieval errors due to changing surface conditions. Loss of data due to melt season onset occurs during the second half of May and at the start of freeze-up in October low ice concentrations initially delay data acquisitions in the ice margins.

On assimilation of CryoSat-like data into ice-ocean model

The assimilation experiments for ice thickness, using the Optimal Interpolation method with data updated every 15 days, showed that a thickness data field with measurement error of ≈ 1 m will have significant effect on the analysed fields. Experiments using measurement error of ≈ 0.5 m, only needed a few assimilation steps to obtain e-folding of the RMS distance between the modelled and the observed ice thickness field, indicating a strong “pull” of the model state towards the observation fields.

On spatial and temporal requirements for CryoSat measurements

Based on the assimilation results we can assess CRYOSAT measurement requirements as follows: The error variances in ice thickness given as input to the assimilation experiments had a typical value of 0.5 m representing 1s measurements. This error reduces when averaging over a 10^5 km² box. According to the Cryosat documentation, which says you get approximately 3000 km of track in such a box then you would get ~ 400 measurements which reduces the error by a factor of ~ 20 . This turns an error of 0.5 m into 2.5 cm, similar to that quoted in the CryoSat proposal. These requirements on the CryoSat measurements will provide useful data for assimilation which have significantly impact on the performance of a coupled ice-ocean models as shown in Task 4.2.

6.5 LIMITATIONS OF CURRENT STUDY AND RECOMMENDATIONS FOR THE FUTURE

Generation of synthetic CRYOSAT data

- (i) The major limitation of this study concerns the realism of the error variances used which were determined using a very limited set of simulation scenarios (due to computational expense). The statistics generated were sufficient only to determine the dependency of retrieval errors on surface state to first order. A more comprehensive understanding of the errors and their interdependence may be achieved through a much larger set of simulations obtained, for example, by shifting the location and orientation of the satellite track in the current set.
- (ii) The current study used only prototype versions of the CryoSat simulator and the Payload Data Segment. As these components of the CryoSat system evolve the development of more realistic synthetic data sets could be considered although this would necessarily involve co-operation with the various elements of the CryoSat team and it's activities.
- (iii) The error statistics used to generate the synthetic data set depend on the surface state as determined by the NERSC model. The use of alternative sources, such as SSM/I to determine surface state parameters such as ice concentration and surface melt state could also be considered. The seasonal and regional variability of snow depth can also have a significant effect on retrievals and should be investigated further.

The assimilation exercise

There exist some uncertainty in the actual model error statistics for a data assimilation method such as Optimal Interpolation. Using a data assimilation scheme with an Ensemble Kalman Filter could give more correct statistics for the model error. However, for the model described in this study, using the EnKF will have a high demand on computer resources.

Recommendations

Improvements to the CryoSat simulations and synthetic data sets.

- (i) Simulations should be carried out using the more advanced CryoSat (CRYMPS) simulator in development at MSSL.
- (ii) More sophisticated ice/water discrimination and re-tracking procedures should be used in line with prototyping of the IPF software.
- (iii) More comprehensive retrieval error statistics should be obtained through ensemble (rather than single) runs over the different ice surface scenarios. In particular the location and orientation of the synthetic ground track should be varied.
- (iv) Observations of ice concentration and surface melting (from SSM/I and re-analyses data) should be used to prescribe changes in surface conditions likely to affect the retrievals on a daily basis.

Assimilation schemes:

The present experiments only represent an initial study, and more assimilation experiments are needed with other and more advanced assimilation schemes such as Ensemble Kalman Filter.

Appendix A

A	Thermodynamic calculations for water and sea ice	1
A.1	Appendix: Thermodynamic calculations for water and sea ice	1
A.1.1	Heat fluxes over Water, Ice and Snow-Covered Ice	1
A.1.2	Heat Budget for Sea Ice	4
A.1.3	The thermodynamics of a grid cell	5

Appendix A

Thermodynamic calculations for water and sea ice

A.1 Appendix: Thermodynamic calculations for water and sea ice

In the following, the thermodynamic computations are briefly described for open water, and for ice and snow covered grid cells (Drange, 1996).

A.1.1 Heat fluxes over Water, Ice and Snow-Covered Ice

The total surface flux Q^{tot} of heat to the marine surface consists of the net downward solar irradiance Q_s , the upward sensible heat flux Q_H , the upward latent heat flux Q_L and the net upward long wave radiation Q_l : $Q^{\text{tot}} = Q_s - Q_H - Q_L - Q_l$. The surface fluxes Q_s , Q_H , Q_L and Q_l are expressed in W m^{-2} , and $Q^{\text{tot}} > 0$ implies that heat is supplied to the marine surface.

Solar Irradiance Flux Q_s

The net downward solar irradiance Q_s that penetrates the marine surface layer is given by the irradiance at the surface Q_s^0 (provided by NCEP), with a correction for the surface albedo. The surface irradiance is split into two components; one for direct light and one for diffusive light, with the corresponding albedo coefficients α^{dir} and α^{dif} (in fractions of unity):

$$Q_s = Q_s^0 \left[(1 - \alpha_j^{\text{dir}}) (1 - C) + (1 - \alpha_j^{\text{dif}}) C \right]. \quad (\text{A.1})$$

Here C is the total cloudiness in fractions of unity (from NCEP), the subscript j denotes whether the marine surface layer consists of open water ($j = w$), ice ($j = i$) or snow ($j = s$). The numerical value or expression of the different physical and thermodynamic constants and parameterizations used in this study are listed in Table A1.

Surface albedo

The surface albedo over open water for the diffusive and direct component of the irradiance field is parameterized by the dimensionless parameters α_w^{dif} and α_w^{dir} , respectively. In

Table A.1: Overview of the physical constants and parameters used in the thermodynamical module.

Quantity	Symbol	Value/Expression	Unit
Albedo over ice (ice thickness dependent)	α_i	Eq. A.3	–
Albedo over snow	α_s	0.75	–
Albedo for melting snow	α_{sm}	0.50	–
Albedo for melting ice	α_{im}	0.50	–
Albedo over water for diffusive light	$\alpha_{w, dif}$	0.065	–
Albedo over water for direct light	$\alpha_{w, dir}$	Eq. A.2	–
Density of ice	ρ_i	900	kg m ⁻³
Emissivity of ice, snow and water	$\varepsilon_{i, s, w}$	0.97	–
Gas constant	R	2.87×10^2	Pa m ³ K ⁻¹ kg ⁻¹
Heat of fusion of ice	Q_i	3.02×10^8	J m ⁻³
Heat of fusion of snow	Q_s	1.10×10^8	J m ⁻³
Ice conductivity	k_i	2.04	W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹
Latent heat of vaporization	L_w	2.5×10^6	J kg ⁻¹
Latent heat transfer coefficient	c_L	(Isemer <i>et al.</i> , 1989)	–
Maximum fractional ice cover	F^{\max}	0.99	–
Melting point of ice	$T_{i, mlt}$	273.05	K
Melting point of snow	$T_{s, mlt}$	273.15	K
Minimum thickness of newly formed ice	$h_{i, min}$	0.6	m
Molecular weight of water vapor to that of dry air	ε	0.622	–
Sea ice salinity	S_i	10	per mil
Sensible heat transfer coefficient	c_H	$= 0.94 c_L$	–
Snow conductivity	k_s	0.31	W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹
Specific heat of dry air at constant pressure	$c_{p, air}$	1004	J K ⁻¹ kg ⁻¹
Specific heat of sea water	c_p	3987	J K ⁻¹ kg ⁻¹
Surface pressure	p	10^5	Pa
Stefan-Boltzman constant	σ	5.67×10^{-8}	W m ⁻² K ⁻⁴

accordance with observations we have set the open water albedo for diffusive light α_w^{dif} equal to 0.065 (Payne (1972), Section 2.5 in Kirk (1983) and Roemmich (1992)), and for the direct component of the light we use the zenith angle dependent formula proposed by Roemmich (1992),

$$\alpha_w^{\text{dir}} = \max\left(0.15, \frac{0.05}{\cos z + 0.15}\right). \quad (\text{A.2})$$

For young ice, the albedo strongly depends on the ice thickness h_i . In order to include this effect, the ice albedo adopted in this study is taken from Maykut (1982)

$$\alpha_i = 0.08 + 0.44h_i^{0.28}. \quad (\text{A.3})$$

In the case of a snow cover on the ice and surface temperatures below freezing, the surface albedo is set to α_s . In the melting season the albedo may change considerably due to the occurrence of melt ponds, which may cover up to 50% of the ice in July (Maykut, 1982). If the surface temperature exceeds the freezing temperature, the albedo is set equal to the albedo of melting ice and snow, α_{im} and α_{sm} , respectively.

Sensible Heat Flux Q_H

The upward sensible heat flux has been estimated by means of the standard bulk formula (e.g. page 30 in Gill (1982))

$$Q_H = \rho_{\text{air}} c_{p,\text{air}} c_H W (T_{\text{srf}} - T_{\text{air}}). \quad (\text{A.4})$$

Here ρ_{air} (kg m^{-3}) and $c_{p,\text{air}}$ ($\text{J kg}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$) are the density of air and specific heat of dry air at constant pressure, respectively, c_H (dimensionless) is the sensible heat transfer coefficient, W (m s^{-1}) is the NCEP surface wind speed, and T_{srf} and T_{air} (both in K) are the simulated marine surface temperature and NCEP air temperature, respectively.

The numerical value of the sensible heat transfer coefficient in equation (A.4) is taken from Tab. 2 in Isemer *et al.* (1989), and depends on the wind speed and the stability of the atmospheric boundary layer.

Latent Heat Flux Q_L

The latent heat flux has been estimated by means of the standard bulk formula (e.g. page 30 in Gill (1982))

$$Q_L = \rho_{\text{air}} L_j c_L W \max(0, q_{\text{srf}} - q_{\text{air}}). \quad (\text{A.5})$$

Here L_j (J kg^{-1}) is the latent heat of vaporization (over water) or of sublimation (over ice and snow), c_L (dimensionless) is the latent heat transfer coefficient, and q_{srf} and q_{air} (both dimensionless) are the specific humidities at the marine surface and in air, respectively. The specific humidities in air are computed using the Comprehensive Ocean and Atmosphere Data Set (COADS) (Slutz *et al.*, 1985) merged with values from Table 1 in Maykut (1978). The max-function ensures that negative evaporation does not occur (Kleeman and Power, 1995).

The latent heat transfer coefficient is proportional to the sensible heat coefficient, $c_L = c_H/0.94$ (Isemer *et al.*, 1989), and thus depends on the wind speed and the stability of the atmospheric boundary layer. The specific humidities are functions of the water vapor pressure e and the surface pressure p (e.g. page 41 in Gill (1982)), both in Pa.

For completion, it can be mentioned that the evaporation rate E (m s^{-1}) over open water follows from the expression of the latent heat flux: $E = Q_L/(L_w \rho)$, where ρ (kg m^{-3}) is the density of sea water.

Net Long Wave Radiation Flux Q_l

The expression for the net outgoing long wave radiation Q_l is based on the parameterizations of Efimova (1961), as recommended by Budyko (1974):

$$Q_l = f_{l1}^Q + f_{l2}^Q T_{\text{srf}}, \quad (\text{A.6})$$

where

$$f_{l1}^Q = \varepsilon_w \sigma T_{\text{air}}^4 \left[\left(0.254 - 4.95 \times 10^{-5} e(T_{\text{air}}) \right) \right. \quad (\text{A.7})$$

$$\left. \times \left(1 - \chi C^{1.2} \right) - 4 \right], \quad (\text{A.8})$$

and

$$f_{l2}^Q = 4 \varepsilon_w \sigma T_{\text{air}}^3. \quad (\text{A.9})$$

In the above expressions, ε_j (dimensionless) is the emissivity of water ($j = w$), ice ($j = i$) and snow ($j = s$); σ ($\text{W m}^{-2} \text{K}^{-4}$) is the Stefan-Boltzman constant; and $e(T_{\text{air}})$ (Pa) is the vapour pressure evaluated at the air temperature. Observations by M. E. Berliand, cited in Budyko (1974), indicate that the factor χ in equation (A.8) varies linearly with latitude. From Tab. 8 in Budyko (1974), we get that

$$\chi = 0.5 + 0.246 |\phi|, \quad (\text{A.10})$$

where ϕ (rad) is latitude. The exponent 1.2 occurring in the cloudiness correction factor in equation (A.8) is taken from Isemer *et al.* (1989), Budyko (1974) suggests an exponent between 1 and 2.

A.1.2 Heat Budget for Sea Ice

Ice surface

The net heat flux supplied to the top of the ice ($j = i$) or snow ($j = s$) layer is described by equation (A.1), and additionally the conductive heat transfer across the ice/snow-air interface:

$$Q_j^{\text{top}} = Q_s - Q_H - Q_L - Q_l + f^c (T_f - T_{\text{srf}}). \quad (\text{A.11})$$

Here f^c (W K^{-1}) is a conductivity factor, and T_{srf} (K) is the temperature at the ice-air interface. Assuming linear temperature profiles in the ice and snow and a balance of heat fluxes at the snow-ice interface, the effective conductivity factor of the combined snow-ice slab becomes

$$f^c = \frac{k_i k_s}{k_s h_i + k_i h_s}. \quad (\text{A.12})$$

Here k_j is the conductivity ($\text{W m}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$) and h_j is the thickness of ice ($j = i$) or snow ($j = s$). Note that all components of equation (A.11) are linear functions of T_{srf} , equation (A.11) and the condition for a balanced heat flux budget, $Q_i^{\text{top}} = 0$, can then be easily solved for T_{srf} . (This solution procedure does not take into account that the surface specific humidity that enters the expression of Q_L depends on the surface temperature. To correct for this, an iterative solution procedure has to be applied.)

Ice bottom

The heat flux at the bottom of the ice layer consists of two parts: One part that is caused by a mixed layer temperature different from that of freezing sea water and one part that is caused by the conductive transfer of heat through the ice cover.

If an ice cover exists, the mixed layer temperature T_{ml} equals the freezing point of sea water T_f (both in K) at the end of each time step. During the following time step of length Δt (s), the mixed layer temperature may deviate from the freezing point of sea water as a result of advection of warm water or vertical mixing of water masses across the base of the mixed layer. The heat (in W m^{-2}) supplied to the bottom of the ice layer for $T_{\text{ml}} \neq T_f$ equals

$$\frac{c_p \rho h_{\text{ml}}}{\Delta t} (T_{\text{ml}} - T_f). \quad (\text{A.13})$$

In the above expression, c_p ($\text{J K}^{-1} \text{kg}^{-1}$) is the specific heat of sea water, whereas ρ and h_{ml} are the density and the mixed layer thickness, respectively.

The total heat Q_i^{bot} (W m^{-2}) supplied to the bottom of the ice layer is then given as

$$Q_i^{\text{bot}} = \frac{c_p \rho h_{\text{ml}}}{\Delta t} (T_{\text{ml}} - T_f) + f_i^c (T_{\text{srf}} - T_f) \quad (\text{A.14})$$

If $Q_i^{\text{bot}} > 0$, the ice layer is melted from below, and if $Q_i^{\text{bot}} < 0$, the thickness of the ice layer increases.

A.1.3 The thermodynamics of a grid cell

A grid cell generally consists of both ice and open water, and we let F denote the fraction of ice present at the start of a time step. The following describes the procedure taken during a time step (Δt) when calculating the final thermodynamical state of a grid cell.

Ice Covered Fraction of Grid Cell

The sum Q_j^{top} of the net downward heat flux at the top of the ice or snow layer is given by equation (A.11), whereas the heat flux Q_i^{bot} supplied to the ice-water interface is given by equation (A.14). Ice is then melted or frozen according to the following: If the calculated surface temperature exceeds the melting temperature of snow or ice, T_j^{melt} , the surface temperature is set equal to this temperature. This results in an imbalance between the fluxes at the surface resulting in $Q_j^{\text{top}} > 0$, and snow and ice is melted accordingly. If snow is present it is melted before any ice is melted.

At the bottom of the ice, ice is frozen or melted according to the heat flux given by equation (A.14). As ice melts, remaining snow is transformed into ice, and the remaining energy is used to melt this ice as well. In case the ice is totally melted, the remaining energy is used to heat the mixed layer water in the initially ice-covered fraction F of the grid cell.

Finally, if there is a fraction F of ice in a grid cell and the heat flux into the initially open water part of the grid cell $Q_w^{\text{top}} > 0$, then the ice concentration will be reduced over the time step (lateral melt). The energy going into the initially open water fraction of the grid cell equals $(1 - F)Q_w^{\text{top}} \Delta t$, and of this energy the fraction F is used to melt ice laterally while the fraction $(1 - F)$ is used to heat the mixed layer in the initial open water part of the grid cell (see section A.1.3 below).

The salinity and mixed layer thickness is updated by conserving the salinity and total mass of the ice, snow and mixed layer system for the initially ice covered part of the grid cell.

Open Water fraction of a grid cell

The net heat flux Q_w^{top} over open water leads to the updated ocean surface (and mixed layer) temperature

$$T'_{\text{srf}} = T_{\text{srf}} + (1 - F H(Q_w^{\text{top}})) \frac{Q_w^{\text{top}} \Delta t}{c_p \rho h_{\text{ml}}}. \quad (\text{A.15})$$

Where $H(x)$ is the step function ($H(x) = 0 \forall x < 0$, $H(x) = 1 \forall x \geq 0$), introduced to include the effect of lateral melt (see section A.1.3 above), and T_{srf} is the initial mixed layer temperature. The mixed layer temperature is not allowed to go below the freezing temperature T_f of sea water. If equation (A.15) predicts a new water temperature below T_f , a fraction δ of the time step Δt is used to cool the mixed layer until $T'_{\text{srf}} = T_f$. The remaining part of the time step $(1 - \delta)\Delta t$ is then used to laterally freeze new ice of thickness $h_{i,\text{min}}$. If the ice fraction exceeds the limit F^{max} , the ice fraction is set to F^{max} and the ice thickness is increased until the heat budget is closed.

Once the newly frozen ice and fractional ice cover have been determined, conservation of mass and salinity for the ice and mixed layer system give the new mixed layer depth and salinity for the initial open water fraction of the grid cell.

Final Thermodynamic State of the Grid Cell

The final state of the mixed layer and ice for the grid cell is calculated according to mass weighted conservation formulas with contributions from the initially ice covered (F) and open water ($1 - F$) fraction of the grid cell.